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(edited by)

THE EVOLVING CONCEPT OF 'SCHOOL LIBRARY' AND ITS PROFESSION

Luisa Marquardt, Giovanni Moretti e Arianna L. Morini
(Eds.)

International Seminar on
**The Evolving Concept of ‘School Library’
and Its Profession**

Organised by the
Department of Education, Roma Tre University,
and the IFLA School Libraries Section Standing Committee,
with
AIB, Biblioteche di Roma, Forum del Libro, IASL, IBBY Italia
and the collaboration of Ledizioni, OCLC and MLOL Scuola

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The International Seminar was to be held in presence on 2 April 2020, at and in collaboration with the “Polo didattico” of the Department of Education. Due to the health emergency caused by COVID-19, it was held virtually through the dedicated "ecosliprof" blog (<https://ecosliprof.blogspot.com/>) and YouTube channel "EcosliProf".

The digital version of the proceedings is available in OA on the Torrossa platform and the IFLA Repository.

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Introduction,¹ by Massimiliano Fiorucci²

The International Seminar on ‘The Evolving Concept of ‘School Library’ and Its Profession’ was originally planned to be held on the 2nd of April 2020, at the Department of Education of Roma Tre University, within the IFLA School Libraries Section Mid-Year Meeting Initiatives (that were about to take place in Rome March 30-April 6, 2020 and have been postponed to 2021).

Due to the global pandemic of the COVID-19, and following - on the one hand - the WHO’s instructions and the containment measures by the Italian Government, and - on the other hand - the request and expectations of many colleagues and school library professionals, the International Seminal Meeting was therefore turned into a ‘virtual’ one. This ‘virtual’ International Seminal Meeting aims at gathering Worldwide and Italian scholars’ and experts’ contributions on new ways - through dynamic library spaces, attractive and interesting collections, stimulating school library programs and initiatives, strategic collaboration etc. - that school libraries, their professionals and associations are currently carrying on to address several issues (e.g., declining reading literacy, curriculum implementation, insufficient global competences etc.).

Although the direct interaction and discussion with experts and scholars will be missing, most of the experts and speakers’ contributions are available in this blog³ in a PPT presentation format and/or video. Further comments, reflections, exchange of experiences etc. are welcome and will constitute the base for the next school library meeting (to be held on April 15, 2021).

In the hard times we are living and experiencing new and unexpected challenges, we bear very clearly in our mind that we have to turn disadvantages into advantages, difficulties into opportunities. We

¹ Translation by Luisa Marquardt.

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³ <https://ecosliprof.blogspot.com/>

therefore do believe that, although in this unconventional mode, this 'seminal meeting' provides to those who are interested in the topics with a good opportunity to benefit from the experts' research, suggestions, etc., and also a way to face the hard situation that recently emerged and is still going on.

New challenges, a new historical frame, new conditions of life are in front of us: education and library science, universities, schools, kindergartens and nursery schools, different types of libraries, and their practitioners have to find innovative and effective ways of preparing and serving the 21st Century new generations and enable them to find their own way and place in our interconnected and complex world. Best wishes of a fruitful exchange of research findings, experiences, ideas!

The IFLA School Libraries Section, by Joanne Plante⁴

I am Joanne Plante, Chair of the IFLA School Libraries Section, and I was looking forward to meeting you in person to learn about the situation of school libraries in Italy and libraries in general. Unfortunately, life decided otherwise.

During our meeting, we would have had the opportunity to talk about the new IFLA-UNESCO Manifesto for School Libraries. For at least two years, the IFLA School Libraries Section and IASL have in fact been working with school librarians from all over the world on this pillar for school libraries. Two years ago, at the Section meeting in Kuala Lumpur, we voted to update this text, which is often used in other documents to promote our work. So we launched a global call so that we could update it. We received many comments that Katy Manck, President of IASL, and myself read, classified and turned into texts to update our *Manifesto*. I would like to take this opportunity to thank IASL and especially Katy Manck, the school librarians, teachers and all those involved in the world of school libraries who have taken the time to make comments to ensure that the new document is up to date. Our Section is currently commenting on the first draft of the *School Library Manifesto*. We will make this document public in the months to come to have a further opportunity to comment on it before arriving at the final version. I would particularly like to thank Luisa Marquardt for the work she did to make this seminar happen anyway and for believing in it right to the end. My thanks for the commitment to this initiative go to the Department of Education of Roma Tre University, its Director and the Scientific and Organising Committees, the various Partners, the sponsors MLOL Scuola and OCLC, the willing participants, the IASL and the IFLA School Libraries Section, whose Mid-Year Meeting in person (with a new seminar) is postponed to April 2021. Hope to see you next year!

⁴ Joanne Plante, Head of Laure-Conan Library, Optimization of Operations, Laval (Montreal, Canada), and Chair of the IFLA School Libraries Section. E-mail: joanneplante@gmail.com.

School Libraries and Librarians: Between 'Inspirations' and 'Aspirations'. Presentation of the International Seminar, by Luisa Marquardt⁵

Abstract

The International Seminar, jointly organised by IFLA and the Department of Education of Roma Tre University, with the collaboration of other organizations, aimed to offer an opportunity for reflection and exchange for those involved in the school library as an educational and inclusive environment. The focus was on information education, reading promotion (including digital reading), and collaboration between schools and the local community to provide a qualified and integrated offering of information, reading, and opportunities for personal, cultural, and social growth. A professionally managed school library has positive effects on the quality of learning. However, particularly in countries without a specific legal framework, school libraries and their staff often need to legitimize their function. The various contributions were intended to offer theoretical insights and practical experiences to inspire those in charge of (or with competence over) school libraries. The goal was to encourage them to aspire to raise the quality of library services and activities, including remote offerings. The seminar aimed to contribute to the implementation of the curriculum, broaden organized and qualified access to information, reading, and culture from a network perspective, and, more generally, to the acquisition of global and informational skills. Ultimately, the seminar sought to support the integral formation of individuals capable of navigating independently through informational and other complexities.

Keywords: school library; IFLA School Libraries Section; guidelines.

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Introduction

School librarianship can be seen as an intersection where the worlds of librarianship and education meet and nurture each other. For this intersection to be a fertile ground for exchange, it is crucial to have not only scientific and professional journals but also events like seminars and conferences. These occasions foster communication, discussion, reflection, and the development of joint projects among those involved in school libraries—whether for research purposes (such as scholars and researchers) or for institutional tasks (such as school administrators)—and those directly engaged in the service (e.g., school librarians, information specialists, teacher-librarians, volunteers, etc.).

During the IFLA⁶ Annual International Conference held in August 2019 in Athens,⁷ the author, as an elected member of the IFLA School Libraries Section, was entrusted with organizing the 'Mid-year Meeting,' a biannual meeting required for Sections. The location—Rome—and the period (end of March to the first week of April) were intentionally chosen to coincide with the International Children's Book Fair in Bologna and the Easter holidays. This timing aimed to offer participants not only the week of work for the Section but also the opportunity to visit the significant Book Fair.

The convergence of many authoritative members of the Section—including university lecturers and researchers, school librarians, and representatives of library institutions and associations—from various countries (Canada, Japan, France, the United Kingdom, Germany, Australia, etc.) in Rome presented an extraordinary opportunity to engage with various Italian communities (academic, professional, institutional, and voluntary). Thanks to the support of Roma Tre University, particularly its Department of Education (DSF), it was confirmed that the meeting would be held at the DSF teaching centre on Thursday, April 2, 2020. An international study seminar would also be conducted on the theme of the dynamic nature of the school library concept and the evolving profession of school librarian-information specialist.

⁶ International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, <http://www.ifla.org>.

⁷ see IFLA WLIC 2019, <https://2019.ifla.org/>

The IFLA School Libraries Section

The IFLA School Libraries Section was established in 1977 with the aim of promoting the development of school libraries and educational resource centres worldwide and, in particular, the employment of qualified and trained staff as a crucial factor in raising the quality of school library services. The Section provides an international forum for the exchange of ideas, experiences and research results in the field of school libraries. Over the years, the Section has produced research and publications with the aim of providing a reference point and useful tools (such as the *Manifesto* and the various editions of the Guidelines) for anyone interested in school libraries.

Communication tools include the Section's web pages, the 'School-L' mailing list, and the blog. In order to effectively achieve common goals, IASL and IFLA signed a three-year cooperation agreement⁸ in 2006; for the implementation of which the IASL-IFLA Joint Committee was established, whose activities resulted in important contributions to school librarianship, including the second edition of the Guidelines.⁹

Every year the Section carries out some institutional activities within the framework of two regular meetings: the World Library and Information Congress (IFLA WLIC), which by statute is usually held in August, and the semi-annual meeting (the Mid-year or Mid-term Meeting) at a variable period of the year (usually between the end of February and the beginning of April).

In particular, this second initiative takes place in collaboration with specific organisations (universities, institutions, etc.) and associations that have expertise and/or interest in the school library sector, thus providing a valuable opportunity for the IFLA Section to meet the local reality, as was also the intention for the Seminar from which these Proceedings originated.

⁸ The actual implementation of the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) started in September 2009, after the IFLA WLIC in Milan and the 38th IASL Conference in Padova and Abano Terme.

⁹ IFLA School Libraries Section Standing Committee. (2015). *IFLA School Library Guidelines*. (B. Schultz-Jones, & D. Oberg, Eds.) <https://www.ifla.org/files/assets/school-libraries-resource-centers/publications/ifla-school-library-guidelines.pdf>

The International Seminar: Organization and Content

The International Seminar on 'The Evolving Concept of 'School Library' and Its Profession' (<https://ecosliprof.blogspot.com/>) was jointly organised by the Department of Education of Roma Tre University and the IFLA School Libraries Section, with AIB (the Italiana Library Association), Biblioteche di Roma (the public library network of Rome), Forum del Libro (i.e., Book Forum), IASL, IBBY Italy, and in collaboration with MLOL and OCLC. The seminar day, which initially also included an exhibition area, was intended to provide an opportunity for reflection and exchange for those involved in school libraries as an educational and inclusive environment, information education, promotion of reading (including digital reading), and collaboration between school and territory for a qualified and integrated offer of information, reading, and opportunities for personal, cultural and social growth. Studies and research (Ohio Study, Colorado Study, Invalsi etc.) show how a library that is professionally managed has positive effects on the quality of learning. Nonetheless, particularly in countries without a specific legal framework of reference (and Italy is among them), school libraries and their staff are constantly having to legitimise their function.

Innovative school libraries, their professionals, and professional associations are successfully experimenting with new methods and strategies. In various parts of the world, including Italy, studies and research are being conducted, and projects and experiments are underway to develop inviting and dynamic library spaces and collections—both printed and digital—that are attractive and meaningful for both the school curriculum and personal interests. These initiatives also include the provision of stimulating services and activity programs (accessible remotely as well), and the activation of strategic collaborations (e.g., with public libraries and various associations).

The goal is not just to enhance the school library itself but to elevate its educational function to address crucial issues such as the general decline in reading skills, difficulties in navigating information complexity, and the need for effective curriculum implementation. Through these efforts, the school library can contribute to the acquisition of global and informational skills, which are more essential today than ever before. Ultimately, this contributes to the holistic development of individuals, equipping them to navigate independently

through informational, digital, social, and work-related complexities, while actively engaging with their communities.

The seminar was structured into four sessions, each designed to offer theoretical insights and practical experiences to ‘inspire’ those involved with school libraries. The aim was to encourage participants to ‘aspire’ to raise the quality of library services and activities, including remote offerings. The specific goals of each session were:

- First Session: Chaired by the author, this session focused on implementing the curriculum in an effective and motivating way to improve students’ learning outcomes.
- Second Session: Chaired by Prof Giuseppe Carrus (Roma Tre University), this session addressed the creation of innovative school library spaces that are functional, safe, meaningful, attractive, and regenerative.
- Third Session: Chaired by Dr Flavia Cristiano, newly appointed President of IBBY Italy, this session focused on expanding reading materials (both paper and digital) and promoting diverse reading practices (shared and augmented).
- Fourth Session: Chaired by Prof Giovanni Moretti (Roma Tre University), this session discussed providing better opportunities for organized and qualified access to information, reading, and culture from a network perspective, through strategic alliances and the professionalism of those working in and with school libraries.

The seminar program, including the final drafting of the new Manifesto on school libraries, was to be complemented by a series of professional visits. These visits aimed to familiarize participants with some of Rome's key library and cultural institutions, including the National Central Library of Rome, the Joint Parliamentary Library (the Chamber of Deputies Library and the Senate Library), the ‘Luigi De Gregori’ Library of the Ministry of Education, the ‘Collina della Pace’ Library of the ‘Biblioteche di Roma’ network, the Vivona High School Library, the Cieri School Library of I.C. ‘Piersanti Mattarella’, the ‘Mauro Laeng’ Museum of School and Education, and several libraries of Roma Tre University.

The pandemic caused by Covid and the measures needed to contain it have unfortunately disrupted plans, forcing the cancellation of flights, stays and visits.

Technical Proof of Resilience

The severity and difficulties of the situation that emerged in early March 2020 were amplified not only by the necessary strictness of the measures, including the total lockdown of services and activities deemed non-essential and the ensuing economic crisis, but also by the general disorientation, numerous human losses, and the urgency of addressing unprecedented problems. Among these, for schools and universities, was the rapid transition to online teaching. Despite this, under the banner of ‘Roma Tre does not stop,’ efforts were made to ensure that the commitment put into the organization, and more generally into the week of work for the IFLA Section, and particularly the International Seminar, was not wasted. The latter thus became ‘virtual,’ and the website dedicated to the program and abstracts also became the portal for accessing presentations and video interventions. The even more tangible sign is represented by the final version of the contributions that are offered here, with the hope that the research outcomes, various practices, and projects described will serve as a useful stimulus and a valuable source of inspiration for further research, to improve the school library. For decision-makers, it is hoped this will help them understand how the school library should be considered an integral part of the school, curriculum, and community—not an additional or unnecessary expense, but a true investment for the future.

Innovating School Libraries: The Commitment and Leadership of Lourense H. Das and Fabrizio Melchiori, by Luisa Marquardt¹⁰

Abstract

Organizations of all kinds (institutions, associations, companies, etc.) and communities must find ways to accompany and, if possible, anticipate change, making innovation a continuous process and method. The innovation process applied to libraries fosters new ways to stimulate and facilitate meaningful learning (Bessant & Francis, 1999), utilizing library resources and opportunities to support creativity and innovation (Katsirikou & Sefertzi, 1999). The human and professional factor plays a pivotal role in driving change and innovation in any organization, including professional associations.

In recognition of their dedication, exemplary leadership, and innovative contributions to school librarianship and library documentation, the figures of two information and documentation professionals who significantly advanced the sector to enhance the quality and impact of learning are commemorated: Lourense H. Das and Fabrizio Melchiori, both of whom passed away prematurely in 2019.

Keywords: Das, Lourense Herma; Melchiori, Fabrizio; school librarianship; library associations; leadership role.

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Introduction

In a globalized and interconnected world, within societies characterized by complex dynamics and continual changes, spurred and accelerated by information and communication technologies, organizations of all kinds (institutions, associations, companies, etc.) and communities must find ways not only to adapt to change but ideally to anticipate it (Scott & Jaffe, 1998). Managing change, particularly in light of the current health emergency, is more challenging now than in the past (Magnani, 2020). It is therefore crucial to strike a dynamic equilibrium: maintaining organizational identity without becoming rigid and vulnerable to disintegration during crises, while also exploring new paths, embracing innovation as an ongoing process and method.

As argued by Gilley, Godek & Gilley (2009b), similar to the human body's instinctive and immune responses which can either resist or adapt to new conditions, the human and professional factor in any organization plays a pivotal role in fostering, hindering, or rejecting processes of change and innovation.

In order to ensure the sustainability of the organization, a culture of change is essential. Constructing this culture relies heavily on communication (Vodonik, 2018: 468) and the leadership role, which significantly impacts the effectiveness and success—or failure—of the change process (Gilley, McMillan & Gilley, 2009a; Nohe et al., 2013). It is crucial to ensure that human and professional resources are well-prepared—adequately informed, trained, and up-to-date—and possess a clear understanding of the process being initiated, actively involving them in the transformation.

Innovation in the Library World

When implemented in a library context, innovation processes not only aim to find new organizational or technological solutions but also facilitate the discovery of new methods to stimulate and enable meaningful learning (Bessant & Francis, 1999; Palfrey, 2016, particularly pp. 70 and 83-92). This aspect is especially important within the overall framework of the knowledge society paradigm and the perspective of lifelong learning. On the other hand, the library environment—rich in a wide range of information and documents, flexible in adapting to user needs, and capable of fostering interaction—promotes creative and innovative processes. It provides users, each with their own background and viewpoints, with optimal

conditions to collaborate towards a common goal using a variety of sources and tools (Katsirikou & Sefertzi, 1999).

This holds particularly true for school and university libraries, which are integral to learning and research processes. Bell (2019), reflecting on Goldie Blumestyk's contribution regarding change in universities,¹¹ notes that in most libraries, innovation tends to be gradual¹²—a form that avoids major risks. Evolutionary innovation¹³ involves greater investment but, where a culture of change is established, staff generally adapt to new developments without difficulty. Radical innovation,¹⁴ which positions the library as a leading entity within an organization or community, is less common. It would be simplistic to view innovation solely through technological lenses, as new scenarios

richiedono, ancora prima dell'acquisizione di competenze tecniche, l'innalzamento dei livelli di consapevolezza sociale, di partecipazione, di responsabilità, di riflessività, di agentività nella realizzazione dei propri progetti di vita personali e professionali (Costa, 2016: 43), i.e.:
demand an elevation of social awareness, participation, responsibility, reflexivity, and agency in pursuing personal and professional life projects even before technical skills are acquired (Costa, 2016: 43 – Author's translation).

Especially in this particular historical moment, libraries are challenged to seek innovative solutions—sometimes not merely gradual—to address unprecedented situations such as those arising from the pandemic. They can turn crises into opportunities for growth. Consequently, it becomes crucial for librarians to 'focus on what digital media and the Internet make possible, rather than on what they destroy' (Palfrey, 2016: 18).

Many librarians, not only professionally prepared but also passionate about their work, are committed to **'improving society by facilitating**

¹¹ Blumenstyk, G. (2019, October 13). What Real Change Looks Like: Experts offer three guiding principles of innovation. *The Chronicle of Higher Education*. <https://www.chronicle.com/article/what-real-change-looks-like/>

¹² Introduzione di modifiche a un servizio esistente (cfr. Bell, 2019).

¹³ Introduzione di nuovi servizi rivolti a un pubblico esistente o di servizi esistenti a un nuovo pubblico (cfr. Bell, 2019).

¹⁴ Per esempio, l'introduzione di nuovi servizi per un nuovo pubblico. Su questo punto, Bell invita a essere molto prudenti e a valutare bene costi e benefici che un cambiamento radicale comporta.

the **creation of knowledge** within their reference **communities**¹⁵ (Lankes, 2014, p. 23), transforming and making their reference communities (university, school, educational, etc.) more inclusive and better. This commitment extends to the professional associations they belong to. It is no coincidence that Lankes urges librarians to be ‘engaged and innovative’ (ibid, p. 120) and

to continually and proactively scrutinize our profession and affiliated organizations to find opportunities for positive change (ibid).

This approach challenges tradition: ‘supporting what works and innovating (or eliminating) the rest’ (ibid). Actively engaging in their communities and professional associations is therefore an important aspect of professionalism. This commitment often goes beyond strictly professional dimensions: based on their expertise and personal qualities, members can significantly contribute to the development and transformation of their professional associations.

In this regard, the dedication of two professionals in the world of school libraries and library associations—Lourense H. Das and Fabrizio Melchiori, who were nearly contemporaries and both passed away prematurely in 2019—is a testament. They are briefly remembered here for their significant human and professional contributions to school librarianship and library documentation, and to their respective associations.

The seminar ‘The Evolving Concept of ‘School Library’ and Its Profession,’ structured at both international and national levels for a fruitful exchange of reflections and experiences, was dedicated to their memory.

Lourense H. Das

Lourense H. Das (Hilversum, 30/03/1956 - Baexem, 21/02/2019) was trained as a librarian at the ‘Frederik Muller Akademie’ of the University of Amsterdam, specializing later in school librarianship. Her educational background encompassed librarianship, information technology, digital documentation (University of Amsterdam,

Figure 1. Lourense H. Das at the DoE – Roma Tre University (Photo: LuiMar 2009)

¹⁵ Italics and bold are in the original text.

2003), and no-profit organization management (University of Tilburg, 2009-2010). She embarked on her professional career as a librarian at an agricultural college, followed by roles such as provincial advisor for school libraries (Roemond, 1979-1981), research assistant at Maastricht University (1981-1983), archivist and management secretary (Roermont, 1985-1988), and school information specialist (Brunssum, 1988-1998). Concurrently, she served as chairperson of the Regional Working Group on School Libraries (1994-1999). From 1995, she managed 'Meles Meles',¹⁶ focusing particularly on the school library sector (development of services, staff training, etc.).

From 1996 to 2005, she edited the professional periodicals 'Dossier Kennis & Media' and 'Studiehuis' (NBD/Biblion BV), and from 1998 to 2012, she worked as a consultant for the Information Centre of the Maastricht School of Management. Her intense commitment to association work was not insignificant: for LWSVO, the association of school librarians in the Netherlands (2000-2005), IASL, the International Association of School Librarianship, of which she was 'Director Europe' (2003-2009), IFLA, of whose School Libraries and Resource Centres Section she was Secretary (2005-2007), NVB, the Netherlands Library Association (2005-2008).

Figure 2. Promotional poster of 'Meles Meles' School Library Service

It is not possible to mention the long series of numerous meetings, conferences, and conventions that Lourense organized¹⁷ or collaborated on at both national and international levels. The author of

¹⁶ 'Meles Meles' is the scientific term for the common badger in the Linnean classification, in Dutch 'Das', Lourense's surname. The badger was therefore chosen as the logo and mascot of many promotional materials (flyers, bookmarks, etc.) through which, in an original and appealing manner, Lourense Das constantly conveyed a new idea of the school library, linked above all to its educational function.

¹⁷ Among which 'The School Library Rocks: living it, learning it, loving it', the 44th International Annual Conference of IASL, held in Maastricht from June 28 to July 2, 2015. <https://iasl-online.org/2015-Conference-Proceedings>.

this chapter vividly remembers, with enthusiasm and emotion, the so-called ‘Amsterdam Meeting,’ magnificently organized by Lourense Das, with the invaluable assistance of her late husband Albert Dohmen and the support of Helen Boelens.¹⁸ During those days of intense study and work in March 2003, experts from various European and non-European countries discussed and debated the topic of school libraries. It was during this meeting that the ‘European Network for School Libraries and Information Literacy’ (ENSIL) was established, and the Amsterdam Declaration was formulated to affirm students' right not only to access information but also to information literacy education, aiming to achieve a commendable level of information literacy to confidently address various problematic aspects.

Without overlapping with the activities of IASL and IFLA, but rather complementing and expanding them, ENSIL (initially as a spontaneous group, later from 2008 as a ‘Stichting,’ i.e., foundation), under the coordination of Lourense Das, has represented a reference and networking point at the European level for those involved in school libraries as learning environments, particularly focusing on their educational role in information literacy (Das, 2011).

Figure 3. The ALIES Campaign in South Africa – Cover page of «The Equalizer», (March 2012, No. 5)

Lourense staunchly advocated for the promotion of school libraries, conceptualizing the advocacy campaign ‘ALIES - A Library In Every School,’ which inspired the twin Italian campaign ‘BIOS - una Biblioteca In Ogni Scuola’ (Marquardt, Perego & Soria, 2012). She also initiated the ‘ALIES’ campaign in Africa, adopted by Equal Education,¹⁹ a

¹⁸ Helen Boelens, PhD, at the time a librarian at Kalsbeek College, a secondary school in Woerden, drew inspiration from the discussions and contacts during the Amsterdam Meeting for her doctoral research. See Boelens, H. (2010). *The evolving role of the school library and information centre in education in digital Europe: A thesis submitted to Middlesex University in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy*. London: Middlesex University.

<http://eprints.mdx.ac.uk/7329/><https://eprints.mdx.ac.uk/7329/>.

¹⁹ <https://equaleducation.org.za>.

non-governmental organization active in South Africa, which mobilized students, teachers, librarians, writers, etc., in marches advocating for quality school libraries in every school. Concurrently, she initiated the network of African school libraries and, with Cosmas Mabeza, founded 'Bookery,'²⁰ a book lottery whose proceeds fund the purchase of new books for school libraries, establishment of new libraries, or renovation of existing ones, and training of library staff.

Equally generous and dynamic was her commitment to contributing to numerous initiatives in various countries, including Italy,²¹ and to

Figure 4. The ALIES Campaign in South Africa – 'The Bookery'.

training, professionally updating, motivating, and supporting many young school librarians in different parts of the world (for example, Tanzania and South Africa²²). Among her many accolades, Lourense Das²³ earned the IASL School Librarianship Award in 2008 for her dedication to school librarianship, and in 2009, specifically in the field of innovation, she received the NOT Innovation Award (Utrecht) and the MKB-L1mburg Innovation Award for

²⁰ An initiative strongly and actively supported by Lourense Das herself and by the author. See: <https://equaleducation.org.za/campaigns/libraries-and-the-bookery/>. Nowadays it is an independent dynamic organization, whose motto is: 'Every child deserves to experience the joy and the power of reading'. <https://thebookery.org.za/>.

²¹ For example, in Milan in 2007 at the 'Convegno delle Stelline' (Das, 2007), and in 2009, first at the 'Convegno delle Stelline' on March 13th in the session 'School library between reading and research in the learning society,' and later at the IFLA WLIC (World Library and Information Congress) from August 23-27 (<https://www.ifla.org/past-wlic/2009/>), at events of AIB in Florence and Rome (for instance, 'Bibliocom 2003'), and multiple times at Roma Tre University.

²² The author remembers the stimulating experience shared in the townships and workshops at the universities of Johannesburg and Cape Town, in November 2011. See, for instance, <https://equaleducation.org.za/2011/11/07/debate-on-school-libraries-in-south-africa/>.

²³ As the Secretary of IFLA School Libraries Section, Lourense Das edited the content of the May 2006 issue (<http://archive.ifla.org/VII/s11/news/school-newsletter42.pdf>), awarded with the 'IFLA Best Newsletter 2006 Award' as the most information-rich and creative newsletter.

'FacTotem2.0,'²⁴ an advanced technological solution aimed at enhancing learning outcomes through modern media and the social world of students, emphasizing how they collaborate and utilize information in today's multimedia environment.²⁵

In the field of school librarianship, it was thanks to Lourense Das, in close collaboration with Professor Donatella Lombello and the author,

Figure 5. Lourense H. Das (in the middle), recipient of the NOT Innovation Award (Photo: LuiMar, 2009).

that the 38th Annual International Conference of IASL²⁶ was brought to Italy for the first time in 2009. This event led to a closer and more fruitful collaboration with the IFLA School Libraries Section.²⁷ It was a significant opportunity for meeting and exchanging ideas among

representatives of various library associations, experts, and school library

practitioners from Italy and around the world. The conference was rich with stimulating scientific and professional contributions, as well as many cultural and social moments that further strengthened professional and personal relationships, leaving an indelible memory.

The passing of the baton, which occurred during the elections held at the 38th IASL Conference, from Lourense Das to the author as 'Director Europe for IASL,' has since taken on deeper and more

²⁴ The author confirms the enormous interest generated by this innovation during the 'Didactiekbeurs' in Utrecht.

²⁵ This is an ergonomic multimedia workstation loaded with high-quality websites and resources essential for learning. See the information brochure at URL <https://issuu.com/melesmeles/docs/2010factotem2-0-documentatie-update>

²⁶ <https://iasl-online.org/2009-Conference-Proceedings>.

²⁷ The agreement between IASL and the IFLA School Libraries Section, signed in Lisbon in 2006, had remained largely inactive. The 38th Conference was crucial in initiating very concrete joint actions between IASL and IFLA, such as the development of a self-learning package dedicated to school libraries under the IFLA 'BSLA'- i.e. Building Strong Library Associations-campaign, <https://www.ifla.org/bsla/training-package>

profound meanings over time. This encourages us to cherish the many professional and personal lessons learned and to carry forward her significant legacy.

Fabrizio Melchiori

Fabrizio Melchiori (Rome, 15/02/1955 - 08/07/2019, Fig. 6), an eclectic personality, after earning his degree in Psychology, specialized in Semiotics and Communication Theory, and in Philosophy of Language. He worked as an information and school documentation operator, and also specialized in managing multimedia school libraries.

He directed the Documentation Centre at 'Liceo Machiavelli' in Rome and, with the aim of enhancing school documentation and promoting knowledge of the local reality, he promoted various projects. These included the research project 'Kleffler, Centurini, il quartiere Macao e il capitalismo italiano',²⁸ where he actively participated by coordinating research and organizing study days²⁹ (Fig. 7) and exhibitions (Melchiori & Conte, 2012). He also collaborated in reorganizing part of the school archive.

It is noteworthy Fabrizio Melchiori's commitment to integrating three realities of his school - the historical archive, the school library, and the documentation centre. These were modest representatives of much more substantial and historical 'knowledge infrastructures' in the area,

Figure 6. Fabrizio Melchiori.

²⁸ The author reported on this during the conference 'I beni culturali della scuola: problemi di conservazione e di valorizzazione', i.e., School Cultural Heritage: Issues of Conservation and Enhancement, organized by the University of Pavia and held in Cremona on September 26th and 27th, 2007 (Marquardt, 2008). Furthermore, the author carried on these activities in the academic year 2008-09, using it as a methodology for research and 'reading' of the local area. <https://www.slideshare.net/marquardt/marquardt-pres-presentation>

²⁹ See, for instance, the meeting 'Il Villino Centurini e il quartiere Macao', i.e., The Villino Centurini and the Macao Borough, the 2nd study day held at Istituto Machiavelli on June 24th, 2010.

<http://www.ismachavielli.eu/pags/spip.php?article453&date=2019-07>

yet they served as an important and fundamental ‘gym’ readily accessible to students for their educational development.

He was an Adjunct Professor in ‘Library and Information Science’ at the Department of Educational of Roma Tre University and a close collaborator of the author, particularly in the field of media and information literacy education, as detailed later. Fabrizio Melchiori also taught as a contract lecturer in the First-level Master's program in Library Science ‘From Paper to Digital: Information, Research, Knowledge’ at Niccolò Cusano Online University.

Figure 7. Poster of the 2nd Study Day on The Macao Borough – Rome, June 4, 2010. (Particular.)

In terms of professional associations, Fabrizio Melchiori was actively involved in AIB (Italian Library Association), where he had been a member since 2000, holding various positions: member of the Work Observatory - School sector and Regional Coordinator for School Libraries,³⁰ Coordinator of the Communication Group for the Librarian Profession (GCPB), and finally a member of the AIB Lazio Regional Executive Committee (2003-2008). Fabrizio Melchiori was also a driving force in several communities, including the Nahima Foundation for intercultural and interreligious dialogue, where he served on the Scientific Committee. He was involved with information specialists associated with the now dissolved AIDA - Italian

³⁰ He had indeed dedicated specific studies and contributions to the figure of the librarian and school libraries (see, for example, Melchiori, 2002).

Association of Advanced Documentation (of which he was a member since 2003), various groups of scholars and librarians engaged in information literacy initiatives, and of course, his own school community, where many students and former students have provided positive feedback over the years on the effectiveness of his information and documentation education activities.

Fabrizio Melchiori was also deeply involved in digital rights, co-authoring with Alessandro Rossi the *Carta internazionale dei diritti digitali*, i.e. the International Charter of Digital Rights (Rossi & Melchiori, 2014), presented in Rome during ‘SIA2014’³¹ and incorporated into the *Dichiarazione dei diritti in internet*, Declaration of Rights in the Internet (Camera dei Deputati, 2015). He was particularly interested in information literacy, which he sought to explore comprehensively. Specifically, he dedicated himself to studying and applying the Canadian model of the six stages of research ‘Chercher pour trouver’ (Search to Find), developed at the École de bibliothéconomie et des sciences de l’information (EBSI) of the University of Montreal by Hlne Guertin in collaboration with Paulette Bernhard. Melchiori, involving teachers and students from Machiavelli’s, translated the model into Italian (included at the end of this contribution) and applied it to various disciplinary and interdisciplinary areas and different themes, some more strictly curriculum-related and others broader in cultural and educational scope.

Among the numerous projects implemented in the field of information literacy, mention should be made of those dedicated to health themes, including the construction of a school portal for verified health information, and, as a Subject Expert, the laboratory activities that formed an integral part of the Course in Bibliography and Library Science. Regarding these two disciplines, the approach chosen by the author has been and continues to be constructivist, aimed at actively and collaboratively equipping students with the necessary skills to navigate increasing information complexity. In particular, (though not exclusively), the *Guided Inquiry* was employed, an approach developed by Carol Kuhlthau, Professor Emerita at Rutgers University, who has since the early 1980s dedicated her research to scientific investigation

³¹ The first edition of the Social Innovation Around initiative, a yearly meeting– under the patronage of the European Commission Deputy Office in Italy –promoted and organised by SIS-Social Innovation Society.

into information problems and their solutions, as well as behaviours in information searching and usage.

The uniqueness and comprehensiveness of this approach lie in its consideration not only of cognitive and kinesthetic aspects but also of the emotional and affective elements influencing research behaviours. Significant attention is devoted to creating the ‘third space,’ a vital intersection connecting the personal (first space) and the formal (e.g., curriculum-based) realms to facilitate authentic research. Collaboration between teachers and librarians is also emphasized.

Despite the overall positive experience, some students appeared less engaged in active research and exploration. In these cases, although limited, the works required from students as a final assessment often turned out to be collations of online texts. In instances where bibliographic and documentary research was conducted across multiple resources and tools, the reprocessing of retrieved information was often inadequate or absent. How can students be not just interested but also engaged in research, proper information organization, and creative use?

The underlying idea was to develop laboratory activities that would engage even seemingly passive students. Responding to this challenge, Fabrizio Melchiori explored new models, leading to the concept of the ‘bibliographic story.’ Developed and successfully applied in various contexts (educational, academic, and correctional) in collaboration with the author of this contribution, the idea emerged from texts in the ‘Le biblioteche’ series by the Fondazione Mondadori and other documents. These texts presented a mix of various textual types, sometimes incorporating multiple codes (e.g., iconic), prompting the idea to combine narrative writing—sometimes autobiographical—from personal interests, ideas, or experiences (the ‘first space’). This would be followed by an ‘interrogation’ through bibliographic research, reading, and organizing retrieved information (the ‘second space’), involving the narratives and knowledge of contemporary or historical writers and authors. This exercise in intertextuality aimed to introduce students to books (in their various forms and formats), reading, and writing, while playing with the retrieval and creative reuse of information.

Thus, the prototype of the ‘bibliographic story’ emerged as an educational tool primarily aimed at fostering research skills and ethical, creative information processing. The results from these laboratory

activities across different contexts, which led to the flourishing of interesting bibliographic narratives (the ‘third space’) and the satisfaction of their young authors, were highly encouraging.³² This success prompted further experimentation and application in different settings, including correctional facilities.

Regarding this, although involved in designing the Basic Library Science Course for library operator training at the ‘Papillon’ Library of Rebibbia Nuovo Complesso prison, Fabrizio Melchiori could not directly participate in the lessons. However, he agreed, at the insistence of the author of this contribution, to attend the concluding ceremony on June 21, 2019. He showed visible satisfaction in presenting the ‘bibliographic narratives’ developed by the incarcerated course participants. On that occasion, with his characteristic modesty and kindness, Melchiori read his own prototype of a ‘bibliographic narrative’ (or story), deeply moving those present. As Chiara De Vecchis, then President of AIB Lazio, fondly recalled, ‘His reading now has the flavour of a farewell, but it leaves us with the desire to find a way to keep his testimony alive in our community.’

And to the almost prophetic words of Melchiori (*pro manuscripto*), who would leave us just a few days after that ceremony, we entrust the conclusion of this section:

Si deve andare.
Ma dove? Verso dove? E con chi? ?
Il vento mi aiuta a pensare. Sfoglia le pagine della mia mente.
Le libera dall’incanto. Accompagna le frasi e le precipita da
un picco. Non ho mai avuto il coraggio di vedere dove
riposano.
Lo cerco nei libri., i.e.:

We have to go.
But where to? Towards where? And with whom? ...?
The wind helps me think. It flips through the pages of my
mind. It frees them from the spell. It accompanies the
sentences and plunges them from a peak. I've never had the
courage to see where they rest.
I search for it in books.

³² See, for example, Mastrobattista, M. (2013). *Amare la lettura attraverso un gesto d’amore*. <https://martinamastrobattista.wordpress.com/il-mio-progetto/>.

Final Remarks

To tackle today's complexity, organizations (work environments, professional associations, communities, etc.) must be open to change, adjusting their identity along new guidelines, redefining operational and communication strategies. In this perspective, the competent, active, and committed engagement of their individual members is crucial, as they have the opportunity to make a significant impact by directly involving themselves.

In various work and association contexts (e.g., schools, libraries, teacher professional associations, library associations, etc.), there is an increasing need for individuals who can lead, take responsibility, make decisions, ultimately playing a leadership role. This role cannot overlook the ability to collaborate, recognize and value the skills and qualities of individuals and groups, involving them and fostering 'conversations' for the construction of shared knowledge. Thus, they introduce vital innovations for new growth perspectives in such turbulent times as the current era.

These innovations can be more visible and disruptive, or more discreet, but their impact will certainly be positive, making procedures more streamlined, processes more effective, and work teams more cohesive and collaborative. From this perspective, Lourense Das and Fabrizio Melchiori, through a lifetime commitment to innovating within the sector of school libraries, documentation centres, and related professional associations, have provided a valuable example.

Both intellectually curious, professionally prepared, collaborative, and diligent, they would certainly have appreciated and contributed significantly to the Seminar 'The Evolving Concept of 'School Library' and Its Profession.' Their participation would have enriched the experience for all participants, especially teachers, school librarians, and educators. A particularly heartfelt and grateful thought goes to them.

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LE SEI TAPPE DI UN PROGETTO DI RICERCA DELL'INFORMAZIONE *

1. Tappa Circoscrivo Individuo l'argomento	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Comprendo la natura, gli obiettivi e lo scopo del lavoro da eseguire ➤ Chiarisco la domanda di ricerca ➤ Attuo un brain-storming ➤ Traggio o colgo le idee importanti e le parole chiave ➤ Scelgo il punto di vista con il quale esaminerò il mio soggetto/argomento ➤ Formulo la mia idea principale ➤ Abbozzo un piano provvisorio ➤ Rifletto sulle risorse di cui avrò bisogno ➤ Pianifico il mio lavoro
2. Tappa Cerco Interrogo le fonti di informazione	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Scelgo le risorse a cui attingere per fare la mia ricerca ➤ Costruisco le strategie di ricerca a partire dalle mie parole chiave ➤ Avvio la ricerca con l'aiuto delle mie parole chiave in Biblioteca e in Internet ➤ Giudico l'efficacia delle mie strategie di ricerca e le adatto al bisogno ➤ Localizzo i documenti e le risorse che mi sembrano più pertinenti ➤ Scambio e condivido le idee con altri interlocutori
3. Tappa Scelgo Seleziono i documenti	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Organizzo i documenti che ho selezionato ➤ Valuto la qualità dell'informazione secondo i criteri fissati ➤ Esamino differenti punti di vista ➤ Individuo l'informazione specifica necessaria al mio lavoro ➤ Prendo nota dei riferimenti e delle caratteristiche dei documenti selezionati
4. Tappa Prelevo Estraggo le informazioni	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Leggo, ascolto, osservo attentamente e prendo nota ➤ Cito le mie fonti d'informazione e rispetto le regole della privacy ➤ Organizzo i mie appunti in maniera coerente e adeguo il mio piano provvisorio ➤ Faccio il punto sui miei progressi e se occorre ripeto le tappe
5. Tappa Elaboro Tratto le informazioni	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Analizzo le informazioni selezionate in relazione al problema della ricerca ➤ Valuto diverse possibili soluzioni per trattare il mio argomento ➤ Unisco le idee e le informazioni provenienti da fonti diverse ➤ Confronto le opinioni e formulo le mie in accordo all'obiettivo del progetto ➤ Confermo o riformulo la mia idea principale ➤ Decido come strutturare/organizzare il mio lavoro nel suo insieme
6. Tappa Comunico Realizzo il lavoro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sviluppo il mio lavoro in funzione dei miei obiettivi e dei destinatari ➤ Esprimo la mia opinione se l'obiettivo del lavoro lo richiede ➤ Mi assicuro che il contenuto del mio lavoro sia coerente ➤ Rivedo la qualità della forma e del linguaggio ➤ Verifico se ho rispettato le consegne ➤ Organizzo il materiale e gli strumenti di cui potrei aver bisogno

*Tit. orig: *Les 6 étapes d'un projet de recherche d'information*, 1996 - 2011. Université de Montréal, Ecole de bibliothéconomie et des sciences de l'information, <<http://www.ebsi.umontreal.ca/jetrouve/projet/index.htm>>. Traduzione a cura di Fabrizio Melchiori & Clara Camilleri, novembre 2005. Revisione novembre 2012, a cura di Fabrizio Melchiori.

Session 1

**Enhancing Students' Learning Outcomes:
The Role of School Libraries in the Learning Process**

Chapter 1

Learning Global, Media and Information Competencies through the School Library, by Luisa Marquardt³³

Abstract

The International Seminar, organized by IFLA and the Department of Education of Roma Tre University, with the collaboration of other organizations, aimed to provide an opportunity for reflection and exchange for those involved in school libraries as educational and inclusive environments. The seminar focused on information education, the promotion of reading (including digital reading), and collaboration between schools and the community to offer a qualified and integrated range of information, reading, and opportunities for personal, cultural, and social growth. A professionally run school library positively impacts the quality of learning. However, in countries without a specific legal framework, school libraries and their staff must legitimize their function. The various contributions are intended to offer theoretical insights and practical experiences that can ‘inspire’ those who manage or oversee school libraries and, at the same time, make them ‘aspire’ to enhance the quality of their services and activities (including remote services). The goal is to contribute to curriculum implementation, broaden organized and qualified access to information, reading, and culture from a network perspective, and generally foster the acquisition of global and informational skills. This, in turn, supports the holistic development of individuals, enabling them to navigate independently in a complex informational environment.

Keywords: Media and Information literacy; infodemic; Information Literacy; IFLA School Libraries Section; guidelines; information literacy education; library associations.

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Introduction

The first session of the International Seminar is entitled ‘Improving Student Learning Outcomes: The Role of the School Library in the Learning Process’ and focuses, from different perspectives, on the contribution that the school library can make to learning and educational success. A professionally run school library, with its well-furnished spaces, extensive physical and digital collections, and well-prepared and available staff, enhances the educational offer of the school to which it belongs. All these elements would be of little value without a clear programme of services and educational, cultural, and recreational activities. Among the educational activities, those dedicated to reading are naturally important, but there is also a growing emphasis on activities dedicated to the acquisition of transversal, ‘soft’ skills necessary for personal, professional, and social fulfilment in the twenty-first century, given the particular complexity of information.

Contemporary societies are increasingly based on information and knowledge, but they are also characterised by the very fine line between active participation in civil and social life on one hand, and exclusion on the other. The industry offers information and communication systems and devices that are increasingly powerful and efficient, amplifying the quantity and speed of information production and transmission, sometimes with disconcerting effects. For example, from its earliest manifestations, the Covid-19 epidemic was accompanied by a parallel information epidemic or ‘infodemic,’³⁴ that is,

Circolazione di una quantità eccessiva di informazioni, talvolta non vagliate con accuratezza, che rendono difficile orientarsi su un determinato argomento per la difficoltà di individuare fonti affidabili. (Treccani, 2020), i.e.

the circulation of an excessive amount of information, sometimes not accurately vetted, making it difficult to navigate a specific topic due to the difficulty of identifying reliable sources. (Treccani, 2020).

The spread of contradictory, misleading, alarmist, or ‘denialist’ news, often in a very convulsive and confused manner, has created confusion, fuelled controversy, anxiety, and scepticism. The infodemic

³⁴ <https://www.washingtonpost.com/archive/opinions/2003/05/11/when-the-buzz-bites-back/bc8cd84f-cab6-4648-bf58-0277261af6cd/>

phenomenon—which is not new³⁵—has highlighted how important it is to navigate through information. Information itself counts for little if one does not possess the skills to search for, select, organise, and reprocess it in order to make autonomous and informed decisions, create something new, and innovate processes, products, and services. The possession or lack of such skills has significant political, economic, and social implications. Due to the pervasiveness of new media—consider the social impact of the Internet, which has had, and continues to have, an impact similar to that of radio and television, albeit over a much shorter time frame—the risk of homogenisation and conditioning is very high, which can undermine the democratic foundations of our society. Instead, society must be firmly based on

people who are aware of their rights and take responsibility for actively defending them. Citizens do not merely observe. They make their voices heard, and even if they are not always listened to, their voices still matter, because they use all non-violent means to monitor the free exercise of power, forming an invisible network of defenders of freedom. (Dahrendorf, 2006: 6. The English translation is ours.)

As Dahrendorf observes, giving up on actively and consciously participating in society can promote the spread of authoritarianism or a misunderstood and exacerbated regionalism, phenomena that are emerging in many countries. The path towards a truly inclusive and knowledge-based society is still long and continuously undermined. Yet, precisely at a historical moment when bridges (and not walls) should be built, education and training pathways—at various levels, from preschool to primary school, to secondary, post-secondary, and tertiary education—play a fundamental role, and their value must be strongly reaffirmed. As extensively outlined by Jacques Delors in the *Report on Education for the 21st Century*, the four important dimensions that education must fully acquire and develop in every person—cognitive, operational, personal ethics, and social ethics—are the four pillars on which a society based on dialogue, understanding, and collaboration among its members, and on the knowledge they contribute to building together, should rest. The education system plays a significant role in preventing or removing cultural barriers and prejudices, in acquiring the ability to learn throughout life, and in

³⁵ Yet in 2003 (May 11), David J. Rothkopf spoke of ‘infodemic’, i.e., ‘information pandemic’.

contributing to building an inclusive society. In this perspective, information literacy (IL) education assumes particular importance.

Information Literacy: A Brief Excursus

The phrase ‘information literacy’, attributed to Paul Zurkowski (1974), began to be used more widely, including bibliographic repertoires and databases (such as LISA and ERIC) in the early 1990s. This indicates the growing body of scientific and professional work driven by studies, research, and experiences. Libraries, particularly school and university libraries, linked to learning pathways, began to develop information literacy education programmes. Interest in this new function of the library grew among scholars and library associations, which formulated definitions, guidelines, and standards. In short, there was a shift from ‘library literacy’, i.e., competence in library use acquired through learning basic information retrieval skills (Lubans, 1978), to ‘information literacy’ (IL), which various authors interpret and define differently (Bawden, 2001). For example, Burchinal (1976) describes IL as a set of skills, including locating and using information, and related informational competence; using information to solve problems and make decisions; identifying and using information efficiently and effectively. Owens (1976) sees IL as an aspect of democracy, highlighting a significant link to active citizenship, while Hamelink (1976) associates the term with the ability to form one's own opinion.

Robert S. Taylor, credited with introducing IL into library science reflection in 1979, identifies the following elements: acquiring appropriate information and data is essential for solving many problems; knowing the available informational resources and their locations is a fundamental requirement of IL; the process of acquiring information, whether continuous or occasional, is always important, as are the strategies for information acquisition. Taylor also identifies librarians as professionals not only of information but also of information education, thus expanding their role: no longer (or not just) mere library instruction, but education in information competence for their users.

In the United States, in the 1970s, the elements of IL were defined in relation to exercising full citizenship, but not yet the specific knowledge and skills needed for this purpose. In the 1980s, the definition of information competence further developed, particularly concerning the educational context at school and higher levels; during this period,

'information skills' were more commonly referred to. Following the 1983 report *A Nation at Risk*, in which the National Commission on Excellence in Education highlighted the state of US education and the need for investment to revive the nation, the U.S. National Commission on Library and Information Science (NCLIS) produced a document specifying what was meant by information skills.

This period saw a proliferation of research, studies, and experiences. Notable contributions include those of Mancall, Aaron & Walker (1986); Carol C. Kuhlthau's research (1987), which suggested that IL was more a learning modality than a set of separate skills (e.g., IT, library use, etc.); and Eisenberg and Berkowitz's development of the 'Big Six' (1988a, 1988b), an approach to solving information problems based on Bloom's taxonomy, emphasising the importance of using skills from early childhood throughout the school curriculum, incorporating them into it. The author of this contribution finds the AASL standard particularly interesting, even years after its formulation. According to the American Association of School Librarians (AASL) of the ALA, a student is information literate when they know how to access, evaluate, and use information accurately and creatively (ALA-AASL, *Information Power*, 1998). Specifically, regarding student learning, the AASL defines 29 indicators for 9 levels of information competence, divided into 3 areas: 'Information Literacy', 'Independent Learning', and 'Social Responsibility'. In these areas, students are information literate if they: 1) access information efficiently and effectively; 2) evaluate information critically and competently; 3) use information accurately and creatively. A student who learns independently is, first of all, information literate and: 4) seeks information related to their own interests; 5) appreciates literature and other creative expressions of information; 6) strives for excellence in seeking information and generating knowledge. Finally, students who contribute positively to their learning community and society are, first of all, information-literate individuals who learn independently, and: 7) recognise the importance of information for a democratic society; 8) practise ethical behaviour regarding the use of information and information technology (this aspect is particularly important in light of cyberbullying phenomena); 9) participate effectively in group work to seek and generate information.

Learning Information, Media, and Global Competence at School

The role of the school library in the personal development process is

as crucial as that of university or college libraries. They must provide complementary education, albeit of a different kind, to classroom learning and facilitate access to information and knowledge recorded on any medium. They also have a fundamental educational role: educating young people to use libraries and, even more importantly, supporting the teaching of reading and writing skills and fostering a love for reading and learning. (Gorman, 2018: 92. English translation is ours.)

However, the school library has an even more specific educational function when it comes to acquiring information literacy or 'information literacy' and for this purpose, various models can prove useful, some of which, for illustrative purposes, are briefly described.

For those—be they curriculum teachers or school librarians/library teachers—who wish to integrate information literacy education more systematically into the curriculum, in addition to the aforementioned standard developed by ALA-AASL, the following points of reference may prove helpful.

Firstly, the '9 questions' from the *Guidelines for School Libraries* (Carroll, IFLA, 1990; translated into Italian by AIB, 1995, p. 2) provide the following framework for information research and use:

- 1) Analysis and formulation of information needs (What do I need to do?)
- 2) Identification and evaluation of likely resources (Where could I go?)
- 3) Locating individual resources (How can I obtain information?)
- 4) Examination, selection, and rejection of individual resources (Which resources could I use?)
- 5) Inquiry of resources (How can I use resources?)
- 6) Recording and classifying information (What can I memorize?)
- 7) Interpretation, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation (Have I achieved the information I needed?)
- 8) Presentation and communication (How can I present it?)
- 9) Evaluation (What have I achieved?).

But information literacy education can begin as early as preschool. In fact, the 'Super3' model (an adaptation of the 'Big6,' which we will explore shortly) offers an approach to information seeking and use applicable from preschool through the first two grades of primary school: planning, doing, and reviewing are the three essential steps.

The 'Big6,' developed by psychologists Michael Eisenberg and Robert Berkovitz (similarly to the 'Super3'), draws from Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive objectives to illustrate the six skills/phases of research:

- 1) Define the task by clarifying and understanding why information is sought, starting with basic questions: what do I already know? What information do I need? Where can I find it?
- 2) Choose research strategies
- 3) Identify information sources (books, encyclopaedias, maps, etc.—print and online resources) and access information
- 4) Use (analyse and select) information
- 5) Synthesize found information by organizing, elaborating, and presenting it logically and orderly for its recipients, using graphs, illustrations, etc.
- 6) Evaluate the entire research process, critically reflecting on both the process and the outcome: Did I solve the problem? Did I learn something new? What was effective? What could be improved? What should I avoid in the future?

A particularly compelling approach, grounded in scientific evidence and encompassing the multifaceted nature of research engagement, is that developed by Professor Emerita Carol C. Kuhlthau. Since the early 1980s, she has dedicated extensive efforts to understanding information needs, especially during developmental stages. This ongoing exploration has led to the formulation of the 'Guided Inquiry' approach—an investigative process conducted under the thoughtful guidance of educators and librarians who collaboratively plan the journey, thereby enhancing student learning. Within guided inquiry, emotional, psychological, and motor aspects are considered. Furthermore, significant emphasis is placed on the 'setting,' notably the creation of the 'third space' (a concept borrowed from U.S. sociologist Oldenburg)—a convergence of the student's first space (knowledge, expectations, interests, lived experiences) and the second space (curriculum, educational objectives, cognitive goals), which may not always harmonize in traditional classroom settings. The school library, when sufficiently resourced and organized, uniquely serves as this 'third space,' fostering authentic and stimulating research.

More recently, the development of 'Guided Inquiry Design' (GID) underscores the critical role of well-planned educational strategies in guided inquiry.

Information literacy should be understood broadly, encompassing proficiency in various mass media and communication, i.e., Media and Information Literacy (MIL), as advocated by UNESCO over the past fifteen years, alongside global competencies. These skills encompass the ability to explore local, global, and intercultural issues, understand and respect diverse perspectives and worldviews, engage in open, fair, and effective interactions with individuals from different cultures, promote collective well-being and sustainable development. (OECD 2019).

Such skills are crucial for fostering harmony in multicultural, multi-ethnic, and multilingual communities, achieving professional success in a dynamic environment, responsibly utilizing media (to counteract the risks of bias and infodemics), and contributing to the realization of Agenda 2030 and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals.

Contents of the Session

The interventions of the first session reflect, from various perspectives, on the school library's contribution to learning and educational success. An important focus, as outlined briefly earlier, is on education in information literacy, for which there are various models. It is noteworthy how Darryl Toerien's reflections, particularly drawing on the works of Barbara Stripling and Carol Kuhlthau, have led to the development of another model – the 'Framework Of Skills for Inquiry Learning' (FOSIL) – which provides a framework for acquiring skills in inquiry-based learning. Toerien's dedication to integrating the Oakham School library into educational and learning activities, particularly in information literacy, extends beyond the school, projecting the new model nationally, adopted in the UK by the School Library Association, CILIP, and the national 'Great School Libraries' project (Toerien, *infra*; Hutchinson, 2020).

For effective educational implementation, the school library must prioritize good organization. Albert Boekhorst, drawing on decades of experience as a researcher and university lecturer, highlights how a well-functioning school library enhances student outcomes and thus must be designed, organized, and managed to foster an environment for learning and information access. The expert stresses the importance of each school developing a clear 'school library policy.' This can be defined with the guidance of the *IFLA School Library Guidelines*, a

concise yet comprehensive document serving as a useful foundation for all school libraries.

Ornella Papa and Rita Marzoli (INVALSI Library) confirm the link between the quality of the school library and student performance. Descriptive research based on data collected by INVALSI during the 2014-15 school year indicates better academic performance in schools with well-functioning libraries and extensive book collections.

Jing Zhang, along with Naiyi Yang and Yi Zhou from Sun Yat-sen University in Guangzhou, China, reflecting on the outstanding results of Chinese students in reading, mathematics, and science highlighted in the latest PISA 2018 survey (OECD, 2019), has examined the factors (such as policies, projects, etc.) contributing to this success and the role of the school library.

Final Remarks

A succinct overview of information literacy has been provided, encompassing its broader scope, which includes media and global literacy. The key aspects of the contributions from the first session have also been highlighted. Given this context, it is imperative that education in information, media, and global literacy be systematically ensured by the school library in collaboration with teachers and fully integrated into the curriculum. Rather than being treated as a standalone subject, it should be embraced as a cross-curricular component, as the skills of information research and usage are relevant across all disciplines. Achieving this requires the comprehensive recognition of the educational role played by school libraries and librarians.

Regrettably, as observed by Gorman,

‘Given the hype surrounding the ‘information age,’ it is understandable how administrators, in uncritically embracing technological innovations, may view libraries (and the space they occupy - which is crucial, considering the alarming number of schools lacking adequate space) as ‘inessential,’ alongside arts, music, and other intangible assets consistently undervalued in a materialistic era.’ (Gorman, 2018: 92).

In various countries, as part of the implementation of what could be termed the ‘digital agenda,’ schools involved often lack accredited librarians, and half of those with libraries lack any qualified personnel to manage them. All of this occurs within a system that continues to invest heavily in an iPad program that has already cost more than a

billion dollars - just one of the most glaring examples. Far from being dispensable, school libraries are essential to education, not least because they serve as the cornerstone of learning and lifelong education. One might wonder whether the poor literacy skills of today's students are connected to insufficient funding for school libraries and their services. In instances where schools have retained 'libraries,' they have frequently laid off librarians; a 'library' without professional assistance is simply a room with books and computers, no better than having no library at all.

If we genuinely desire effective public schools, even as advocated by the most severe critics, and if we aspire to support democracy, I strongly believe that we must advocate for the presence of robust school libraries and provide encouragement to our colleagues working within them. (Gorman, 2018: 93. The translation in English is ours).

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Chapter 1.1

(Re)Discovering Inquiry In and Through the School Library: the FOSIL Model, by Darryl Toerien³⁶

Abstract

School librarianship in the UK faces a number of pressing challenges, ranging from a failure to provide even the most basic professional education at a university level specifically for school librarianship – and where training exists, it lacks overarching purpose and coherence – to an education system that does not require school libraries by law, and so has grown to have little need of them in practice. These challenges combine to leave individual school librarians at the mercy of school-level administrators, most of whom have neither theoretical nor experiential understanding of the value that a properly staffed and funded school library programme adds to the education of our children. And then there is COVID-19, which transforms this pressing and *complex* challenge into a very real existential threat. Against this backdrop, the author's attempts to make his school library integral to learning and teaching, rather than peripheral (or unnecessary), resulted in FOSIL, or Framework Of Skills for Inquiry Learning, a work in progress that is heavily indebted to the works of Barbara Stripling and Carol Kuhlthau. This paper is an introduction to and an overview of FOSIL, and concludes with some thoughts on the potential contribution of FOSIL to school librarianship in the UK.

Keywords: Inquiry; Information Literacy; FOSIL; Empire State Information Fluency Continuum; Information Search Process.

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Introduction

School librarianship in the United Kingdom faces a number of pressing challenges, all exacerbated by COVID-19. The situation may well be illustrated by personal anecdote:

I am a professionally qualified school librarian with a teaching background working as the Head of Library in an independent secondary school in England. By any number of national measures, we offer a high-quality library service. However, when I left teaching in 2003, I was employed as a school librarian without any education or training or experience as a school librarian, which is not an uncommon practice. While I am very grateful for this opportunity, and trust that the colleagues and students who I work with have come to benefit from this situation, it is not a sure foundation upon which to build a profession. I enrolled for a MA in Information and Library Management in 2004, which I passed with distinction, but which taught me nothing specific about school libraries.³⁷ I joined the Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals (CILIP) in 2004, and almost immediately after that the National Committee of its School Libraries Special Interest Group (CILIP SLG), on which I still serve. I also joined the School Library Association (SLA), and recently joined its Board. The fact that school libraries are represented by two associations is telling, and partly accounts for the fact that the very term professional is contested and even divisive, and, as a consequence, we have no coherent idea of what a school librarian is and does, or ought to be and do, and so no way of getting there, although there are encouraging signs that this may be changing.³⁸ This situation is compounded by an

³⁷ Four years later my wife, a Physics Teacher by education and training, passed her MSc in Information and Library Studies with distinction at a different university, and also learnt nothing specific about school libraries. In fact, had we pursued postgraduate professional education at any one of the CILIP-accredited universities in the UK we would not have learned anything specific about school libraries – a debilitating situation that persists to this day.

³⁸ A comprehensive history of school librarianship in the UK still needs to be written, as far as I can tell. However, and very briefly, it appears that at the inaugural meeting of a newly-founded association of school librarians on 28 November 1936, the librarians present regrettably split into what would go on to become the School Library Association on 20 January 1937 and what would eventually go on to become the School Libraries Special Interest Group of the Chartered Institute of Library and

educational system that does not require school libraries by law, and therefore has grown to have little need of them in practice, and, in the course of writing this paper, a global pandemic that I fear will decimate school librarianship in the UK.

This situation leaves school librarians at the mercy of school-level administrators, most of whom, largely for reasons outlined above, have neither theoretical nor experiential understanding of the value that a properly staffed and funded school library programme adds to the education of our children. Against this backdrop, FOSIL represents an increasingly successful attempt to make the school library integral to learning. FOSIL is a model of the inquiry process and underlying continuum of inquiry skills, as well as a growing collection of resources to support inquiry. FOSIL is the focus, but not exclusively, of the FOSIL Group, which is a growing international community of education professionals working to more effectively equip our children with the kind of knowledge that they most need, which is knowledge that will enable them to get more knowledge for themselves (Papert, 1993). FOSIL has recently been endorsed by the Great School Libraries (GSL) campaign as its recommended model of the inquiry process (see footnote 3), and, consequently, FOSIL is now inextricably bound up with the future of school librarianship in the UK.

What follows is an account of my attempt to make school libraries integral to education rather than peripheral, if not actually unnecessary, through FOSIL.

FOSIL (Framework Of Skills for Inquiry Learning)

Dallas Willard (2014), long-time Professor of Philosophy at The University of Southern California in Los Angeles, claimed that there are four fundamental questions that all human beings ultimately have to answer, of which the answers to the first two concern us here:

1. What is reality? *Reality is what you have to deal with.*

Information Professionals in 1979 (Colebourn, 1986). More than 80 years later, the Great School Libraries (GSL) campaign was launched on 20 September 2018 as a collaboration between CILIP, CILIP SLG and SLA aimed at providing every child with access to a great school library. While this development will not automatically, or even easily, bring about a more unified profession, it is a step in the right direction. Moreover, on 2 March 2020, GSL endorsed the IFLA School Library Guidelines and FOSIL as GSL's recommended model of the inquiry process, which are further steps in this direction.

2. What is success? *Success is how well you deal with reality.*

Now, it is an educational reality that, as Seymour Papert³⁹ is widely reported to have put it, you can't teach people everything they need to know, so the best you can do is position them where they can find what they need to know when they need to know it. It is, furthermore, an educational reality that many schools seem unwilling or unable to deal with, and this has grave implications for not only the students. My efforts to deal with this educational reality resulted in FOSIL (Framework Of Skills for Inquiry Learning).

FOSIL grew out of a deeply held conviction, expressed so simply and so powerfully by Danny Hillis (2004) – inventor, scientist, and computer designer who pioneered the concept of massively parallel computers that is now the basis of most new supercomputer designs – that we ought to be able to learn anything by finding out for ourselves. Now even superficial familiarity with Danny Hillis makes it clear that he knows a thing or two about learning for oneself. In making this claim, he was addressing one of the four conditions necessary for this to happen – information, and specifically the right information in a building maelstrom of information, much of it unreliable and more and more of it even harmful. The other three conditions are the desire, or at least the willingness, to learn for ourselves, an understanding of the processes by which we learn for ourselves, and growing mastery of the skills that enable these processes.

These conditions, or more precisely these conditions in combination, do not occur naturally in school, and if they occur at all, it is by design. FOSIL, then, is learning to learn anything for ourselves by design.

FOSIL and the desire to learn by finding out for ourselves

This goes to the heart of the matter, because what we truly value is revealed by what we make time for. It takes time to learn to learn for ourselves, and it is difficult. As a consequence, the conditions in which the expectation that we learn for ourselves gives rise to the willingness

³⁹ Seymour Papert, Professor Emeritus at the MIT Media Lab, is not the only, or first, or even the last person to describe this educational reality, but he was uniquely positioned to do so – L. Rafael Reif, President of MIT, said of Seymour Papert following his untimely death in 2016 that he ‘helped revolutionize at least 3 fields, from the study of how children make sense of the world, to the development of artificial intelligence, to the unique intersection of technology and learning’ (MIT Media Lab, 2016).

to learn for ourselves, which in turn gives rise to the desire to learn for ourselves, does not exist in many schools. Once it does, an understanding of the processes by which we learn for ourselves becomes necessary.

FOSIL and the processes by which we learn for ourselves

On one level, FOSIL is a model of the inquiry process that is simple to understand and apply. As is often the case, some of our simplest tools are also our most powerful, and this is the case with FOSIL: for example, English students in Year 7 (age 11) used it to carry out an inquiry into science fictional futures while, at the same time, Politics students in Year 12 (age 17) were using it to carry out an inquiry into pressure groups.

Stages in the FOSIL Inquiry Cycle

The simplicity, and power, of FOSIL lies in the logical way the stages in the inquiry process interrelate (see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1. The FOSIL Cycle (3.0)

- **Connect:** Knowledge builds on knowledge, so pausing to take stock of what you already know reveals more clearly what you do not yet know.
- **Wonder:** Gaps in what you know give rise to questions, some more fruitful than others.
- **Investigate:** These questions guide your investigation, which is aimed at sourcing reliable information that you can work with.
- **Construct:** This is the point of learning by finding out for yourself - building knowledge and understanding from information in response to the questions that you have.
- **Express:** Once you know what you are talking about, you need to be able to share it appropriately, effectively and ethically.
- **Reflect:** Doug Engelbart said it best when he said that the better we get, the better we get at getting better (1995).

FOSIL and mastering the skills that enable the processes by which we learn for ourselves.

On another level, FOSIL is also the specific and measurable skills that enable each of the stages in the Cycle, and these skills need to be developed progressively and systematically over the time that a student is at school. For example, the ability to list all of the sources used becomes the ability to cite and reference each of the sources used according to a standard style (see Figure 2 below).

Figure 2. The development of citing and referencing within the Express stage of FOSIL

The dynamic relationship between model of the inquiry process and underlying continuum of skills is essential to bear in mind – as Barbara Stripling (2017), whose work FOSIL is largely based on (see below), points out, ‘providing a framework of the inquiry process is only the first step in empowering students to pursue inquiry on their own, with the next step to structure teaching around a framework of literacy, inquiry, critical thinking, and technology skills they must develop at each phase of inquiry over their years of school and in the context of content area learning’ (p. 52).

FOSIL and the information needed to construct knowledge and build understanding for ourselves

The problem with sourcing reliable information used to be that it was difficult to find because information was scarce. This was primarily a problem of access. Sourcing reliable information is still difficult, but this is because information is overwhelmingly abundant. This is primarily a problem of discernment.⁴⁰ FOSIL addresses this problem in two ways. Firstly, it directs students towards a rich collection of age-appropriate scholarly resources, both print and online, which allows them, initially, to focus on developing their mastery of the processes and skills of inquiry. Secondly, the skills that enable Investigate and Construct include, for example, the effective use of internet search engines to find information and the critical use of web-based information.

The role of the Library

Creating and maintaining the combination of conditions outlined above is a complex task. In countries with a long history of learning through inquiry, librarians and teachers work together as an instructional team. It soon becomes obvious why. Teachers, clearly, are specialists in their academic discipline, who ought to have up-to-date knowledge of developments within their discipline. Librarians are information specialists, who ought to have a concern with how information becomes a coherent body of interdisciplinary knowledge, which is reflected in the library's collection. Because learning to learn for ourselves needs to be taught, and supported, the focus of collaboration between teachers and librarians is threefold:

1. Designing a good inquiry, which requires an understanding of the type of inquiry that is appropriate - closed, guided or open.
2. Supporting the inquiry, which requires an understanding of the stages involved in inquiry – including the affective, cognitive and physical demands that inquiry makes of students.
3. Resourcing the inquiry, which goes beyond merely providing access to age-appropriate data and/ or information in print

⁴⁰ As the science fiction author William Gibson insightfully pointed out, though, ‘the future has arrived – it’s just not evenly distributed yet’ (2012), which is to say that where inequalities of access persist they are now increasingly exacerbated by inequalities of discernment. Both types of inequality urgently need to be addressed.

and/ or digital form to include providing sufficient time for the inquiry and resources to help students manage the inquiry process.

Knowledge or skills?

This is a false dichotomy that arises out of a poor understanding of learning through inquiry and/or a poor experience of learning through inquiry. In both cases, this is almost certainly due to a combination of a poorly designed and supported inquiry combined with students who have not been properly equipped for inquiry. In countries with a long history of learning through inquiry, a properly designed and supported inquiry is a powerful way to gain knowledge, and that is actually the purpose.

Where does FOSIL come from?

FOSIL – which is a model of the inquiry process, an underlying continuum of inquiry skills and a growing collection of free resources to support the systematic and progressive development of inquiry skills – is based on the Empire State Information Fluency Continuum (ESIFC). The ESIFC was developed in 2009 and re-imagined in 2019 by the School Library Systems Association of New York State (SLSA) under the leadership of Dr Barbara Stripling, Professor Emerita at Syracuse University, which serves more than 3.2 million children in 4,236 schools in New York State (as of 1 June 2020, although the actual number of schools and students being served by the ESIFC in some form or another is greater). The ESIFC was ad(o/a)pted as FOSIL in 2012 under CC BY-NC 4.0 by Darryl Toerien, Head of Library at Oakham School, and is made available under CC BY-NC 4.0. Another major influence on the development of FOSIL is Carol Kuhlthau, Professor Emerita at Rutgers University, whose work on describing the affective, cognitive and physical demands that inquiry makes of students adds a vital dimension to FOSIL (see Figure 3 below).

FOSIL Stages and ISP Tasks	Connect		Wonder		Investigate		Construct		Express		Reflect
	Task Initiation	Topic Selection	Topic Exploration		Focus Formulation	Information Collection		Presentation		Assessment	
Feelings (affective)	Uncertainty	Optimism	Confusion, frustration and doubt		Clarity	Direction and confidence		Relief and satisfaction or disappointment		Sense of accomplishment	
Thoughts (cognitive)	Vague				Focussed	Increased interest				Increased self-awareness	
Actions (physical)	Seeking relevant information Exploring					Seeking pertinent information. Documenting					
EE Timetable	EE Seminar 1	Research Proposal	EE Seminar 2		Finalise research question	Gather evidence to support thesis		EE Seminar 3 (including IT Workshop 2)		Culminates in Viva Voce	
	Supervisor Application Form		IT Workshop 1		Formulate thesis statement			EE Writing Days			
	Work through subject-specific LibGuide and arrange to meet librarian if necessary					EE Investigation Days					

Figure 3. Kuhlthau's Information Search Process (2004), FOSIL & the IBDP Extended Essay

FOSIL is the result of trying to solve two specific problems within the International Baccalaureate Diploma Programme (IBDP) relating to the Extended Essay (EE), a mandatory independent, self-directed piece of research, finishing with a 4,000-word paper.

Firstly, how to effectively prepare our students for the demands of the EE, specifically how to accurately cite and reference according to a standard style, when, for the majority of them, their education at school up to that point would not have required work of this nature. This led me to what I thought was a framework of information literacy skills, but, serendipitously, turned out to be a continuum of inquiry skills and accompanying model of the inquiry process (ESIFC), which led directly to FOSIL.

Secondly, how to more effectively support the EE out of a deeper understanding of the inquiry process. This was motivated by a sense that our EE timetable, which in many respects was exemplary, worked against the inquiry process at certain key points because it driven primarily by administrative concerns. The clearest example of this was the requirement for a research question to start the process rather than allowing the research question to emerge from the process. This led me to Carol Kuhlthau's Information Search Process (2004), which not only added an affective, cognitive and physical dimension to our understanding of the inquiry process, which allowed us to realign out EE timetable to work with the inquiry process, but also identified points of optimal intervention in support of the EE process.

FOSIL remains a work in progress, and one that tries to deal respectfully with the extraordinary work that it draws from.

What is in a name?

FOSIL stands for Framework Of Skills for Inquiry Learning. The fact that it sounds like FOSSIL is deliberate. Firstly, the discipline of archaeology is a helpful way to think about inquiry with children. Secondly, it serves as a warning against complacency, because a framework, or continuum, of inquiry skills, many of which are technology dependent by definition or in practice, must evolve in response to changes in the environment if it is to remain vital.

What is in a colour?

While I am no expert, I tried in the time that I had to choose for each stage in the inquiry process the colour that appeared to be most closely associated with the kind of activity that I understood to be involved in that stage. So, while the choice of colour for each stage is somewhat subjective, it is not entirely random. The main reasons for identifying each stage in the inquiry process with a colour was that it added a measure of visual appeal for students, and that it helps younger students in particular to remember the logical order of the stages and locate themselves within the process.

The Evolution of FOSIL

FOSIL is evolving in two ways. Firstly, we are building a deep understanding of learning through inquiry from the ground up, so while we have already come a long way on our journey, we still have a long way to go. This means that FOSIL is a collaborative work in progress. Secondly, and following on from the first, FOSIL is at the centre of a growing community of schools and education professionals who are on a similar journey. To this end we established the FOSIL Group in April of 2019, the purpose of which is to provide a forum for active collaboration on developing a culture and practice of learning through inquiry that is focused on but not limited to FOSIL, which since then has grown to 212 members from around the world. The FOSIL Group is endorsed by CILIP SLG, SLA and the Information Literacy Special Interest Group (ILG) of CILIP, and since April 2020, the School Library Systems Administration of New York State, who, under

the leadership of Barbara Stripling, developed the Empire State Information Fluency Continuum, which FOSIL is based on.

FOSIL/ the FOSIL Group was shortlisted for the CILIP ILG Information Literacy Award 2019, the Strategic Education Initiative of the Year in the Tes Independent Schools Award 2020 and the CILIP ILG Digital Award for Information Literacy 2020. FOSIL was recently added to the list of Models and frameworks on CILIP ILG's Information Literacy website. Most importantly, though, FOSIL has recently been endorsed as the recommended model of the inquiry process by the Great School Libraries (GSL) campaign, which is a collaboration between CILIP, CILIP SLG and SLA aimed at providing every child with access to a great school library.

Final Remarks

Although stated in the extreme, Ivan Illich's (1971) contention that the principal lesson that school teaches is the need to be taught appears still to be the case in many schools and for many children. While not intentional, this is practically inevitable in an educational system that is geared towards subject-specific and content-heavy terminal examinations. Yet, as David Deutsch (1998) points out, in a world where knowledge is growing exponentially, the tools for acquiring and interpreting that knowledge are at least as important as the actual knowledge itself. The tragic irony, then, is that the closer children get to leaving school, and the more 'knowledge' they need to have learnt, the less time there is to progressively and systematically equip them with the tools for acquiring and interpreting that knowledge for themselves. Consequently, at the point in their formal education at school where they should be at their most independent, many, and perhaps most, children find themselves at their most dependent on others for their learning.

FOSIL is, then, at the same time a rejection of *this* educational reality and an approach to bringing about a different one. Norman Beswick, writing about the Library-College movement, argued that 'it is not the library that 'supports' the classroom...but the classroom that leads (or should lead) inevitably and essentially to the library' (1967). The reality that this points to is not one in which the library is more important than the classroom, but one in which, as a consequence of purposeful collaboration between the classroom and the library, our children have

been positioned where they can find what they need to know when they need to know it.

This brings me to the title of my paper, *(Re)Discovering Inquiry In and Through the School Library: the FOSIL Model*. The Galileo Educational Network (n.d.), which is the professional learning arm of the Werklund School of Education at the University of Calgary, describes inquiry as ‘a dynamic process of being open to wonder and puzzlement and coming to know and understand the world, and as such, it is a stance that pervades all aspects of life and is essential to the way in which knowledge is created’. This spirit of inquiry gives birth to the library, and as Daniel Callison remind us, ‘[school libraries] exist as learning centres because of inquiry’ (Callison & Preddy, 2006, p. 601). FOSIL, then, turns out to be an inquiry that discovers inquiry at the heart of the school library, only to (re)discover that it had been there all along...weak from neglect, but aching to be revived.

With the endorsement of FOSIL by GSL as its recommended model of the inquiry process, FOSIL has become inextricably bound up with the future of school libraries and school librarianship in the UK. Whether this combination is enough to actually produce a different educational reality remains to be seen, but the odds against it have decreased, and this is worth fighting for.

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Implementing School Libraries for the 21st Century Learning, by Albert Boekhorst⁴¹

Abstract

In order to survive, to develop and to relax, people need knowledge about themselves, their physical environment and their social environment. They can find this knowledge in three processes to be learned: observation, conversation and consultation. Governments play an important role in this process as they determine the final objectives of education and facilitate infrastructure. School libraries play an important educational role. They function as a learning centre on how to have effective, efficient and ethical access to information and are a channel to information. Research shows that students of schools with a good working library perform better than students of schools without a school library. To have a good working school library there should be a 'School Library Policy', where the aims, tasks, responsibilities and procedures are described. The 2nd edition of the IFLA School Library Guidelines (2015), written by the IFLA School Libraries Section in collaboration with IASL, and translated in many languages, and the workshops materials, developed by the IASL/IFLA School Libraries Section Joint Committee can help in implementing effective school libraries.

Keywords: education; school instruction; school library.

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Introduction

School libraries are important in the educational process. Research about educational trends and pedagogical models shows the significant difference effective school library services can make on student literacy and learning outcomes. However, in many countries school libraries are not available for every student.

Body

In order to survive, to develop and to relax, people need knowledge about themselves, their physical environment and their social environment. They can find this knowledge in three processes: observation, conversation and consultation.

1. Observation refers to the ability to look around and observe objects and processes, this is fact-finding by experimenting and authenticating. If I want to know if it's raining so I'll take an umbrella, I look out of the window and make a decision.
2. Conversation refers to the process in which we ask other people: family, friends, colleagues and experts for the information we need, face-to-face, by phone, by email. So if I want to know if I have to take an umbrella, I can call my sister and ask her. She can look out of the window and decide, maybe she can even inform me better, because she has heard the weather forecast.
3. Consultation refers to the process in which we consult information professionals working in libraries, archives, museums, information institutes and information departments in organisations. This is called stored or recorded information. Due to technology push and users demands long existing walls and traditions between them are disappearing and we call them 'memory institutions' now.

All three processes take place in the 'real' world where we can touch the objects and the 'virtual' world, that we can only access with digital technology. However, there are barriers that impede or can even block successful access to needed information. Till now I distinguished five types of potential barriers that are based on interdependencies between people: economic, political, affective, cognitive and personal characteristics.

The economic barrier refers to the fact that people are dependent on the production and the distribution of scarce resources including food, clothing and housing. Since the 1970s information is considered as the fourth production factor, which functions as the driving force of the economy. This means that supply and demand factors are applicable to the production, use and control of information and the technical and social infrastructure that is needed for access to information and dissemination. Information costs money. As wealth is unevenly spread the access to information is spread unevenly as well.

The political barrier refers to people's need to protect themselves against physical constraints and aggression of others. To obtain this protection a regulation of violence is needed whereby specialists can enforce power entitled to them through legislation. Hereby the law and order of a society is formally stipulated. These rules have reference to all relations people have with one another. Laws regarding information are for example the regulation of author's rights, legislation on archives, access to government information and freedom for the press. These forms of legislation can be seen as political regulation through which access to information can be controlled. I think of nations that try to block access to the internet and Wikileaks.

The affective barrier refers to the fact that people have feelings for one another. People need one another for affection, love and support. These friendships and emotional relations are not limited only to other people, but also include objects and organisations that are appropriate to a person's culture. Therefore, information sources and channels such as books, CDs, DVD's television and internet are also included. This liking has reference to not only the information media, and channel, but also the information type itself.

The cognitive barrier refers to the fact that people are dependent on one another because they learn from one another. People create knowledge and distribute this between one another in the form of information. Until the development of writing, people communicated mainly through speech and verbal communication. Writing and printing made it possible for information to be disseminated in spite of borders of time and space. Learning from one another happens in diverse ways and is not limited to education at school. The scope and content of what is taught to the people depend on their social position and societal relations. An illiterate farm worker in the 18th century was not as affected by his or her illiteracy as an illiterate person in the first decade of the 21st century in Western society.

The personal characteristics barrier refers to the fact that people are of equal value, but are not equal. They differ in gender, length, social environment and so on. And which is relevant for this presentation they can differ in abilities. In some cases, when the differences are significantly big, we speak of disabilities.

Each person has a personal information space where (s)he can find the relevant information resources. It's created automatically when they are born and it develops and expands during their lifetime when they grow older: the learning and working carrier, social contacts and so on. Over the years we have seen a growth of technology, tools and applications to retrieve, process and disseminate information, changes in communication behaviour. Being 'connected' 24/7 has become a way of life. New technologies and 'new' social media offer easy dissemination of disinformation like spam and fake news. The effective and efficient use of information resources is not innate, but is part of the socialization process and has to be learned. There are three main types of education, namely: Formal, Informal and Non-formal. Formal learning is education normally delivered by trained teachers in a systematic intentional way within a school, higher education or university organized and monitored by governments. Informal education takes place outside of a structured curriculum. Non-Formal education, or 'learning by doing' find place through a variety of possibilities depending on the need of the learner and availability of resources.

National governments have a specific responsibility and role in formal education. They are taking care of the infrastructure and content in which the 'unknowing' become 'knowing'. They determine the goals of education and often the way they are to be achieved. Also the physical infrastructure in which the education takes place: building facilities, sport fields and, among others, the school library.

As educational systems and schools differ widely all over the world, school libraries do differ as well. As IFLA estimates that in 2019 there are 2,1 million libraries in the world (<https://librarymap.ifla.org/>) most of them will differ, depending on region. While in some countries an excellent infrastructure exists for both the school libraries as for training and education for school librarians, in other regions they are lacking completely or exist in a minimal format and access is not evenly spread over the population.

However, the differences ideally spoken, a school library is a school's physical and digital learning space where reading, inquiry, research, thinking, imagination, and creativity are central to students' information-to-knowledge journey and to their personal, social, and cultural growth. This physical and digital place is known by several terms: e.g., school media centre, centre for documentation and information, library resource centre, library learning commons. A school library is an educational concept ... Not a room with books and or computers. It enables access to information by learning how to have access, evaluate and use information in an efficient, effective and ethical way (fact finding).

To have an adequate properly functioning school library, each educational institute and library needs a school library policy, which includes Mission, Vision and Purpose. In the 'Mission Statement', a concise explanation of the reason for existence is formulated. It describes the organization's purpose and its overall intention. The mission statement supports the vision and serves to communicate purpose and direction to all stakeholders. Stakeholders are not limited to the library staff but include School managers, Teachers, IT staff, Volunteers, Parents, Related libraries (e.g., Public libraries) and, of course, the students themselves.

In the IFLA/UNESCO School Library Manifesto 1999 the Mission of the School Library is described as 'The school library offers learning services, books and resources that enable all members of the school community to become critical thinkers and effective users of information in all formats and media.'

The Manifesto was extremely well received all over the world and translated into 35 languages; librarians from all over the world are using the manifesto to raise the profile of school libraries in their own schools, own regions and own countries.

To enable schools to develop a suitable polity and organize an efficient and effective school library the IFLA School libraries section published in 2002 the IFLA/UNESCO School Library Guidelines. These were followed by a 2nd edition in 2015 and available in 23 languages. There are 6 chapters:

1. Mission and purposes of a school library
2. Legal and financial framework
3. Human resources

4. Physical and digital resources
5. Programs and activities
6. Evaluation and public relations

Next to the Guidelines, the IASL/IFLA Joint Committee has also developed a set of workshop materials based on the Guidelines. Workshop materials consist of an Introduction and six Modules. The material can be used freely and adapted to meet local needs.

Final Remarks

School libraries can play an important role in training students to develop themselves and become responsible citizens in the 21st century where the access and fair use of reliable information has become more urgent than ever. School libraries are a school's physical and digital learning space.

Therefore, schools need to develop a 'School Library Policy', aligned with the school policy, where the aims, tasks, responsibilities and procedures of all stakeholders are clearly defined and are actively put into practice by the stakeholders.

The IFLA School Libraries Section offers Guidelines for School Libraries and material for workshop(s) in which the implementation of the School Library can be developed.

Acknowledgments

This paper is not the result of a scientific research, but is the reflection of the author on the subject.

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<https://iasl-online.org/>

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School Libraries Section

<https://www.ifla.org/school-libraries>

Improving Students' Achievement by Developing School Libraries, by Ornella Papa⁴² in collaboration with Rita Marzoli⁴³

Abstract

Italian students' results from OECD PISA and IEA ICILS international surveys 2018, aligned with the INVALSI national surveys results, show the urgency of identifying measures to improve Italian school system. Data collected from INVALSI in school year 2014-2015 allowed us to conduct a descriptive research on the relationship between School Library and students' achievement. Information about the School Library comes from the School Questionnaire compiled by School Principals, as part of the Self-Assessment Report (RAV). The results of the INVALSI Tests are used as indicators of school achievement for the school grades investigated. This research is carried out in two studies: the first one exploratory on 9896 schools in grade 5, 8 and 10; the second one thorough on the 7326 grade 5 and 10 in which the administration of Student Questionnaire makes available the ESCS index, representative of the socio-economic and cultural background. The analyses prove better performance in schools with well-functioning School Libraries and large collection size. These results are accentuated, the differences are always significant, comparing schools with Low and Medium low ESCS.

Keywords: school library; student achievement; socio-economic and cultural backgrounds.

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Introduction

The international surveys conducted by OECD⁴⁴ and IEA⁴⁵, in collaboration with national research Institutes⁴⁶, have highlighted some critical aspects in Italian school system. The most important among these is the decline in the results of Italian students after the primary school, which instead shows a good preparation, as demonstrated by the IEA PIRLS⁴⁷ survey conducted on students in the fourth grade of schooling⁴⁸. Another serious problem of our school system is the high variability of the results both between regions with different GDP and between different types of the secondary schools, results confirmed by the annual surveys of the INVALSI SNV⁴⁹. Moreover, the entire Country recorded in 2018 a decrease in Reading Literacy score at OECD PISA⁵⁰ survey and worrying results in Information Literacy at ICILS⁵¹ survey. The opportunity to developing School Libraries (henceforth SLs) for the improvement of student learning is grounded in numerous studies conducted internationally, some of which are very recent. Just the IEA PIRLS⁵² showed that Italian students' scores (in line with international ones) are higher if their SL's book heritage is wider, the scores are lowest when the schools are without SL. The results of two studies (Marzoli & Papa, 2019a and 2019b), carried out on INVALSI data⁵³ and presented below, suggest that SL could play an important role in the Italian school system, of particular relevance for schools with low achievement. The comparison on the didactic function covered by the SL and by the School Librarian in European countries such as Denmark, Germany, France, England, Norway and Poland (Bolletti, Lombello & Marquardt, 2000) reveals an historical gap that Italy in this particular moment could recover. In fact, during the epidemic from Covid-19, because of the forced passage to distance learning, the political decision makers perceived the urgency of a modernization of the Italian education system towards digitization and

⁴⁴ Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development.

⁴⁵ International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.

⁴⁶The National Institute for the Evaluation of the Educational System of Education and Training (INVALSI) for Italy.

⁴⁷ Progress in International Reading Literacy Study.

⁴⁸ See Table 5.

⁴⁹ National Evaluation System.

⁵⁰ Progress in International Reading Literacy Study.

⁵¹International Computer and Information Literacy Study.

⁵² In both cycles 2011 and 2016.

⁵³ <https://invalsi-serviziostatistico.cineca.it/>.

information literacy. As supported by authoritative Institutions at an international level (see, for example, the *IFLA⁵⁴/Unesco⁵⁵ Manifest on the School Library⁵⁶*) the SL can assume strategic importance precisely in the development of programs for media and information skills. Really the first steps towards the development of SL in Italy have already been taken with Law 107/2015 which proclaims it a place of learning *par excellence*, an information and documentation centre for the promotion of culture. In particular Action #24 of the National Digital System Plan⁵⁷ provides the development of ‘innovative’ libraries to which it attributes a key role in overcoming all forms of disadvantages, including the digital divide. The characteristics of this modern SL are approved with enthusiasm by some exponents of the library community because it answers the need of connection between reading and other forms of textuality widespread in the digital age (Roncaglia, 2016). However, the general hope - and primarily that of library community - is an exhaustive legislation to give continuity as soon as possible to the functioning of the SL, freeing to sporadic projects (Venuda, 2016). Furthermore, the allocation of funds for the realization of innovative libraries didn’t concern schools without a library (or without a referent who participates in the project) even increasing the differences among schools. Similarly, the recent law in support of reading (February 5, 2020) finances the training of personnel who manage school library networks but does not provide incentives for schools where, for the most varied reasons, the SL is not functioning or it is not present.

OECD PISA 2018 Results

The OECD PISA international survey measures, in many Countries⁵⁸, 15-year-olds’ ability to use their reading, mathematics and science knowledge and skills to meet real-life challenges, allowing the comparison between different school systems. The survey is carried out every 3 years; each edition focuses on a disciplinary area and dedicates fewer items to the other two disciplinary areas. The most significant results are those relating to the main area of each edition, as well as the most awaited comparisons are those between editions with the same

⁵⁴ International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions.

⁵⁵ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

⁵⁶ Italian version AIB (1999, translation by Luisa Marquardt revised in 2003).

⁵⁷ Acronym PNSD.

⁵⁸ Currently the countries involved are 79.

main area - every 9 years. The first cycle, PISA 2000, had Reading Literacy as main area, the same of PISA 2009 and PISA 2018. In this recent edition, Italian students obtained in Reading Literacy an average score of 476, significantly lower than the OECD average (487); among the 37 participating OECD countries Italy ranks after 23rd place together with Switzerland, Latvia, Hungary, Lithuania, Iceland and Israel (INVALSI, 2020). In line with the international average, 77% of Italian students reach or exceed the minimum level of competence in Reading Literacy, but in Italy only 5% of students are 'top performers' (9% in the international average) and there is a higher percentage of 'low performers' (18% compared to 14% of the international average) with worrisome numbers in some type of schools⁵⁹ and in regions with lower GDP⁶⁰. However, observing the data from PISA 2012⁶¹ we can see improvement in the results of some needy regions⁶² (INVALSI, 2013) despite the 'segregation'⁶³ of students with low performance in some types of schools. The comparison between the cycles with Reading Literacy as main area shows a worsening in Italian students' results, in fact the average score (476) differs significantly (Figure 1) from those obtained in the 2009 Cycle (486) and in the 2000 Cycle (487).

⁵⁹ Vocational Training, Professional Institutes and partly Technical Institutes.

⁶⁰ South regions and Islands.

⁶¹ Cycle after strong PON (National Operational Program 'Education') investments in regions with GDP below the European average. The main domains of investigation were Mathematics and Problem Solving.

⁶² Puglia for example.

⁶³ Much more than in other OECD countries.

Figure 1. Italian students' Reading Literacy results in different PISA Cycles

Comparing to PISA 2000, the result of Italian students decreases significantly also in macro-areas with high GDP (North East -26 points; North West -19 points) and in all types of secondary schools (on average -26 points); same trend emerges considering PISA 2009 results. Interesting to note that in the 2000 and 2009 Cycles the tests administered were paper-based, while in PISA 2018 particular computerized tests have been used: adaptive test that propose subsequent question more or less easy based on the wrong or right answer of the student. Among the sub-scales related to the cognitive processes involved in the tests, Italian students are less performer in the process of *Finding information* (average score 470).

IEA ICILS 2018 Results

With the aim to promote the development of school programs adapted to the transformations of the digital age, since 2013 the IEA has been carrying out the ICILS study on digital and information competencies of 13 and a half years old students in various countries. The information competence, developed with the contribution above all of library science but also of psychology, relates to the processes of identifying information needs, researching and locating information, evaluating their quality. In ICILS (Fraillon et al., 2019) the information literacy is conceptualized as the set of skills that an individual must possess to meet the requirements imposed by the communication society. In addition to these aspects, ICILS extends the attention to the phases of transformation and communication of information. Italy

didn't participate in ICILS 2013, while in ICILS 2018 ranks 11th among the 14 participating countries, with an average score of 461 compared to the international average of 500. Denmark ranks first, just the Country where the SL is compulsory in all schools, the one with the highest percentage of GDP dedicated to school system. The Table 1 shows the average scores of the 12 Countries and the two benchmarking⁶⁴ participants (shown in alphabetical order).

Participants	Results
Chile	476
Denmark	553
Finland	531
France	499
Germany	518
Italy	461
Kazakhstan	395
Korea	542
Luxembourg	482
North Rhine-Westphalia	515
Portugal	516
Russian Federation (Moscow)	549
United States	519
Uruguay	450
International average	500

Table 1. ICILS 2018 results (IEA Source)

Beyond the single national averages, the analyses on ICILS data show a general problematic situation, in fact at the international level only 21% of ICILS students are 'independent computer users' and only 2% of them are capable to 'critically evaluate information'. From the results obtained, the IEA concludes that:

- digital natives do not have sophisticated digital skills;
- providing schools with computer equipment is not enough to improve students' digital and information skills;
- differences in student scores are greater within countries than between countries;

⁶⁴ Territorial realities - provinces or regions - that take part in the survey for their own internal comparison objective, but whose data are not considered in the calculation of the international average.

- there is a gap associated with socio-economic backgrounds of students; specifically, students from favourable socioeconomic backgrounds have significantly better scores (on average >30 points).

Participating actively in the knowledge society necessarily requires the acquisition of a mastery in the research, evaluation and use of information, so the results of ICILS 2018 cannot be underestimated, especially in countries where information competence has been most lacking, such as Italy. Influential national voices, including that of the CNR⁶⁵, require the integration of this competence into the Italian education system, from primary schools to higher education, though it still remains the issue ‘how’ to integrate it with the other disciplines. In fact, the introduction of information literacy as a separate subject raises the same perplexities as the single teaching for digital technologies, which led to the partial failure (Calvani, 2013). A complete review of teaching/learning patterns may be required, including the development of these competences in relation to other areas of expertise. A transformation that cannot ignore the strong link between Information Literacy and SL, supported by the documents of authoritative Institutions at international level. The IFLA/Unesco School Library Manifesto published in 1999 and translated into many languages⁶⁶ promotes SL as an integral part of the educational process a strategic environment for the for information literacy; in particular it recognizes to the SLs a key role in the development of Media and Information Skills Programs (Grizzle et al., 2013). Equal emphasis on the importance of SLs for Information Literacy can be found in the IFLA Guidelines for School Libraries, published in 2002⁶⁷ and reviewed in 2015⁶⁸. The IASL⁶⁹ goes in the same direction, since almost 50 years, organizing an annual conference for the comparison between school

⁶⁵ National Research Council.

⁶⁶ Italian edition by the Italian Library Association, 1999: Translation by Luisa Marquardt revised in 2003.

⁶⁷ Italian edition by the National Commission of School Libraries of the Italian Library Association. Coordination and review by Luisa Marquardt and Paolo Odasso, Rome, AIB, 2004.

⁶⁸ Italian translation by Luisa Marquardt.

⁶⁹ International Association of School Librarianship.

librarians, teachers and researchers on how SLs can contribute to lifelong learning and the development of information skills.

In addition to these important Institutions, ENSIL⁷⁰ is one of the most recent, a European network that aims to document and share experiences of use of the library from an Information Literacy perspective. Also at the national level, contributions have long been given to suggest methods and content of information education courses in the library (Ballestra, 2011) and there is not lack of virtuous examples, although still not widespread.

School Library and Students' Achievement

The positive relationship between SL and students' achievement, showed by numerous studies at international level, has recently been confirmed at national level by two studies (Marzoli & Papa, 2019a and 2019b) on INVALSI data from the 2014-2015 school year, in particular:

- a first exploratory study on 9896 schools of grades 5, 8, 10;
- a second more in-depth study on the 7326 schools of grades 5 and 10 for which socio-economic and cultural background data were available.

The information on the SLs comes from the School Principals Questionnaire⁷¹ completed as part of the School Self-Assessment Report (RAV). The data collected show the presence of the School Library in 90% of schools unfortunately many Libraries don't have resources and basic services: 30% of SLs don't have a Library Referent, the 18% don't have a Reference Room, in 19% of SLs the Loan service is not available (Table 2).

Reference and Basic Services	SLs Percentage
Library Referent	70%
Reference Room	82%
Loan service	81%

Table 2. Reference and Basic Services

⁷⁰ European Network for School Library and Information Literacy.

⁷¹ <http://www.invalsi.it/snv/index.php?action=questscu>.

The SLs provided with advanced resources and services are a minimal percentage, in fact only 23% of SLs have an online Catalog (OPAC), 10% of SLs are part of a Library network and a small 8% practice Interlibrary loan (Table 3).

Advanced Services	SLs Percentage
Online Catalog (OPAC)	23%
Library network	10%
Interlibrary loan	8%

Table 3. Advanced services

Functioning and collections of the School Library

With the previous variables which allow to infer the operation of the SL, a ‘Functioning’ Index has been created, it is divided into 3 levels:

- Adequate Functioning
- Minimum Functioning
- Absent Functioning

The SL Functioning levels have been linked to the results of the students in the INVALSI standardized tests. In the following graph (Figure 2), you can observe how Reading Literacy scores increase when the SL Functioning level increase, in all school grades investigated.

Figure 2. INVALSI Reading Literacy scores in schools with different SL Functioning

Below (Table 4) the results of the ANOVA which confirm in all school grades the significant difference in Reading Literacy scores between schools with different SL Functioning.

School Grades	Fisher's F	Sign.
Grade 5	35.442	.000
Grade 8	23.733	.000
Grade 10	41.136	.000

Table 4. ANOVA results per school with different SL Functioning

In these school grades the association between SL collections and Reading Literacy scores, detected by IEA for grade 4 of schooling, will be verified. The results obtained from the PIRLS 2016 survey are shown in Table 5. As you can see, Italian students perform better as the number of SL volumes increases; the lowest scores are obtained by students attending a school without SL (in line with international results).

Countries	Results per different number of SL volumes			
	> 5000 v.	501-5000 v.	< 500 v.	No SL
Saudi Arabia	~	404	438	431
Australia	544	546	~	~
Austria	551	542	540	538
Azerbaijan	477	475	449	~
Bahrain	465	433	426	~
Belgium (Flemish)	~	522	524	528
Belgium (French)	523	506	496	494
Bulgaria	572	548	540	531
Canada	547	540	~	~
Chile	514	492	481	508
Denmark	550	546	~	545
Egypt	358	338	307	316
United Arab Emirates	485	421	411	~
England	565	558	556	562
Finland	573	567	562	568
France	485	512	507	523

Georgia	490	488	491	~
Germany	~	542	526	537
Hong Kong SAR	569	570	~	~
England	565	558	556	562
Iran, Rep. Islamic	~	471	417	387
Ireland	564	565	570	569
Northern Ireland	561	562	571	571
Israel	550	533	528	520
Italy	559	551	548	540
Kazakhstan	537	534	533	~
Kuwait	426	396	383	~
Latvia	562	558	531	~
Lithuania	548	549	548	~
Macao SAR	544	542	~	~
Malta	446	454	443	456
Morocco	~	404	389	337
Norway	560	560	553	549
New Zealand	528	527	498	~
Oman	426	419	407	417
Netherlands	~	543	542	553
Poland	565	563	~	589
Portugal	528	525	536	~
Qatar	443	446	426	~
Czech Republic	551	541	541	547
Slovak Republic	533	536	539	525
Russian Federation	586	575	537	~
Singapore	582	562	~	~
Slovenia	541	550	534	~
Spain	540	528	518	505
United States	556	543	561	515
South Africa	393	375	320	301
Sweden	558	556	543	545
Chinese Taipei	560	549	~	~
Hungary	563	550	~	537
International Averages	525	512	494	501

Table 5.- PIRLS 2016 results in school with different number of SL Volumes (IEA Source)

Referring to the results of the INVALSI Reading Literacy Tests in grades 5, 8 and 10, a positive relationship between Book heritage and (higher) scores is confirmed, with better results in schools where the SL has a larger number of volumes, as shown in the following graph (Figure 3).

Figure 3. INVALSI Reading Literacy results in schools with different SL Book Heritage

ANOVA⁷² confirms the significance of the differences between groups in all school grades analysed (Table 6) but it shows more considerable values (higher Fisher's F) for grade 10.

School grades	Fisher's F	Sign.
Grade 5	49,854	,000
Grade 8	64,796	,000
Grade 10	115,410	,000

Table 6. ANOVA results per schools with different SL Book Heritage

An observation moved to these results is that schools with the highest performance do have a library but they are also located in areas with

⁷² Analysis of Variance is a set of statistical techniques that allow the confrontation among two or more groups of data by comparing the internal variability of these groups with the variability between the groups.

the highest GDP or, as regards grade 10, are represented by Lyceum schools. To this regard, analyses were conducted exclusively on Lyceum schools and the results confirm that even within this type of school the Book heritage is associated with students' results (Table 7).

SL Book Heritage	Average scores in Lyceum
>5000 volumes	64
500 - 5000 volumes	59
< 500 volumes	54

Table 7. Reading Literacy scores in Lyceums with different SL Book Heritage

ANOVA confirmed a significant score difference on Lyceums with different numbers of SL volumes (Table 8).

Type of high school	Fisher's F	Sign.
Lyceum	26,717	,000

Table 8. ANOVA Results per Lyceums with Different BS Book Heritage

In the next paragraph you can see the results of the analyses conducted on schools divided by socio-economic and cultural background of the catchment area; it is another important variable whose influence on the relationship between SL and performance was considered interesting to investigate.

School library and schools with different ESCS⁷³

To further investigate the results obtained, the ESCS (Economic, Social and Cultural Status) Index was introduced in the analyses. The ESCS is calculated on the basis of representative information about students socio-economic and cultural background, gathered from the Student Questionnaire administered in grades 5 and 10.

The School ESCS - the average of the students ESCS - allowed to divide the schools into 2 big groups:

- Schools with M. HIGH ESCS (namely schools with High or Medium high ESCS);
- Schools with M. LOW ESCS (namely schools with Low or Medium low ESCS).

⁷³ Economic, Social and Cultural Status.

The analyses carried out separately on the two big groups confirm a particular relevance of SL in schools with a disadvantaged catchment area. Both ANOVA (Tables 9 and 10) are significant but the differences per amplitude of Book Heritage appear greater (higher Fisher's F) for the Schools with M. LOW ESCS.

School grades	F di Fisher	Sign.
Grade 5	33,693	,000
Grade 10	42,864	,000

Table 9. ANOVA results per schools with different Book Heritage M. LOW ESCS

School grades	F di Fisher	Sign.
Grade 5	10,643	,000
Grade 10	25,729	,000

Table 10. ANOVA results per schools with different Book Heritage M. HIGH ESCS

Figure 4. Literacy scores in schools with different Library Heritage M. LOW ESCS

Similarly, comparing Tables 11 and 12, greater differences are

observed, in relation to the SL Functioning levels, in schools with M.LOW ESCS.

School grades	F di Fisher	Sign.
Italian grade 5	29,768	,000
Italian grade 10	22,089	,000

Table 11. ANOVA results in schools with different SLs functioning M.LOW ESCS

School grades	F di Fisher	Sign.
Italian grade 5	8,174	,000
Italian grade 10	6,024	,002

Table 12. ANOVA results in schools with different SLs functioning M.HIGH ESCS

Furthermore, the *post hoc*⁷⁴ are not all significant for the Schools with M.HIGH ESCS, only the differences between the extreme operating levels of the SL (Absent-Adequate) are significant. On the other hand, for schools with M.LOW ESCS all post hoc are significant or each level of functioning is associated with a score significantly different from the others; these scores are shown in Figure 5.

⁷⁴ Bonferroni test for *a posteriori* multiple comparisons allows you to identify which differences between groups determined the total significance of ANOVA.

Figure 5. Results in schools with different SL Functioning - M.LOW ESCS

By investigating the endowments and the functioning of the SLs of schools with different ESCS, results, on which it is necessary to dwell, were found. Actually, in schools with M. LOW ESCS only 15% of SLs have an adequate functioning and only 27% have a Book heritage of over 5000 volumes. The percentages in schools with M. HIGH ESCS are much higher: 21% of SLs have an adequate functioning and 40% has a Book heritage of over 5000 volumes (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Book Heritage and SL Functioning in school with different ESCS

Therefore, in the light of analyses that demonstrate a positive relationship between SL and student performance also in schools with

M.LOW ESCS, unfortunately in these schools the SLs are less widespread, less functional and have a reduced Book heritage.

Final Remarks

An active and aware participation in the society of the 21st century necessarily requires a mastery in the research, evaluation and use of information that can only be acquired through information literacy. School measures during this Pandemic have made more evident the need for a renewed interest in Digitization and Information Literacy, critical issues already raised by the ICILS 2018 Survey. In particular, the Innovative library established with law 107/2015, could play the necessary role for the development of digital and information skills, attributed to her in the PNSD, in line with what has long been sanctioned by the documents of authoritative international Institutions. Another good reason why a plan of ‘modernization’ of the school system needs SL diffusion and strengthening as well as dedicated and professional personnel⁷⁵. In Italy, the foreseen ‘lesson ‘ of Digital citizenship (from September 2020) would find an adequate completion in Information literacy and a privileged place of development in the SL.

Investing in SLs can also counteract the high variability of results within our school system. In fact, the analyses conducted on INVALSI data show a positive association between student performance and SLs functioning as well as having wide collection. This association is particularly strong in schools with M. LOW ESCS where unfortunately the SLs are less present, less operational and have less resources. It is not possible to ignore such relevant data since the European Commission itself is focused on inequalities in education. The Report *‘Education and Training Monitor, 2017’* recommended that the educational policies of the EU countries are aimed at rebalancing as soon as possible the gap caused by the socio-economic and cultural disadvantage. In our country, low socio-economic family background is often associated to the territorial one, moreover worsened by the ‘segregation’ of schools that have fewer equipment and resources. Therefore, in respect of educational equity, an action that also leverages the SLs to counter unsatisfactory results attributable to family, territorial and school conditions less favourable to learning appears

⁷⁵ The SL and the school librarian are foreseen since 1990 in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano by specific provincial legislation.

urgent. The admonition of Prof. Tullio De Mauro, during an interview twenty years ago to ‘Tuttoscuola’, is incredibly topical the states that: ‘to strengthen school libraries of all levels and make them actually accessible - that is, information and training centres and not display cases of intangible books and multimedia materials – is of great importance for the development of live training activities’⁷⁶.

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Chapter 1.4

The Relationships between Middle School Libraries and Students' Learning Outcomes in China, by Jing Zhang,⁷⁹ Naiyi Yang and Yi Zhou

Abstract

The PISA 2018 survey showed that, on average, students from Beijing, Shanghai and Jiangsu Zhejiang (China) outperformed students from the other 79 countries in reading, mathematics and science. How did China carry out the cultivation of core competencies for students to achieve such results, and what role does the middle school library play in it? In such a context, the research intends to make a preliminary observation and analysis of the above questions from the perspective of case study. The paper first analysed related policies, projects and projects on 'reading for all' and Chinese subject education etc., through the method of content analysis, to comb through the development background and important path of the cultivation of Chinese students' reading literacy. Then the research selected several cultivation practices in middle schools as a case, and analysed their overall design ideas, definite steps and effectiveness evaluation in the cultivation of reading literacy, and aimed to discuss the function realization and development space of the middle school library.

Keywords: reading literacy and school library, correlation, middle school library, PISA 2018, content analysis.

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Session 2

Innovative School Library Spaces

Chapter 2

The Library as a Resource of Well-being and a Place of Positive Learning: An Environmental Psychology Perspective, by Giuseppe Carrus⁸⁰

Abstract

The speech introduces and comments on the session dedicated to the creation of innovative spaces for the school library. The contribution starts from the definition of 'restorative environments' and their impact on personal wellbeing and interpersonal relationships; reflects on the characteristics of the environments associated by users with well-being (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1998), and then focuses on some innovative and qualitative aspects that emerge from the interventions of the new institution, renovation or expansion of school libraries, in which it is also possible to identify regenerative.

Keywords: restorative environments; well-being; innovative school library.

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Introduction

In this work we present a general theoretical framework about the role of libraries to promote human wellbeing, with potential applications in different areas (e.g., educational, social, environmental). We focus in particular on the implications for the field of environmental education and environmental psychology (e.g., Bonnes & Carrus, 2004). Many contributions in this field of study have investigated the evaluation that people make of the characteristics of their environments of daily life, as a function of a conscious self-regulation of personal behaviour during social interaction (e.g., Guéguen & Stefan, 2016).

The theme of the relationship between people and the environment finds its ideal collocation also within the environmental psychological studies on ‘restorative environments’, which refer to that typology of places that promote, and not simply permit, the recovery of a general condition of psychological well-being, which usually is expressed by different components: stress reduction, attention restoration, increase of positive emotions (Hartig et al., 2014). More recently, some works also suggest that these consequences also have a positive impact on the quality of social relations (e.g., Guéguen & Stefan, 2016) and might therefore have important implications in the educational field (e.g., Carrus, Passiatore, Pirchio & Scopelliti, 2015).

Environment, Well-being and Learning

An interesting line of research has investigated the role of the physical environment on the development of the child. In a review, Evans (2006) emphasizes how ecological models for the study of human development have focused mainly on the psychosocial characteristics of children's life contexts (Bronfenbrenner 1979), almost ignoring the physical context. Among the fundamental environmental variables for the development and well-being of the child, Evans (2006) mentions in particular aspects such as the presence / absence of toxic substances, noise, crowding, the quality of the residence and the neighbourhood, the presence of green spaces, and the educational contexts. Following this perspective, it can be seen that the experience of restorative environments is clearly associated with greater well-being of children.

Characteristics of Restorative Environments

But what are the characteristics of the environments that are most frequently associated with the well-being of its users?

According to Kaplan & Kaplan (1989), an environment with a high restorative potential must have four fundamental properties or components: 1) being-away; 2) extent; 3) fascination; 4) compatibility, that is:

- 1) guarantee physical or psychological evasion from the routinary aspects of life;
- 2) have sufficient spatial extension or meaning such as to allow physical or psychological exploration, and sufficient coherence between its elements;
- 3) capture interest automatically and without requiring mental effort;
- 4) meet the preferences and inclinations of the individual who moves within it.

Restorative environments can also be analysed as 'positive' environments. In a recent book, Corral-Verdugo and his colleagues (2014) proposed the concept of 'positive environments', to identify those physical environments of human behaviour that are characterized by two distinct specific characteristics. First, they are capable of producing positive effects for the individuals and communities that live, use and populate them. Second, they also require some degree of care, attention and appropriation by their users. Scholars who have proposed an approach based on the concept of positive psychology would probably agree in finding an interesting parallel between these ideas and the general concept of Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi's 'flow' theory. This theory well describes the optimal psychological state in which individuals feel whenever they engage in some enjoyable but challenging activity, and the long-term benefits to humans of systematic flow experiences (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). In this sense, the library certainly appears, from a theoretical point of view, a place that could be identified as a restorative environment or a positive environment.

The School Library as a Restorative Environment

Following this theoretical perspective, it can be argued that libraries in general, and school libraries in particular, can play an important role as a 'restorative environment', that is, a place that has the function and task of promoting human well-being and development, and not only to allow the carrying out of activities, however important they are, such as the reading and use of texts. Libraries can thus be framed as positive environments according to the definition proposed by Corral-Verdugo and colleagues (2014).

The motivation for knowledge and exploration of the environment, and the processes of environmental assessment are in fact key factors for understanding and explaining the processes of self-regulation of social behaviour, and can be identified as basic factors for positive adaptation and for the effectiveness within the learning and education process, considering the micro-system and the meso-system of the educational process, according to the ecological theories of human development (eg, Bronfenbrenner, 1979). These concepts could also be relevant for a deeper understanding of the processes of environmental education and the promotion of sustainability in the educational and social spheres.

These aspects are important first of all to the social interaction that occurs directly in educational contexts, both inside the classroom and outside it, in other educational spaces, such as libraries, outdoor spaces or school gardens (see e.g. Carrus et al., 2015). Furthermore, the question of a more conscious information processing regarding the value attributed to one's perception, imagination and abstraction is relevant for understanding the cognitions and behaviours of pupils and students even outside the educational context. This could be particularly relevant for promoting the ability to consider the future consequences of one's actions, in relation to other humans, other species and ecosystems in general (e.g., Strathman et al., 1994). The implications of cognitive and social conceptualizations on time and space have also been suggested by some authors in the field of environmental psychology, and this could have strong relevance for environmental education practices (see, for example, Corral-Verdugo, Fraijo -Sing, & Pinheiro, 2006).

Furthermore, we can here argue that, in addition to the educational context, the approach we propose here is relevant to better understand the relationship between the person and the environment in general. Indeed, understanding the interaction between individual perceptions and cognitions, the built environment and man-made habitats, and the behavioural aspects of interacting with the physical and social environment, require a more general consideration of human evaluation processes. An example in this field is crowding, a problem that has been found to affect the quality of life and human relations in different types of environments. Crowding has to do with the negative evaluation of the perceived density in a given space; the perception of the loss of control and the large volume of information entering the perceptual system of the subjects is an important part of this evaluation

process. Based on the vast literature on crowding in environmental psychology, it would also be interesting to carry out studies on libraries, adopting an evaluative as well as descriptive approach. Even starting from the paradigm of positive or regenerative environments, libraries could be interesting arenas for applying a theory of assessment, since it has been shown how variables at different levels (e.g., individual, social or developmental) can interact in influencing the relationship between the perception of the restorative abilities of a given environment and the subjective well-being of its users. In this sense, the ability of libraries to arouse positive emotions and evaluations on the part of their users, not only in education and schools, could be explained by the ability to influence the quality of human life in contexts of daily life through the experience of restorative environments.

From this point of view, the interesting experiences of restructuring and management of school libraries so brilliantly illustrated by the authors who animated this session, certainly offer important starting points for reflection, and also for the possible planning of future studies and research in the psychological and educational field.

Final Remarks

Many good practices referring to the experiences of the design, construction and management of school libraries were presented in this session, such as those of the library of the 'Pascoli' secondary school, the complex of the IC Levi - Montalcini in Turin (see Di Perna, Magnano, Maranta, *infra*), the 'Alessandro Cieri' school library at the primary school 'Randaccio' in Rome, the IC 'Mattarella' in Rome (see Buttinelli, Ficorilli, Marino, *infra*), or experiences such as the widespread library and the 'reading corners' at the Liceo 'Vivona' in Rome (cf. Benincasa, Sangalli, Rubino, *infra*) and the 'Mattarella' library at IC Modena 3. These are all examples of how the management and restructuring of libraries can provide an important contribution to the creation of restorative environments in learning contexts.

It would be interesting, for the future, to conduct empirical research in this field to explore, on the one hand, the perceptions and evaluations of users regarding the spaces of libraries and, on the other hand, to monitor the positive effects of library use. Environments that are so well designed and built could be a real-life setting to study how they can affect the learning processes and well-being of pupils and teachers.

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Chapter 2.1.1

Aligning the School Building Spaces to Educational Innovation, by Laura Di Perna⁸¹

Abstract

The contribution underlines how the re-development of the 'Pascoli' school-building - whose space is arranged in learning environments, including a distributed library - implied a change both inside the school, in teaching and learning activities, and outside, in the relationship with the local community and the services addressed to it.

Keywords: teaching innovation; learning environments school library; distributed library; local community; collaboration.

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‘Torino fa Scuola’ [i.e., Turin Makes School, <https://torinofascuola.it/>], a school building redevelopment project in Turin, came out with innovative learning environments and spaces at ‘Pascoli’ Middle School (part of the ‘Rita Levi-Montalcini’ Comprehensive School, where I have been working as the School Principal for the last six years). The project was designed according to the evolution of our school community’s pedagogical approaches, keeping an eye on constraints and resources given by the existing building arrangement.

The redevelopment process stimulated the entire school community to adopt an innovative approach in the way of schooling and, above all, living the school as a beautiful and meaningful place, where it is possible to compare, collaborate, dialogue, improve, and grow.

The school teachers, with great enthusiasm, constantly look for cultural resources, methodologies, educational tools necessary to carry on an active and modern teaching, aiming at fostering students’ self-direction in learning and their well-being at school.

Instructional activities - working individually and in group, experimenting and studying the subjects - take place not only in classrooms, but also in the distributed spaces, laboratories and reading rooms, that develop themselves vertically on the two floors, since the school is conceived as a dynamic, open and interconnected educational space.

Among these spaces, the distributed library represents a training place for meeting, socializing, consulting, exchanging and becomes a resource for the territory, since it opens its doors to citizens on some days of the week.

In this process of change, it was essential to share with all of the players in the school community an open, flexible, interactive vision of ‘school’ in order to reach our children and make them able fall in love with culture.

A ‘Distributed Library’ at ‘Giovanni Pascoli’ Middle School, Turin, by Daniela Maranta⁸²

Abstract

The middle school ‘Giovanni Pascoli’ is part of the ‘Rita Levi – Montalcini’ Comprehensive School, which is located in the third district, densely populated and full of different places of cultural interest. The Comprehensive School comprises four complexes, from kindergarten to middle school. The ‘distributed library’ of ‘Giovanni Pascoli’ Middle school, after the renovation completed in September 2019, introduces itself to students and users as an element of discontinuity with respect to the past. It aims to become a cultural reference point not only for the school community but also for the whole city area that hosts it. The school library was conceived and structured for this purpose, starting from its location on different floors, passing through the thematic specificity attributed to each reading area. The welcome that each place offers is already stimulating the students to discover new learning opportunities, as well as motivating them to participate in various activities, also in collaboration with the network of school libraries to which the school adheres.

Keywords: educational innovation, learning environments, school library, distributed library, territory, cooperation.

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A Distributed Library Project

The middle school ‘Giovanni Pascoli’ – following the renovation completed in September 2019 - has a school library defined ‘distributed’ for spatial and conceptual reasons; in fact, it was conceived and structured as an open space, located over several floors, each with its own thematic peculiarity.

It aims to become a cultural reference point playing a central role in the documentation and information literacy activities not only for the school community, but also for the whole city area that hosts it. The school library, in fact, cannot give up being both a physical place where everyone can experience the beauty of reading, and a point of enhancement and dissemination of cultural activities, that are promoted by the regional institutions, also through the debate around relevant issues.

The Spaces and the Activities

Students and users, going through the different floors of the building, can access the bibliographic and documentary material concerning different thematic areas. On the ground floor, we can find firstly the school’s newspaper library, designed to be a space for the citizenry, and then a reading area dedicated to sport, environment, travel, and curiosities from all over the world. In this space, we are organizing⁸³ moments of reading, study, and research related to the 2030 Agenda around issues concerning environmental protection, as it appeared urgent during the General States meeting organized on the November 12th, 2019 by ‘Torinoretelibri Piemonte’ (i.e., the Network of School Libraries of Piedmont).

The teachers of the school firmly believe that the school library must not only meet the legitimate requests for disciplinary study and the discovery of new texts to read, but must be also a place of stimulus towards the knowledge of the surrounding world and a guide for our young readers to their education as future citizens.

And therefore, given the easily accessible nature of this first reading area, in the early months of the school year 2019-2020 were organized two book market exhibitions, both in Italian and in English. This has encouraged the knowledge and the collaboration with local bookshops

⁸³ Autumn–Winter 2019–2020.

and, on the other hand, the awareness of the students in approaching the publishing products on the market. In this sense, the members of the library commission have defined the goal to give even more space to foreign language texts.

The next market exhibitions will host thematic workshops, especially in English, with possible afternoon opening to the adults too, because it is our firm belief that the value of reading can also be promoted through the organization of similar initiatives, regardless of age and starting condition.

These workshops, providing for the participation of specialized personnel, can also accompany our students in the construction of a personal bibliographic path.

Going on with the discovery of 'Pascoli' distributed library, we find a reference area, so-called for its nature as a consultation and reception room, with large spaces dedicated to the meeting of users of different ages and different backgrounds. Within this space it is also possible to meet our classical heritage consisting of those books that we presented to students as 'the voice of grandparents who still have something to tell us'. A corner dedicated to Giovanni Pascoli - the poet to whom our school was named - is under construction inside this area.

During school hours, this area is animated by students involved in storytelling activities and press reviews.

In this area – designed for reading and educational activities - it was possible to start a series of activities that the students have shown to appreciate because it, being a less structured place than the classroom, offers greater visual and relational stimuli. It is preferred by our students with special educational needs that we put at the center of our educational process. During the afternoon, currently for a day a week, the school's library opens up to the territory starting from this space, which, as has been said, has the right characteristics to act as a place of reference, reading, and lending narrative texts which, embracing the different literary genres, satisfy the needs of readers of all ages. For this purpose, the collaboration with local booksellers goes well beyond the setting up of the various book market exhibitions because they offer a precious help to the teachers in thinking and planning moments to promote the reading. On the upper floors, the reading areas of the Institute offer material relating to particular thematic areas, from the scientific-technological to the artistic one. The stimulus to read

specialist works is pushing students to deepen their knowledge, sometimes under the solicitation of the teachers, others independently.

Furthermore, the synergy between the physical environments of the reading areas and the classrooms gives life to the realization of projects which, inspired by the activity of 'Torinoretelibri' (the Turin school library network) and by the free initiative of the school teachers, enhances the relationships with local libraries.

Indeed, for us, the school has to be both a place of education and a centre for promoting the values of future citizens and this central role can be played by the school library, point of contact between the various cultural institutions whose aim is to improve the variety of services offered.

For this reason, our school library participates, for the second consecutive year, to the European project 'Read More' promoted by 'Torinoretelibri' giving at the disposal both of students and teachers, twenty minutes a day to cultivate the reading of a book based on their personal choice. During these twenty minutes, every student is free to move inside the reading areas of the school. In those precious minutes the teacher devotes himself to a free reading, together with his students, because we believe that learning also passes through a good practice to be imitated.

Joining this activity also offered students the opportunity to learn about 'Read On', a European project, which, in addition to 'Read More', hosts numerous other initiatives, in order to connect the world of the school with the families of our students. 'Read on' provides, by means of an online platform, interaction between students and writers to build stories together and answer student questions directly. Another strong point of our library, intended as a place for promoting activities and events, is its consolidated participation in initiatives such as 'Libriamoci. Giornate di lettura nelle scuole' (i.e., Let's Take Off with Books. Reading Days in Schools), promoted by 'Centro per il libro e la lettura' - CePeLL (i.e., The National Book and Reading Centre) - and the week dedicated to reading with 'Torino che legge' (i.e., Turin that Reads), a joint project by the City of Turin and the 'Forum del Libro' (i.e., Book Forum), in collaboration with the Piedmont Region, MIUR and the UNESCO Center, promoted on the occasion of the World Book and Copyright Day, established by UNESCO to be celebrated on the 23rd of April.

These activities are organized in two distinct moments in a year, during which middle school students meet other students, both from the same comprehensive school and from other schools in the area.

At the heart of the events, in both cases, there is the choice of an important theme, an aspect of the reality which students are invited to reflect on. The event named 'Torino che legge' also becomes an opportunity for our young readers to meet people in the street and to dedicate them beautiful moments of reading and reflection; moreover, the method of reading aloud acquires a central role in the cognitive and emotional development of the students. The development of vertical projects is significant for 'Torinoretelibri' and for us because the meeting between students of different ages can offer opportunities for personal enrichment.

Teaching Becomes Distributed

The presence of a 'distributed' library within the Pascoli school is progressively changing the relationship that students have with the concept of library: no longer in a closed place, where to find books or information material, but an open and articulated, accessible space, welcoming and above all stimulating. Within the various activities that were organized in the first part of the school year 2019-2020, the greater degree of involvement of the students was evident. They, with a growing spirit of initiative, began to attend the places designated for reading, preferring one or the other depending on the activities proposed or freely designed. I do not intend to indicate here exclusively the activities relating to the promotion of reading, but I refer to the numerous interconnections between the projects and the educational paths that involve students daily. And here the teaching becomes 'distributed' and this happens because, thanks to the presence of this type of library, there are no more physical or conceptual boundaries: individual or shared reading, so as a teaching activity proposed by the teacher, are carried out within the spaces of the library, capable of hosting numerous students at the same time and supporting cooperative learning activities. In a project with these characteristics a decisive role is played by digital resources: a catalog of e-books, audio-books, periodicals written in different languages, sheet music, movies and more, is increasingly supporting the growth and the cultural enrichment of our students. They are learning how much culture

should be considered in a global, never sectorial way, and how much this can be done through the study of works of different types and languages. The advantage is also from a methodological point of view because the presence of digital resources is offering us the opportunity to conduct transversal educational activities, drawing on numerous resources with high cultural profile. The 'distributed' library, with its digital soul, becomes part of the teaching itself and, at the same time, helps to spread it, going well beyond the boundaries of the walls of the classrooms, since every space of the school, properly set up, can be experienced as a place of study, comparison and debate around a topic of interest.

And teaching becomes 'distributed' every time it takes advantage of these spaces and change of perspective that is involving the whole school community. Experiencing these places is also having a positive impact on the level of attention and participation of the students during the school activity, so teaching is 'distributed' also because the life around the school library is positively changing the approach that students sometimes have with studying; the book is no longer exclusively a text to be studied but it is also an opportunity to meet and discover a common interest, a passion, a language that makes us feel part of a group.

The Future of the 'Pascoli' School's Distributed Library

Among the activities we wish to carry out in the following three years, we would like to create an integrated system starting from the creation of a union catalogue (OPAC) for all of the school libraries in the network. The cataloguing, which respects the standards ISBD and REICAT (Italian Cataloguing Rules) used in SBN (the National Library Network), is managed through a single management software, Clavis. When the cataloguing of our Library will be updated, it will be possible to find information concerning the physical and digital availability of each document in possession of 'Pascoli' or in possession of the numerous libraries belonging to the integrated system. I refer to the availability of resources in digital format thanks to the collaboration with the online Media Library On Line (MLOL) platform, also offering a rich catalog for the school (MLOL Scuola).

Furthermore, in a path finalized to reach an integration, at different levels, between school and public library systems, the 'Giovanni Pascoli' school library is available for participation to a project of a

Library system integrated between the Turin Civic Libraries and the School Libraries in the ‘Torinoretelibri’ network to sustain initiatives and good practices to promote reading.

Another important aspect for the ‘Pascoli’ school library is to contribute to a debate to support the birth of a specific professional figure who deals, within the school, with the book heritage and the activities to promote reading. Last but not least, the ‘Giovanni Pascoli’ library wishes to support, together with the other partners, the organization of activities to meet the objectives of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, signed by the governments of the 193 member countries of the United Nations General Assembly on September 25th, 2015. All existing projects will be supported, and, at the same time, we foresee the creation of new ones concerning, for instance, the creation of transversal reading groups - through social reading platforms - around the individual interests of the students.

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The Future School Is Here, and We Made It, by Raffaella Magnano⁸⁴

Abstract

‘Working on the school means first of all working on the community, on young people, to educate about beauty. In this case, vision is everything, it means being able to see beyond the real structural needs of a building, to realize the dream of an ideal school, optimizing resources and redesigning spaces even there, where spaces are not there’: this is how AREAPROGETTI and Archisbang rethought the ‘Pascoli’ Middle school within the ‘Torino fa scuola’ program. The distributed library and newspaper library constitute a strong reference point: like the entire structure, they are available to the school community and the local one as well. ‘We designed a library that develops vertically,’ explains Raffaella Magnano, an architect specializing in library design. The library is constantly evolving: conceived primarily as a place for extended teaching outside the classroom, it will be enriched with paper and digital documents, becoming in all respects a reference for the neighbours. Its characteristic shape, from the reading room on the mezzanine level, to the thematic libraries with comfortable stations that invite children to read for pleasure, makes it an ideal place for adhering to the various European shared reading projects. Through large windows, the library overlooks the gym, another flexible space designed to also become a theatre.

Keywords: distributed library; well-being; innovative spaces; learning; reading; middle school.

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The Future School Is Here, and We Made It

About 70% of the 40,000 school buildings in Italy were built before 1975. The aging of the structures, the inadequacy of seismic safety and the poor energy performances are an emergency to face, but at the same time a unique opportunity to renew the spaces for teaching.

As schools now tend to be considered new civic centres with qualified services such as libraries, auditoriums and meeting spaces, redevelopment is fundamental for urban regeneration.

The challenge of the project 'Torino fa scuola' (i.e., Turin Makes School) comes from these considerations; the project was promoted and supported by the 'Agnelli Foundation' and the 'Compagnia di San Paolo', in collaboration with the City of Turin and the 'Fondazione per la Scuola' (Foundation for the School), which allowed us to work on two emblematic cases study of the Italian school building heritage and to test an interesting prototype of partnership between public and private to streamline procedures and optimize resources.

The 'Pascoli' School project acts as a model of intervention on the typology of the nineteenth-century building, taking on the challenge of bringing innovative teaching within the walls of a protected historic building, permeated by structural and cultural constraints, breaking down the barriers of the classroom towards large impressive spaces that become inhabited environments.

Spaces design develops and enriches the ambitions of the pedagogical project. It enhances the strengths and recognizes the critical aspects of the existing building, furthermore it is a starting point to imagine other and unusual solutions, so as to achieve the objectives and fulfil the wishes of future students.

Continuous teaching requires large, bright spaces, contact with the outside, total accessibility of the rooms. The building puts itself at the service of the training project and becomes an integral part of it. The school is an inclusive space where it is possible to learn by playing and it becomes a reference point for children and the rest of the community.

The most complex interventions that give to the school a strong innovation are the creation of the roof terrace, the displacement of the entrance with the creation of an internal atrium and the mezzanine created to house the library. However, these interventions respect historical architecture and enhance its potential, hidden by interventions carried out in the economy over the years. The

redevelopment of the spaces has been integrated into a global rethinking of the building, with the aim of obtaining a school projected towards the future. A school with contemporary spaces and solutions, which maintains intact the characteristics that had marked its construction over the long years of activity.

The main staircase is a characteristic element of contemporary school buildings even if this was previously altered by the fire compartment. Thanks to the new design of the external safety stairs, it is possible to restore the initial design of the main stairs. They become, indeed, the fulcrum of the distribution system, exactly as it was originally thought. The new connections between the main staircase and the mezzanine levels and the roof slab are made with light metal walkways. They tend to disappear against the background of the walls of the stairwell because they are painted white. All the buffered arches are freed, representing a further element of return of the initial proportions.

The pre-existing technical blocks, made with an absolutely random design, are integrated with the new service compartments, joined to the floors and treated as fixed furniture elements.

To restore the dimensions of the corridor on the ground floor, previously occupied entirely by a compass that altered its proportions, the entrance was moved and a ramp was created to overcome the difference in height from the street level. In the same way in all the internal corridors, used for common activities, the infill of the arches towards the classrooms is eliminated, in favour of fixed furnishings and glazed portions on the lunettes, currently filled.

With a view to opening and releasing the historical supporting structure, the recovery and restoration of the characteristic checkerboard cement tiles helps to restore the reading of the continuity and breadth of the distribution spaces.

The restoration of the gym brings to light the coffered ceiling hidden for years by false ceilings; the construction of the mezzanine for the library allows the reading of these details, in a contemporary, and at the same time suggestive, space. In the classrooms, the ceilings are replaced by linear slabs, slightly detached from the side walls, leaving the historical vaults to be perceived; the compromised floors are replaced with new wooden ones, taking up the historical use of the material. The replacement of the safety staircase, determined by the need to serve all floors with coherent escape routes, allows, finally, a reorganization of the external space, not directly usable by users, but privileged

overlooking from classrooms and workplaces, as well as from the roof terrace.

The New Entrance and the Restoration of the Facade on via Duchessa Jolanda

The intervention involved moving the entrance to Duchessa Jolanda street, where an existing window was transformed into a portal that reaches the sidewalk level. The metal frame of the portal takes up the colour and proportions of the frames that mark the other windows on the facade. The door is transparent, with two doors, and is surmounted by a fixed cover.

The Entrance Hall

The demolition of a bay of vaults allowed to create a new ramp to overcome the difference in height between the sidewalk and the mezzanine floor, which intersects laterally with the steps leading to the new atrium. The compass and the flight of stairs which performed the same function have been eliminated, to create instead a large and partition-free environment, in which the structure of the historic building is readable again. On the floor below, where the archives of the 1563 Foundation of the 'Compagnia di San Paolo' are located, the intrados of the ramp are left exposed. The progress of the reinforced concrete ramp constitutes the new ceiling of the gallery, denouncing the intervention. The ramp of the new entrance, the steps and the hall are paved in Luserna stone, while the atrium is paved in bamboo and houses two low volumes, the reception and the toilets, which detach themselves so as not to interfere with the large vaulted room.

The Restoration of the Gym and the New Mezzanine Floor for Library Use

The intervention involved the restoration of a gym room, which could be transformed into a theatre/conference room, in a space that was already present inside the building. Part of the ancient space and the adjacent corridor were occupied for the changing rooms and service areas. In correspondence with these, the great height made it possible to exploit a double level with the insertion of a new mezzanine floor, compartmented by windows. The demolition of the false ceilings freed the historic coffered ceiling.

The Central Stairwell and the Connecting Walkways

Following the intervention, the stairwell becomes again the fulcrum of the building. In fact, the construction of the two external emergency stairs allows to keep it open on the corridors on the different floors, freeing all previously buffered gates and eliminating the REI compartments. The stone steps, the iron parapet and the wooden handrail have been cleaned and restored. The metal walkways, with white painted steel parapet, the intrados in fireproof plasterboard and bamboo flooring, delicately fit into the frame of the staircase, connecting the new levels opened by the project both with the staircase and with the lift tower. In correspondence with the landing of the staircase on the floors, technical blocks have been created which interact by colour with the cement floor and group all the necessary technical and storage functions as separate elements.

Thematic Libraries and the Enhancement of the Glass Window on the Internal Courtyard

The movement of the toilets allowed to enhance the glazed area located on the internal corner between the two sleeves of the building. In this position the thematic reading rooms of the floor have been placed, conceptually connected to the distributed library, around the central stairwell.

The Modification of the Section of the Sleeve Duchessa Jolanda: Second Mezzanine Floor and Roof Terrace

The intervention changes the section of the sleeve facing Via Duchessa Jolanda transforming the pitched roof into a terrace roof. This makes it accessible from the top floor of the school through the central staircase. The attic floor (second mezzanine floor) was half raised, on the internal courtyard, and dedicated to group work, office space and teacher space. The new roof slab was left with the exposed intrados as in the case of the entrance ramp on the archive, this rests on the existing arches creating a game of double levels. The terrace is in yellow sandstone, the facade that emerges on the internal courtyard is covered with stoneware slabs that bind chromatically to the decorations of the facade. The empty parts pick up the rhythm of the underlying ones.

The New External Safety Staircase

In order to serve all the existing floors and the new terrace for fire safety purposes, the intervention provided for the replacement of the external emergency staircase serving the sleeve of via Duchessa Jolanda. It is a metal ramp, surrounded by a full parapet with the effect of a band, which wraps around a central septum in exposed concrete.

The floors

The cement floors in the distribution spaces have been maintained, integrating with new elements where the plant passages are concentrated. The original wooden floor of the gym has been restored, while the decay of the other flooring has unfortunately not allowed their conservation. Therefore, it was decided to replace them with industrial wooden flooring (bamboo), as it was already supposed for the spaces where the floors were not original and in the new escape routes. Instead, PVC was used in different colours in the bathrooms and laboratories. The entrance ramp and the staircase that connects to the atrium is made of Luserna stone, taking up the material of the main stairwell. The roof terrace is covered in yellow gold quartz arenite.

The New Partitions

The new partitions are made of acoustically insulated double sheet plasterboard. These sheets set back from the load-bearing walls which always allows the reading of the arches. Between the classroom and the corridor, the effect is accentuated by the presence of a transparent glass bezel. Three times in a different way, two on the first floor and one on the second floor, movable walls have been inserted to allow the classes to communicate in a large unique environment.

The Suspended Ceilings

In order to mask off-track systems and to improve the acoustic quality, false ceilings have been created in all areas except for the corridors, the sleeve of the first mezzanine floor and the stairwell. There the vaults have been bleached, enhancing them and showing them off. With the exception of the bathrooms and the technical rooms, all the false ceilings are treated like sails that detach themselves from the walls to leave visible the supporting structure and the depth of the vaults above.

The Structures

The assessment of the seismic vulnerability of the building allowed us to identify the weak points where to operate to improve its performance. Therefore, specific consolidation interventions were carried out on some masonry masts of the basement. Threaded bars were inserted, hidden in the mortar between the bricks, while the bricks of the entrance hall were treated with reinforced plaster. The new structures were built with lightened reinforced concrete. The connecting walkways and the new mezzanine floor, on the other hand, were dry-constructed with a steel structure and wooden planks.

The Plants

The new electrical system has been created by limiting the undercut passages and exploiting the new false ceilings, so as not to compromise the load-bearing structure excessively. The bathrooms were mostly located close to the existing ones, in order to optimize drains and vents. As for the heating system, already connected to the district heating network, the heating elements and the distribution uprights have been replaced, following where possible the traces of the existing passages. The mechanical ventilation system, present on the first mezzanine floor only, was built using as much as possible the niches on the load-bearing walls. The supply and return of air were concentrated on the façade of the windows of the floor libraries, which masks the technical room itself.

The Improvement of the Acoustic Quality

In order to improve the reverberation times in the classrooms and in the other rooms of the school, sound absorbing melamine panels have been applied to the walls and ceilings. Acoustic ceilings have been set up, to which a layer of polyester fibre has been combined. In the atrium and in the entrance gallery, there are also sound absorbing panels affixed to the walls like paintings. Inside the music room, the system has been further integrated with the insertion of other wall devices, made of wood and synthetic material, and with the use of axes with double surfaces, reflective on the outside and absorbent to the 'internal, which allow you to adjust a different perception of sound when needed.

The Colours and Furnishings

The building envelope was renovated in neutral tones: white and dark blue were used for the fixed furnishings, which reflect the colours of the checkerboard concrete floor. In this way they integrate more with the walls and do not weigh down the image of the building. The mobile furnishings, on the other hand, are in coloured tones typical of the school function.

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Chapter 2.2.1

An Innovative School Library: The ‘Biblioteca di Alessandro’ (Alessandro’s Library), by Antonia Marino⁸⁵

Abstract

School innovation also passes through school libraries, as laboratories where implement notions, knowledge and transversal skills using new teaching methods, in order to develop key skills for lifelong learning. As it is known, reading represents an indispensable tool for understand reality and oneself, to mature critical thinking and autonomy of judgment, essential elements for a harmonious and integral development of the person. Hence the importance of creating at school a playful and stimulating reading environment, like the school library school can be, which manages to bring children closer to the magical world of reading, arousing in them the pleasure of reading.

Keywords: teaching innovation; reading; learning; school library.

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Introduction

The 'Alessandro's Library', donated to the I.C. Piersanti Mattarella - Plesso Randaccio by Alessandro Cieri's parents and looked after by the teacher librarian Costanza Buttinelli, is characterised by a very accurate selection of texts and picture books from the best publishing houses, small sections of books for children with special needs and popularisation texts.

The activities concerning the 'Alessandro Cieri' Library have as their main aim the education of 'quality reading', a fundamental requirement to bring pupils closer to a love of books. To this end, the Library organises: readings in the library, readings and workshops in continuity between school grades, meetings with authors, exhibitions and training meetings; it is actively involved in initiatives of national resonance such as: 'Scelte di classe', 'Io leggo perché', 'Libriamoci' etc.

Building a Future between the Pages

Such a library, equipped with spaces designed for different reading modes and enriched with books that are true 'shelf art', owns all the requirements to become an ideal school library. To this end, our Institute aims to implement its potential to the fullest by making it a library that is 'open' to users and technologically equipped for our digitally native pupils.

We are convinced, in fact, that literature represents a preferential channel of access to an articulated imagination, an infinite container of stories, essential nourishment for every human being, a powerful accelerator of empathy; it is a means of processing the complexity of the world and relationships, it is the forge of the possible that feeds the imagination.

Promoting reading with children and young people with the aim of forming knowledgeable and passionate readers cannot, therefore, be separated from exposure to literature, i.e. to quality books - books that bring meaning, astonishment and authenticity: they make sense when the story can unfold towards a certain universality and makes the outside converse with the inside; they create astonishment when they are able to overturn expectations; they are authentic when, even if an adult is uncomfortable in them, a young person feels understood.

Our school libraries, therefore, have as their main purpose to give our pupils the opportunity to create 'a future between the pages', initiating children and young people into the pleasure, mirroring and nourishment they can find in books, so that they embrace a practice of meaning that will accompany them throughout their lives.

'Growing as readers' means forming critical individuals, offering food for thought and elaboration that enables children and young people to read beyond the books themselves, promoting the development of active and

creative thinking, all through the use of diversified and 'playful' teaching methodologies.

Knowing by Reading (also Digitally and Online)

The centrality of 'knowing - reading' cannot be separated from the technological innovation of a school library that allows the use and production of both textual and multimedia content. This objective has been achieved through the I.C. Piersanti Mattarella's membership of the school library network whose name seems both a project and a wish (*nomen omen*): B.L.A., acronym of Biblioteche Luoghi Aperti, i.e. Libraries Open Places. The network, whose lead school is the I.C. 'Perlasca' Rome, has as its main purpose that of creating a network of innovative school libraries that cooperate in the dissemination of reading and social sharing practices, with the aim of arousing the daily pleasure of reading, including through digital technology, and to stimulate and encourage greater social cohesion, creating close and shared collaborations both with families and with all the realities present in the area.

The activities that aim at achieving these objectives will be implemented by developing the library services along three lines of action:

- a) full and facilitated access to library material, both in print and digital form;
- b) training activities and workshops designed and structured for different age groups;
- c) events and reading festivals for children and young people open to the territory, to involve not only children, but also their families, as a fundamental element to support and develop the pleasure of reading in children.

In addition, in order to be recognisable, the network will be characterised not only by the presence of a common digital space (<https://blabibliotecheluoghiaperti.wordpress.com/>), but also by a recognisable physical space in each participating institute set up with the same tools (tablet or computer) and furnishing elements (notice board to advertise activities and events and reader's chair) '1.

Thanks to the network agreements, our teaching staff had the opportunity to train in the following areas

1. federated cataloguing through the ClavisNG automated library system;

2. training and management of innovative school libraries;
3. promotion of reading at school.

The network project has also enabled us to enrich our 'physical' libraries with access to MLOL [Media Library On Line] Scuola, a portal providing students, teachers and families with the digital lending services. MLOL has enriched the offer of our libraries with:

- a) digital library lending of e-books (2 per month, lasting 14 days) from a catalogue of over 60,000 titles and audio-books (unlimited access),

and access to:

- b) an international newsstand with over 5,000 multilingual newspapers and periodicals;
- c) music resources (Spotify);
- d) collections of free content;
- e) useful content for learners with Specific Learning Disorders.

Final Remarks

In this way, Alessandro's Library is characterised as an innovative school library, where the written text and picture books are the prerequisite for the use of reading also through digital means.

Websites

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<https://www.istitutocomprensivopiersantimattarella.edu.it/>

IC Mattarella – Plesso Randaccio

<https://www.istitutocomprensivopiersantimattarella.edu.it/luogo/scuola-primaria-giovanni-randaccio/>

The Alessandro Cieri Library, a Poetically Innovative Space,⁸⁶ by Costanza Buttinelli⁸⁷

Abstract

The 'Cieri' Library was conceived in 2018 within the 'Randaccio' Primary School, part of the Istituto Comprensivo 'Piersanti Mattarella' in Rome, to honour the memory of Alessandro, the son of Luca Cieri and Daniella Picarelli. The parents aimed to create a beautiful and innovative library, realized by commissioning Architect Gianluca Ficorilli. Ficorilli, in collaboration with the teacher-librarian (who has been active in reading education and promotion at the same school since 2007), designed an integrated architectural and cultural project that combines diverse but complementary perspectives.

The library is organised into centres of interest, offering users access to films, books, live readings, augmented reading tools, and exhibitions. Great care was taken in selecting the book holdings, guided by rigorous quality standards. The selection emphasises overall editorial quality, including format, texts, illustrations, authorial qualities, and the complexity and intensity of contents, along with their usage possibilities. Additionally, the collection includes texts that are essential to the history of children's literature and publishing in Italy, as well as those designed for alternative augmented reading.

It is well known that the presence of an active school library enhances the quality of a school's curriculum.

Keywords: school library; Biblioteca 'Alessandro Cieri'; children's literature; high-quality books; innovative library spaces.

⁸⁶ Translation by Antonio Lenzo.

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Introduction

The ‘Alessandro Cieri’ Library, founded in 2018 following a tragic event, is a very special library: the love it contains and with which it resonates can be perceived as soon as one enters it, and all children can feel it anytime they walk past the great glass-wall marking the passage from the school hallway to the library’s entrance.

Alessandro Cieri was a pupil at ‘G. Randaccio’ School when, in the first grade, he fell ill. With an extraordinary strength of character, he endured the three years of his illness. He was a child of great value, brilliant and intelligent, affectionate, generous; he enjoyed school, he loved his schoolmates, who dearly loved him back; he especially loved the library. When Alessandro left the world, his parents, Daniella Picarelli and Luca Cieri, decided to support library renovations for his former school community; in particular, Luca Cieri decided to commission such a significant project to Architect Gianluca Ficorilli (who curated the project and its realization). The Cieri family and Alessandro’s paternal grandmother also ensured the new library would bear the child’s name.⁸⁸

Dedicating a school library to a child who left the world, in the school he attended, is not only a formal act, but it represents an actual mandate, for those inhabiting the library, to keep the memory of that child ever living, through the very existence of that space, which thus becomes a sort of everlasting Eden, forever a child, alive through the life and games and stories that run through the life of the living, luckier than him. A library that is born with this mission forcefully states that keeping memory alive is an essential aspect of its mission and of its nature. After all, is memory not a fundamental aspect of the identities of each of us, as individuals and as a community?

Along with this mission, a school library’s aims also include reading education, the broadening of school curricula and, as any educational institution would state, the aggregation of a school community, in response to the growing needs of impoverished areas.

The *Avviso pubblico per la realizzazione da parte delle istituzioni scolastiche ed educative statali di biblioteche scolastiche innovative* (PNSD, Azione#24), an open call for school library implementation, signed by MIUR Director General Simona Montesarchio, reads:

⁸⁸ For further information on Alessandro’s character and on the genesis of the library that bears his name, see also Buttinelli (2020).

Uno spazio accogliente, vivace, luminoso, colorato, organizzato in modo accessibile e confortevole, adatto ad attività differenti per utenti piccoli e grandi, famiglie e studenti, per l'intera comunità scolastica., i.e.

A welcoming space, lively, well-lighted, colourful, organized in a comfortable and accessible manner, fit for different activities for younger and older users, families and students, and the entire school community. (The English Translation is ours.)

Such a declaration leaves no room for doubt: the school library cannot only be the place for books, but it becomes a place to absolve different, new and complex functions.

The Roman neighbourhood of Casalbertone, where the school is located, has few meeting places, a scarcity of cultural activities, though it is characterized by ethnical and sociocultural plurality. Near the recently renewed Tiburtina station, it is undergoing a process of gentrification which, in turn, does not present the area with either services or adequate maintenance of what is already there. In this situation, the school's role is of crucial significance, as it is the first and sometimes the only social, cultural, intercultural hotspot for children and their families.

In recent years the educating community is bearing increased attention to educational poverty or, rather, to educational *poverties*, prompted by contemporary issues as also reported by studies and research. As is known, the humanitarian association 'Save the Children', published *Il tempo dei bambini: atlante dell'infanzia a rischio 2019*, edited by Giulio Cederna and ten years after the first edition, which won the Andersen Prize in May 2019. This excellent work classifies the different poverties as economical, urbanistic, institutional, sociocultural and, finally, relational. Carla Ida Salviati, in her article *Miseria senza nobiltà*, published in the «Andersen» magazine, monographic issue 364, July-August 2019, depicts how complex the problem is as to require varied and advanced intervention tools: actions and interactions especially targeted and diversified; probing and unprejudiced analyses; constant dialogue and shared intents.

In this scenario, a school library appears as an extremely powerful instrument to reach an area that is deprived under several aspects, as well as its inhabitants, children and adults, without hiding the complex issues that this consideration implies.

In the first place, the library of the 'Randaccio' school complex was of the sort that is typical of many Italian schools: shelves stuffed with dusty old books (the latest acquisitions dated from 40 or 50 years prior), even those inaccessible because covered in plastic sheets; the lending register recorded almost no activity and teachers were witnesses that previous librarians had not promoted initiatives or improving interventions of any kind. However, over the last decade, a systematic effort has been aimed at reading education, following the hiring of the current teacher-librarian, who has been working full-time in this context since 2007.

The adopted methodology involves weekly reading aloud sessions, in the library space, with class groups. Since children between the ages of six and ten are involved, great attention is devoted to the relational aspects encouraged by this activity: the book acts as a link between the reading adult and the listening child, and between the children themselves. Over time, it has been recorded how, for all children at the school, going to the library to listen to the reading constitutes not just a routine school activity, but a proper event, highly anticipated and dense with emotional implications. One of the most surprising outcomes was that the children would ask to borrow even the older, dusty volumes in the library, demonstrating a strong dedication to the experience undergone in that space. So, as much in the past as in the present, for a child reading is more intense and grounded if channelled by a mediating figure.

Yet, how to mediate? How does one present the book and, even more so, the experience of encounter with storytelling?

Imagining and Designing a Vibrant Space

It is by attentively recollecting our own childhood, by keeping it in mind, if not always happily, that we as educators are able to situate ourselves against that of the children we are entrusted with, in a position of fair distance, taking on both the responsibility of our roles and a sense of respect for their difference, their different perception of reality, their inalienable alterity, seeking, in us, authority (not authoritarianism), power (not arrogance), attention (not overindulging). If the adult sincerely expresses their passions, children are easily inspired.

Seriously interrogating ourselves on this subject as educators leads us to project spaces with an eye to the actual use they, not us, may make

of them. A linoleum floor, on which children might read while lying down, demands we envision the reading encounter in a different way than if we sat around a table with the children. All of this asks of us not only a change of posture, but a change of perspective too. Using a video projector and a screen with Internet access allows us, for example, to work with the text in a PDF format and with the physical book at the same time, or to use augmented reading or a reading application, so as to transform a traditional reading encounter through the many virtual windows that correspond to as many languages, so familiar to generations of digital natives. The shift in perspective also leads us to accept that, more often with *silent books* than when working on divulgation, children might take our hand and lead us down unexpected avenues.

We cannot avoid this challenge, if we really want to be witnesses to what it means to read, because culture is this, also: discovering other perspectives, other ways of telling stories. Digital technologies at Alessandro's library are a valid and fundamental support for any learning activity and they offer the possibility to integrate traditional methods with innovative ones. Nonetheless, the essential task for the educating adult cannot be delegated to these means: leading children to individuate instruments and methodologies to showcase the knowledge of which they are bearers and to build autonomously the skills they will develop.

The work of Architect Ficorilli was decisive in giving order and concreteness to the imagined environment and to its functions, realizing a space full of meanings, which stimulates paths and activates connections: because of this, it is fair to emphasize how forward-thinking Luca Cieri was. A way of thinking forward which was concrete and recognizable in the use of as sophisticated a space as that which was made a reality. Sophisticated more invisibly than in a visible sense, more so for its immaterial contents than for the material ones.

The Book Collection

Now it seems important to direct our attention to the selected books, as they represent a fundamental aspect of the library's beauty. The soul of this place is in these books; it would not be here if Alessandro had not been a child attentive to the beauty of words and images. This beauty is less flashy than that of the space created to showcase it, but

in the usage that can be made of it lies the most important, most lasting and fertile legacy.

From the previous library, only a few adequate items in good condition were transferred to the new:

- Children's literature classics
- Popular photographic encyclopedias of recent publication
- Illustrated albums
- Fables
- Dictionary

Really, just a few tens of books.

The Feature of the «Fondo Cieri»: Quality Books

The books of the Cieri's donation constitute a group of their own, as they were immediately stamped with the 'Fondo Cieri' [Cieri Fond] stamp when they were delivered to the school.

Since the greatest investment was made towards masonry and furniture, the number of books selected for the library was relatively small.

As expressly requested by Alessandro's mother, a shelf was devoted specifically to visual communication books, for children with autism spectrum- and dyslexia-related issues; another shelf, for children of ages ranging 11 to 13, to allow Alessandro's classmates to continue attending the library once they had continued into the neighbour secondary school, as well as all students of the same, of course.

Texts devoted to divulgation (artistic, naturalistic, geographic, etc.) were acquired from those editors stocking whole collections devoted to the same and who, at the same time, devote rigorous attention to editorial quality. Quality (of contents, style, and editorial) is a fundamental feature of the bibliographic collection of the 'Fondo Cieri' and it was the aspect that characterized the entire work of selection. The selection was guided by rigorous standards of quality, with an emphasis on overall editorial quality standards, as may be recognized in editorial format, in texts and/or illustrations, in authorial qualities, in the complexity and intensity of contents, in the usage possibilities. Such a selection also considered the acquisition of texts bearing essential witness to the history of children's literature and publishing in Italy, and texts designed for alternative augmented reading. It should be considered that, in setting up and developing a collection, be it for a

school library or a young adults' library, quality is not an accessory or a caprice, nor a useless luxury, but a necessary prerequisite for the children's growth. The most important for reading education. In particular, when discussing editorial quality, what is meant is a care of the book in all of its aspects: the paper, the typography, the suppleness of the cover and of the binding, the format chosen in relation to the theme, the beauty and style of the illustrations and the way in which they interact with the text, the precision of the language of both, the richness of sense and complexity, the polysemy, the rhythm, time and structure of the story, the variety of its languages, points of view, the possibility of building reading paths between different books in a library with a commitment to avoiding gender stereotypes and biased histories on themes and events.

Several books from favourite authors were acquired, so as to enable work on authorial poetics. Books that deal with difficult themes, too. Books with a significant cultural background, demanding further engagement of the mediating adult, knowledge, attentive inquiry, thought, so as to be used to the best of their possibilities, so as to find in them one's own voice in the moment when they are read out to children. A broad section was devoted to fables, with the assurance that, to say it in Italo Calvino's words (1956: p. XX), that:

«(...) le fiabe sono vere. Sono, prese tutte insieme, nella loro sempre ripetuta e sempre varia casistica di vicende umane, una spiegazione generale della vita», i.e., in our translation:

«(...) tales are true. They are, taken all together, in their always repeated and always varied casuistry of human deeds, a general explanation of life.»

Equally represented were *silent books*, essential tools for visual literacy education in today's diverse world. They play a crucial role in overcoming language barriers and fostering connections with children from various linguistic backgrounds. Poetry also held a significant place, encompassing rhymes, nursery rhymes, and verse for all by renowned poets such as Piumini, Tognolini, Carminati, Vecchini, and others. We deemed it important to include books that have left a lasting mark on children's literature in Italy and beyond, such as those by Iela Mari, Leo Lionni, Bruno Munari, Emanuele Luzzati, Astrid Lindgren, Roald Dahl, and Maurice Sendak, among many others.

Final Remarks

One of the reasons why a school library should prioritize not only its physical space but also the quality of its book collection is its mission to cultivate and enhance a culture of children's literature among educators, as practiced in countries that place greater emphasis on this essential aspect of education. It is widely acknowledged that an active school library enhances the overall quality of a school's curriculum and educational outcomes, which are further bolstered by practices such as reading aloud and shared reading.

La correlazione tra la qualità dei servizi bibliotecari scolastici e il successo formativo è costantemente testimoniata da ricerche e studi basati su evidenze (che qui non è possibile presentare dettagliatamente), alcuni accessibili nella sezione 'School Library Impact Studies' del Library Research Service (LRS) del Colorado o in 'School Libraries Make a Difference' nel sito web della IASL. (Marquardt, 2014: 307)., i.e.

The correlation between the quality of school library services and formative success is consistently supported by research and evidence-based studies (which cannot be fully detailed here). Some of these studies can be accessed in the 'School Library Impact Studies' section of the Colorado Library Research Service (LRS) or in 'School Libraries Make a Difference' on the IASL website. (Marquardt, 2014: 307).

A heightened appreciation for libraries and children's literature empowers teachers to see themselves as creators of ideas, not merely as developers of the basic skills often limited by governmental policies. They are adults entrusted with nurturing young minds during their most flexible and receptive years, when intelligence is at its peak potential. This immense responsibility deserves serious consideration, as childhood is fleeting and precious.

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**‘Giovanni Randaccio’ Primary School, Rome:
The ‘Alessandro Cieri’ School Library,⁸⁹ by
Gianluca Ficorilli⁹⁰**

Abstract

The project for the 'Alessandro Cieri' Library is part of the 'Giovanni Randaccio' Public Primary School in Rome. The new library was created by repurposing three previously unused spaces: one was the end part of a corridor leading to the classrooms, and the other two were former classrooms, very similar to each other. The project's concept is to treat these three spaces as a single, homogeneous environment while preserving the individuality and autonomy of each area.

Initially, this appeared to be a challenge, but it was ultimately embraced as a positive aspect. The different design choices were made with the aim of resolving what initially seemed like a contradiction. The three rooms are unified by the treatment of the side walls and ceilings. Each part of the library is designed as a flexible tool, allowing children to experience the library in various ways.

This contribution describes the main features and uses (traditional, theatrical, and immersive) of each room. Multi-functionality (e.g., seats that allow playing Tetris; surfaces that can transform into display stands) and flexibility are key features of the project, allowing the space to be rearranged as needed.

Keywords: ‘Alessandro Cieri’ School Library; innovative library spaces; school library; design; colour; light; theatre.

⁸⁹ Translation by Luisa Marquardt.

⁹⁰ Architect, Designer of ‘Alessandro Cieri’ School Library.

Introduction

The project for the 'Alessandro Cieri' Library was developed within the rooms made available at the 'Giovanni Randaccio' Public Primary School, a branch of the 'Piersanti Mattarella' Comprehensive School in Rome. The new library occupies three areas: the first was the end section of a corridor leading to the classrooms, while the other two were formerly classrooms, very similar to each other. The project aims to treat the three spaces as a unified, homogeneous environment while preserving the individuality and autonomy of each area. Initially, this posed a challenge, but it was ultimately embraced as a positive feature. The various design choices were made to address and integrate what initially seemed like a contradiction.

The Project

Figure 1. First Area: Reception and Reading (Photo by Archt. G. Ficorilli).

The three areas are standardized by the treatment of the side walls and ceilings: the colour shapes and define the external perimeter of the library, while the inner area walls are treated with neutral colours and materials, underlining the separation of the rooms. Each part of the library is designed as a flexible tool, which allows children to experience the library through different possibilities of use.

In the first space (Fig. 1), large suspended spheres of light measure the volume, meanwhile tables and chairs suggest a traditional and composed use of the space. Furthermore, a work by Felice Limosani makes

good use of neon tubes to draw a thought that seems to be born in a child's mind.

Figure 2. Theatrical area for performances and meetings (Photo by Archt. G. Ficorilli).

The second area (Fig. 2) is designed as a potential theatrical space, with steep steps that can be used for movement or seating, as in the case of projections. In this area, a small, separate space near the windows is carved out to provide a more intimate and secluded reading environment, benefitting from natural light.

Figure 3. Immersive environment 'between trees and starry night' (Photo by Archt. G. Ficorilli).

The third area is defined by a plaster dome, evoking a sky full of stars that is mirrored on the floor with a photograph of the sky seen through branches from below, further suggesting the idea of storytelling and listening gathered around a tree.

The library users are elementary school children, so their size dictated the project's dimensions and furnishings. The height of the bookcases allows children to access all the displayed books. The chairs can be overturned and turned into stools, providing a less conventional way to sit. The circular seat under the dome also serves as a book container, allowing young visitors to lay down on the floor to read and, through their imagination, lose themselves, suspended among the branches of the trees.

Another interesting aspect was the ability to transform and adapt spaces and furnishings, revealing hidden meanings visible through children's use. The seats double as bases for playing Tetris; the bookcases become chalkboards; the footboards in the first room conceal a circular path connecting the entrance to the small ramp near the windows. In the third room, the ability to switch on or shield the lights accommodates the rapid alternation of day and night in the dome.

Lastly, a requirement from the beginning by Librarian Costanza Buttinelli was the ability to host exhibitions. To achieve this, we treated the back of the bookcases as neutral backgrounds, and the displays, as mobile furniture, can be moved among the three areas to design the exhibition layout.

Figure 4. Porthole in the wall between the second and third rooms.
(Photo by Archt. G. Ficorilli).

Chapter 2.3.1

School Library, Teaching and Reading: Exploitation Strategies from the Experience of ‘Francesco Vivona’ Grammar School in Rome,⁹¹

by Daniela Benincasa⁹²

Abstract

The Headmistress of the ‘Francesco Vivona’ Grammar School in Rome explains what strategies a School Principal can put in place for the construction or the enhancement of the School Library, serving both the school community, teaching and learning activities etc., and the territory, the local community. The experience of the ‘Francesco Vivona’ Grammar School is presented here: from the creation and motivation of the work team - training and enhancing the various professional skills - to identifying the Library as the fulcrum of the School Improvement Plan (PDM) and the shared definition of the vertical curriculum on the Net; from the involvement in the network of local authorities and institutions - Bibliopoint - to the functional redefinition of spaces and the optimization of resources with a view to teaching, promoting reading and the territory.

Keywords: school library; exploitation; school improvement plan; collaboration; BiblioPoint.

⁹¹ Translation by Luisa Marquardt.

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Introduction

The 'Francesco Vivona' Grammar School boasts a strong tradition not only in the teaching of classical languages but also in scientific disciplines. Over the years, many alumni have excelled in various professions, achieving prominent positions in the legal, medical, and scientific fields. Notably, mathematician Alessio Figalli, a Fields Medal⁹³ recipient in 2018, is among them. Today, while maintaining its rigorous academic profile, the school has embraced several innovative projects, including mathematical and scientific enhancement, language skills development (through the CAIE Language Project and CAIE sections with the teaching of Latin, Geography, Biology, and Chemistry), and internationalisation, which has led to exchanges with partner countries in Europe and beyond.

Upon my arrival at the 'F. Vivona' Grammar School in 2013, I discovered a splendid library, rich with prestigious books, but unfortunately underutilised. It was confined to spaces that did not support its use for teaching, learning, or promoting reading within the school community and the broader territory. Since then, we have implemented targeted strategies to enhance the library. The School Library is now a 'Bibliopoint' and serves as the centre for various cultural and educational activities.

The recently established reading corners, which transcend the usual spatial and functional limits, represent the culmination of this process and the beginning of further innovative paths.

The Work Team: Identification of Professional Resources, Training, and Organizational Lines

The process began with the formation of a working group consisting of teachers representing all subjects (from both the lower and upper secondary levels) and the two teachers appointed to the library. Identifying and selecting available professional resources, particularly those who are truly motivated to undertake professional development, represents a very delicate phase. In the case of the 'Vivona' High School, this process was facilitated by the determination and interest immediately shown towards the project. This was set against a backdrop of a highly qualified professional dimension tied to a 'traditional' approach to teaching, yet open to activating paths that

⁹³ International Medal for Outstanding Discoveries in Mathematics. (TN)

promote classical and scientific culture through a deeper understanding of the available informational resources, which needed to be known, organised, and made accessible. Additionally, there was a need to initiate a more effective entry orientation policy to counteract the decline in enrolments for the classical studies track in grammar schools that had been occurring nationwide for several years.

After surveying the existing resources (catalogue, types, and arrangement of collections), a synergistic 'networking' approach was adopted to promote collaboration with institutions through an agreement for targeted training activities with Roma Tre University, particularly with its Department of Education and the Chair of Library and Information Science.

The collections were then updated by removing obsolete and barely usable materials. At the same time, the library spaces, increasingly conceived as 'learning environments,' were renovated with the purchase of new bibliographic materials, furniture, and equipment through a careful study to optimise the existing spaces. In parallel, the working group organised and regulated all activities.

The Construction of the Library as a Complex Reality: The School Improvement Plan and the *Liber@Biblioteca* Project

The starting point for institutional network relationships, with Vivona playing a leading role in the BiblioRoma Network, was the implementation of the biennial 'Liber@Biblioteca' Improvement Plan during the 2014/15 and 2015/16 academic years. This plan included:

- Planning didactic activities to define a vertical continuity curriculum between the final classes of the 1st-grade secondary school and the 1st and 2nd year classes of the 2nd-grade secondary school.
- Cooperative creation of didactic units to be tested with students from different classes, aiming to improve their text comprehension and logical/mathematical skills.
- Training for teachers through professional development workshops led by experts in instructional design, pedagogy and evaluation, expressive reading, use of e-learning platforms, and library science.

The Construction of the Library as a Complex Reality: Institutional Collaboration Networks and the Territory

Meanwhile, contacts with various agencies were established:

- MIUR - MiBACT Interministerial Commission and Libraries 21 Project Commission
- Roma Tre University, Department of Education, Library and Information Science

Different Memoranda of Understanding were signed with:

- ‘Biblioteche di Roma’ for the establishment of the ‘Vivona’ Bibliopoint
- The ‘Lazio’ Libraries Network (formerly ‘Bibliorete Ostia’)
- Appia Antica Regional Park and IPSEOA Tor Carbone - Ancient Modernity Protocol for ASL [i.e. Alternanza Scuola-Lavoro] dual training routes.

Optimization of Resources and Functionality of Spaces

Over the years, the ‘F. Vivona’ Grammar School Board has supported the investments necessary to transform the former library into a multifunctional space for cultural activities and reading promotion. Meanwhile, the school has been equipped with IT resources (enhancing scientific and language laboratories, with interactive whiteboards in every classroom) and increasingly powerful and effective connectivity to support various activities.

The book collection is housed from the ground floor to the second floor. The designed reading corners highlight and enhance the common spaces at the entrance and on the different floors. We are also awaiting the completion of the Aula Magna's restoration, which will be improved and equipped with modular furniture, soundproof reading areas, and common work areas.

The Library in Teaching and Planning: From Reading Promotion to Paths for Cross-Orientation Skills

Numerous cultural activities focused on the promotion of reading, conferences, seminars and training activities, and concerts have been organized in collaboration with the ‘F. Chopin’ Association, directed by the internationally renowned M.^o Marcella Crudeli. Other events include film forums and appearances by prominent figures from the world of culture and entertainment.

The contribution of the students who have been working on online cataloguing and implementing the OPAC over the years is fundamental. This has been made possible by an important agreement between the 'F. Vivona' Grammar School and Roma Tre University, enabling the 'School and Work Alternation' program, now known as 'Paths for Transversal Orientation Skills.'

Final Remarks

Targeted management synergies, training, and the development of specific and motivated professional resources, along with the optimization of resources, have made it possible to build the 'F. Vivona' Grammar School library over time. This library is still in the process of expansion and improvement.

This serves as proof that energy invested with perseverance, systematic efforts, and shared purposes and methods towards common objectives can produce tangible, functional, and rewarding results, even in complex contexts.

'The founding of libraries was like constructing more public granaries, amassing reserves against a spiritual winter which by certain signs, in spite of myself, I see ahead...' (from *Memoirs of Hadrian* by M. Yourcenar).

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I would like to thank Prof. Luisa Marquardt, Architect Serena Rubino, Profs. Emanuela Sangalli and Graziella Maltese, the Liber@biblioteca Project Working Group, the Deputy Team, the Administrative Director Ms. Liliana Loru, and the School Governing Boards—the Teaching Board and the School Board of the 'Vivona' High School—who have been involved over time, for sharing with me and contributing to the creation of a wide-ranging project to serve students and their learning, with the hope that it can help them become aware and autonomous in their choices, and responsible citizens.

Websites

Biblioteche di Roma, www.bibliotechediroma.it

Liceo Francesco Vivona, www.liceovivona.edu.it

A Distributed Library to Promote Reading at School: a Challenge for the ‘Vivona’ Grammar School in Rome, by Emanuela Sangalli⁹⁴

Abstract

This contribution explains the reasons why, years ago, ‘Liceo Vivona’ decided to plan new reading spaces and develop expanded reading corners on each floor of the building to integrate teaching and reading in all forms. The project started in 2015 and has since involved a mixed team working in various areas such as cataloguing, book enhancement, and redesigning school spaces, particularly the halls and the main lecture hall. The theoretical premise emphasizes the users’ central role and their need for information, literacy, and socialization. The complex library system, in its central elements (professionals, spaces, and collections), aims to fulfil these needs by focusing on efficient promotional actions, starting with reshaping library spaces to make them more spread out and attractive.

In the 2014-15 and 2015-16 academic years, two empirical studies investigated ‘Liceo Vivona’ Library users’ behaviours, needs, and expectations. The results of this fieldwork served as guidelines for subsequent activities and as a basis for identifying unused and anonymous spaces, which were then reconfigured to enlarge access to all forms of information the school offers, such as MLOL, which allows digital lending. The enhancement of reading spaces—usually given more attention in lower grades—should also be promoted in secondary schools to foster the impulse to read, especially during adolescence when students tend to lose interest in this activity.

Keywords: distributed library; reading corners; regenerative environment; school library; teenagers.

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Introduction

I am not a librarian myself. I am a teacher of Italian Literature who believes, both privately and professionally, that direct contact with books (despite their form, print or digital) is the key for a true and personal culture and education. Therefore, since the beginning of my teaching career, I have been dealing with the school library in the schools where I have taught, because, as it was usual 30 years ago in Italy, there was not any professional in charge of the library. For 30 years I lived and worked in different parts of Italy, from North to the Centre, and therefore I could also experience different attitudes towards the school library. Currently, I have been teaching for 8 years at the ‘Vivona’ Grammar School, a ‘Liceo Classico’ (i.e., a secondary high school whose main subjects are Latin, Greek and, in general, Humanities) in Rome. It was here that I met Daniela Benincasa, a principal, who shares my passion for books and believes in the school library as the key for education. Another important factor is the presence of a professional, Silvia Locatelli: a librarian who can follow the needs of all the library’s users. Furthermore, Vivona Library has got more than 15.000 books, a rich collection built from the 60ies. This is the essential starting point to enhance the library’s collections and to promote reading through new useful spaces and not limited to one place, but present in different areas of the school building.

Two Meanings of the Word ‘Space’

The problem of the ‘space’ for a school library is not only a physical one - the library place, its decoration, furniture and colours -, but also a mental and a didactic one. I think the second one is the most difficult to put into practice in a school like ‘Vivona’ where a strong emphasis is placed on the students’ knowledge and on their academic results: our teaching subjects and method aim to give a thorough vision of the past which makes the students able to analyse and direct themselves in their present reality but with a look to the past roots.

Then I will start from my second point – the didactic space of a school library in Italy. In order to understand the environment where Vivona’s school teachers work, I think that making a comparison between two data is useful. The results of Italian students’ reading literacy in the 2018 PISA tests were quite worrying: 15-year-olds in Italy scored 476 points compared to an average of 487 points in OECD (Organization for

Economic Co-operation and Development) Countries. The most problematic area for Italian students was reading comprehension. In particular, only one in 20 Italian 15-year-olds is able to distinguish fact from opinion when reading a text on an unfamiliar topic and one in four has difficulty with basic reading comprehension, failing to identify the main idea within a medium-length text. Things have worsened in the last decade, as our country has dropped ten points when it comes to reading skills since 2009.

Nevertheless, I must say that the 'Vivona' Grammar School students look motivated when it comes to reading. I will show in detail the results of a survey thesis carried out by two university students, Federica Damico and Giulia Di Pietrantonio, in 2015 and 2016, but for the time being I must share the encouraging data they discovered: 84% of our students like reading and the average books read by them is 14 per year. This does not deny the PISA results, but it shows that there are various elements which must be taken into account.

These encouraging facts can be used to enhance and disseminate the interest in reading and overcome problems in reading comprehension. I also would like to point out that new practices can develop students' skills even more than what is the already encouraging starting point.

The Library in Our Teaching Method

Our teaching method is a sort of triumvirate formed by the teacher, the students and the book. Our books are usually thick volumes organized in the form of a comprehensive presentation of the subject where both teachers and students can find all the material needed to study. Now they are usually combined with internet material already set. Lessons can be frontal or interactive, but the activities of the students are mainly limited to replies to the impulses the teacher gives. Inside this pedagogical context, it is difficult to find a place for the library as a source of the active function of the student.

The 'Vivona' Grammar School teachers had fruitful and strong inputs to change these preconditions by Luisa Marquardt, professor of Library and Information Science at Roma Tre University. She led our project both through setting up a library advisory team and teaching in a refresher course at Liceo Vivona in 2016 (L. Cl. Vivona, 2015). Luisa Marquardt pointed out the idea of the school library as a part of a new environment and of learning commons. In this context, through books and new technology, the library can help build a new learning activity 'in a participatory way and it gives students and teachers the chance to

overcome the class borders' (Marquardt 2013 in Vivarelli, Ed.: 299-304). In this perspective, the school opens up to new sources of information and gives the students not only the technological means, but also the skills to orient themselves in a culture, characterized by new flows of information.

In our school, the teaching activity has got as a support a school library with more than 15.000 volumes and a digital lending platform whose potential I will show later. We have then the basis to work in accordance with the goals of a school library as in the IFLA Manifesto, particularly:

- supporting and enhancing educational goals as outlined in the school's mission and curriculum;
- offering opportunities for experiences in creating and using information for knowledge, understanding, imagination and enjoyment.

To develop these skills teachers must know that students live in a new ecosystem, ruled by digital web and dramatically different from the past⁹⁵. The complexity that young people face is not only textual but also the one produced by a constant, fragmented and diversified information flow which uses different communication codes.

Then, the IFLA Guidelines become considerably more relevant since they underline the importance of the school library as a place which operates as a:

- digital space in a school that is open and accessible to all;
- technological space providing a diverse range of technology tools, software, and expertise for the creation, representation, and sharing of knowledge;
- information environment for all in the community through equitable access to resources, technology, and information skills development that are not always available in homes.
- If the school library offers all sorts of information sources (books and other types of media), it also discloses the problem of information literacy.

⁹⁵ On this aspect it is interesting what we can read in Roncaglia G. (2018). *L'età della frammentazione: cultura del libro e scuola digitale*, Roma-Bari: Laterza and, in particular, Chapt. 6 (p. 35 e 39), where the author criticizes the term 'digital native': the pupils in our schools are not anthropologically different from the past, but they live in a different «environment, a new communicative ecosystem..., dramatically different from the past and ruled by the digital web» (cf. p. 40).

In Italy, we are trying to narrow the gap with other countries as far as school library and information literacy are concerned. A considerable effort has been made in the last few years, especially with the Law no. 851/2015 which provides the guidelines of the National Digital School Plan (Piano Nazionale Scuola Digitale- PNSD) and the ‘Azione #24’ (Roncaglia, 2018: chap. 24, 158-166). This plan stresses the importance of information and digital literacy, the need to shift from a primarily passive transmission method to an active one, and the significance of the school library. In particular, the Action#24 aims to promote the school library as an environment to develop reading and comprehension skills using both traditional and digital sources and also digital lending. Even if at the end the economic investment was not proportional to the needs, it has been a first step. In the meantime, there is a lot of effort on 2.0 classes, which are open to new sources of technological information and to different forms of a participatory culture and to ‘flipped’ classroom methodology. Regarding the flipped classroom, Roncaglia (ibid, Chap. 13: 72-73) invites the teacher to be cautious in using teaching methods that should include a unitary context in order not to fragment information.

The Vivona Library Physical Space: from the Library as a Jar to the Library as a Learning Environment

The starting point

In this theoretical framework, 6 years ago we started our work in order to give a new shape to Vivona’s library, which was established in the 60ies at the same time as the school itself and did not have functional and modern furniture, moreover the accessibility was far from meeting teachers’ and students’ requirements. Students especially need technological instruments and an attractive and flexible environment as a new stimulus to help achieve cultural and educational growth. The transformation and enhancement of the space started from acquiring data from the school community about its habits and dispositions towards reading and its expectations, from public libraries and their school library in order to develop a project involving different directions and aiming to create

‘a library advisory team where representatives of the different groups of the school community are involved so that they can identify different needs in order to prepare a library service

widely shared and responding to all expectations' (Marquardt, 2013, in Vivarelli, Ed: 315. English translation by the author.)

During 2014, with the great help of Luisa Marquardt, a library advisory team was set up: teachers of different subjects worked together to find a common direction.

A partnership between the school and the Department of Education of Roma Tre was formally established; the agreement implied the involvement of two university students, the above mentioned Federica Damico and Giulia Di Pietrantonio, who carried out, in the academic year 2015-16⁹⁶ as a training and degree thesis, a research which had Vivona Library as its core study. This field work identified problems in the organization of space and in the lack of technological instruments: the library came out to be an uncomfortable and unfriendly space, because of the lack of organization and appropriate furniture; its organization was not connected with the school curriculum and the local community; its collections (16.000 books) were registered, but not catalogued, neither classified, nor updated, and resonated only in part with its users.

Planning the Change

Besides looking for data about users' needs (such as students, teachers, but also parents and other school employees), we also wanted to involve students themselves in the project so that they could feel the library is more than just a part of their school life. The Law 107/2015 (the so called 'Buona Scuola') helped us introducing work placement (formerly 'ASL - Alternanza Scuola Lavoro', currently 'PCTO - Percorsi per le Competenze Trasversali e l'Orientamento, Path for Transversal Skills and Orientation). The partnership with the Department of Education of Roma Tre enabled the school to offer a course on cataloguing addressed to the Library Team and the students. The operations of cataloguing and classifying the book collection (and implementing the OPAC, as well) started under the supervision of experts. This work was shared on the 20th of March 2017, during the

⁹⁶ The Damico's and Di Pietrantonio's field works results were reported in the paper 'The school library is mine, too! A participatory approach involving students to rethink their library in a grammar high school in Rome', by Luisa Marquardt on the 23th august 2016, at Meij University in Tokyo, during the 45th International IASL Conference 'A School Library Built for the Digital Age!' (45th Annual International IASL Conference, 20th International Forum on Research in School Librarianship, <http://iasl2016.info/>).

event 'Roma che legge' (i.e., Rome that Reads'), through a speech – 'Reading promoted by the school library' - with the aim of spreading good practices.

As mentioned, in resetting our school library space in order to reshape it as a new learning environment, the above-mentioned field work carried out by Damico & Di Pietrantonio was very important. It was based on Lewin's method and organized through 4 phases:

Planning: How to improve the school library to fulfil teachers' and students' needs?

First Action Step: add value to collections, creating an OPAC, reorganize the spaces open the library to the local community

Observation: conduct a survey to identify teachers' and students' ideal school library.

Evaluation: Did the results match expectations?

It would obviously be too long to mention all of Damico's and Di Pietrantonio's complex and remarkable work, but I at least need to refer their conclusions.

Students and teachers in 2015 noticed that the school library was too old fashioned and disorganized. The school library was there, but did not offer the services of a modern and efficient structure. As from the case study:

- there were two paper catalogues in a poor condition and not complete;
- the classification system did not help the users in finding the books on the shelves;
- there were shelves for the books, but no tables or desks for reading;
- neither computers nor other digital devices.

The students desired also couches, pictures, table lamps, generally speaking everything which could offer more comfort through an attractive and relaxing atmosphere.

The Library and the Local Community – The Library as a 'Bibliopoint'

Our library has sought partnership with the local community to become a Bibliopoint of Biblioteche di Roma (Rome Public Libraries; portal: <http://www.bibliotu.it>). Established in 1996, the 'Istituzione delle Biblioteche di Roma' coordinates the city's public library and

cultural centres network to enhance library services, cultural programs, and activities. This institution has not only established public libraries across Rome but also Bibliopoints—cultural and reading centres within school libraries open to the public outside school hours, benefiting both the school and the Library Institution by fostering community engagement and broader dissemination.

Through this partnership, Civil Servants have provided invaluable support, aiding in the development of our web catalogue and organizing book collections according to the Dewey Decimal Classification system.

Engaging with the local community demands significant effort, particularly in promoting these new cultural centres and ensuring ongoing access to services. After years of dedication, we now offer afternoon openings once a week. One effective strategy to raise awareness of the Bibliopoint has been hosting meetings with authors, such as the successful event in 2017 with writer and radio presenter Giordano Meacci. During these events, students creatively posed questions using a specially decorated jar, creating a warm and welcoming atmosphere.

The Library and its OPAC

A significant milestone in opening our library to the local community and the general public was transitioning from a paper catalogue to an Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC). This ongoing effort has involved collaboration among librarians, teachers, students, and Civil Servants, who received specific training from Biblioteche di Roma.

To implement the OPAC, we joined the school library network 'Bibliorete Ostia', initially comprising 15 schools in 2015. More recently, we have adopted 'Clavis', a new open-source cataloguing and circulation management system, and joined the 'RBSLazio' network, which includes over 90 school libraries across the region. This network provides opportunities for cataloguing training and sharing best practices to promote reading.

Now, accessing our catalogue is convenient from home, and users can also reserve materials they wish to consult.

Beyond the Library Physical Space

During the COVID-19⁹⁷ emergency we experienced the importance of another remarkable service we can offer: the digital lending, which does not involve reading e-books only, but also implies using different media through the web. We use the service of MLOL, a digital lending platform which is accessible 24/7. Students, teachers and parents can borrow e-books from all Italian publishers, and they can choose among 60.000 titles, they have access to 5.000 newspapers and journals from all over the world and other media such as audio-books, video and music. This means the chance for the users to enjoy and use the library service not only in the physical space of the school library, but also in the comfort of home. Another great opportunity given by MLOL is to meet the reading taste of the young generation: often in secondary school teachers prefer to select books and materials that they think students should read and sometimes they forget that the pleasure of reading can vary according to age. Digital lending allows us to expand our virtual resources to include young adults' literature and works that we might not have in mind.

In this way the public can have access to an enormous and diverse amount of materials in any place and at any time.

The Distributed Library

We are still working on the spatial renovation of the library. Now the Aula Magna is a multifunctional space where books and meetings related to literature and promotion of reading are held. In the last years, lectures on 19th century Literature were organized; shared readings with younger students from other schools were held, and also concerts with the Chopin Association were performed. Recently the students themselves have started their 'Book Club': once a month they meet to discuss a book they have all chosen to read.

The Aula Magna is now more attractive since new furniture was placed, gaining some free space. There are also small moveable and modular tables to allow working in groups.

The next step is the distributed library to suggest the idea that reading is possible everywhere in the school and not only in the library. The entrance or the hallways, underused and anonymous spaces, were

⁹⁷ On the new distance learning activities during the COVID-19 emergency and on 'School library as a source' see Roncaglia (2020).

newly planned by the Architect Serena Rubino, and now they find a new function and can supplement teaching with reading.

Final Remarks

Despite the overall positive balance, some critical issues still remain, such as, for example, the timetables of our schools, our school organization, the difficulty in easily integrating learning with teaching that always manages to exploit the wide world of information that nowadays also includes digital. It is difficult to combine new active learning with several positive sides of our tradition. In the last few years there has been a passionate debate about the future of the 'liceo classico' (i.e., grammar school) in Italy. In particular, in 2014, a trial on the 'liceo classico' was held in Turin (Fondazione per la Scuola & MIUR, 2014), in which well-known scholars, such as Canfora and Eco, took part. Canfora especially underlined the importance of this type of high school for four reasons: the opportunity to study history of philosophy and science, in particular to study history itself, to acquire a philological mind and to achieve the practice of translating Greek and Latin. These sophisticated activities require the teacher's guidance and central role, knowledge and not only competence and time for students to study on their own and absorb a method. This work needs concentration and it is difficult to practice in a workshop activity. Especially as translating involves interpretation, decoding and language management.

In Italy, a further problem is that the teacher of Italian language and literature is usually in charge of reading promotion and education, while these skills should be improved in all subjects. Unfortunately, teamwork among teachers of different subjects is very often hard to put in place.

Another aim should be getting students involved in the different library activities: for instance, decorating the library walls and setting up the school library website are important ways to show to all users that the library is a place for them since it is related and functional to their life.⁹⁸ I would like to finish my talk referring to what Eco wrote about home libraries not only being a place where we read books, but also a place

⁹⁸ Cf. Marquardt (2013). *La biblioteca scolastica...* In Vivarelli, Ed., qtd., p. 317; she refers to Joan Frye Williams, mentioned in [Peggy Milam Creighton] (2006, November 9). Thoughts on the School Library Journal Summit in Chicago continued, *AASL Blog*. <<http://www.aasl.org/aaslblog/?p=137>>.

where we learn from our unread books. The Italian writer shows that even just moving a book, removing dust from it, transferring that book to another place with others relating to it, we read even the ones we do not read simply getting to know their paper, their colours, another old time when they were written. Therefore, not only our personal library, but I think all libraries are a gateway to the books never read, and we should not be afraid if a book disappears, but if a library disappears. Especially in a school. School libraries should not disappear, since they are seeds of knowledge that must grow in every school.

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The Distributed Library of ‘Vivona’ Grammar School: The Reading Corners Project, by Serena Rubino⁹⁹

Abstract

The reading corners project of ‘Liceo Vivona’ in Rome comes out from the need for expanding the outreach of its library. Former interventions to improve the space lacked an overall view of the school situation, as well the new ways of reading and learning were not taken in account. The project’s key point is a connection between customers’ needs and wills and the school’s architectural assets, which lead to the reuse of some extra aisle space. The main project goals were: searching for a new space in a defined perimeter; re-conceptualizing the same space through design furniture; punctual study of materials, forms and colours; several painting solutions for the walls. The project and its creative process mainly emerge in the reading corners’ realization as an ‘architectural object’, which works both on its own and in a whole system, and can be the pilot project for further interventions in other parts of the school building. This quality is needed as an aspect of sustainability, because of the need for working at versatile micro-projects, made out of mobile elements, which are replicable and introductory to future projects. Last but not least, the reading corner can be defined as a typological element itself, that can be exported in other schools and places, just by putting an eye on chromatic and spatial needs, and without losing its meaning.

Keywords: Regenerative environment; Reading corner; Distributed school library; Design; Materials; Arts.

⁹⁹ Architect, Assistant Professor at Roma Tre University.

Introduction

The state of places corresponds to the reality of many Italian school buildings, which, although maintained and improved over time, don't perfectly correspond to the whole range of spaces and learning opportunities that we have nowadays.

The entire 'F. Vivona' Grammar School building suffers from the lack of a comprehensive redesign intervention that addresses all the functions taking place inside it. This is needed despite the success of some previous improvements, such as the construction of new classrooms and laboratories, the expansion of spaces, and the opening of a small café as a refreshment area for students and teachers. The didactic function, in all its aspects from the most theoretical to the most practical and applicative, is not the only function of a school building. Consideration must also be given to sports, reception, the representation of the school building at official events, and, last but not least, the need for flexible and useful spaces to accommodate various uses of the building, even outside class times.

The school building has a Roman brick facade and pitched roof, it is provided with large outdoor spaces, including a garden that introduces us to the entrance. The building was built between the 1950ies and 1960ies, as can also be seen from the treatment of the facades, with contrasting horizontal stripes, from the large windows that bring light to the distribution spaces and classrooms, and from the treatment of some spaces glazed with perforated bricks, which create a filter pattern between the outside and the inside.

The orientation of the main facade to the south-east makes the parts that take light from these spaces very luminous in the morning hours, and pleasantly enlighten even in the afternoon, avoiding the reddish light of the sunset, typical of the west positioning, and not useful to read. Following the positioning of the main facade, the spaces for the reading corners are located in the corridors, at the entrance and on the first and second floors. These are spaces that are currently underused, which house only some furnishings and the occasional stay of students or school staff. Specifically, the areas destined for reading corners are located between the corridor, the lift landing and access to the stairs; these spaces, that correspond to 6 m² one of them and to 11 m² the remaining two, are directly illuminated by large windows, which also guarantee good ventilation, and are sound insulated from passage

noise, thanks to the plan arrangement, which takes count of the corridor necessary space.

The Reading Corner Project

The actors of this project are the tools, chosen to ensure a good use of the space as a space for reading, specifically: seats, tables, shelves and sound-absorbing elements.

The first furnishing element to characterize the project, consists of the sound-absorbing room separators necessary to delimit the reading corners and to isolate them from the walking noise of the corridor. These are cactus-shaped panels in three different shapes and colours, from 1.50 m to 1.80 m in height. Talking about the entrance reading corner, the room separator limits introspection in addition to the perimeter, promoting a silent and calm atmosphere as necessary for reading.

The cactus-shaped panels, coloured red, orange and petrol blue, have characterized and given identity to each corner through the colour, and guided the choices in terms of colour of the sound-absorbing poufs used as seats, to further contribute to the acoustic insulation and to absorb the sound of footsteps in the corridor.

In an environment characterized by colour, the remaining elements of furniture, tables and shelves, make their contribution in making the coloured element stand out, thanks to the transparency of plexiglass and opacity of black wood. In fact, the reading tables for one person, black coloured like the base of the cactuses, characterized by the rounded triangular shape of the shelf, integrate well into the space, making themselves appreciated for the design but without being noisy. These are small tables, so as to encourage their use exclusively for reading, making the space more characteristic, and avoiding any overload of users considering the available space.

The shelves in transparent plexiglass house the reading materials and hold the books on display, explaining the function of the space and well integrating with the walls, provided of wall paintings. In the two variants with two and three levels, the shelves have the suitable heights and thicknesses to house the volumes, and a low weight, which makes them suitable for passageways, for which changes in the arrangement could occur in case of events, collective reading or other use needs. Furthermore, the reading corners lend themselves well to welcoming

people waiting to be received, for example during teacher-parent interview activities, or as rest and refreshment areas during official events of the school community.

In order to define the spatiality of each reading corner, in addition to the furnishing and space definition solutions already mentioned, the concerned walls will be decorated during a workshop involving the designer and the students, who will personally work on the painting of the walls, with the help of an artist, in order to realize some reproductions of artworks in a geometric pattern. In addition to the aesthetic and design factors, the importance of creating wall paintings together with the students is important in order to create awareness of these new spaces, so as to encourage the integration of the function, the understanding of the type of activity that will take place in the reading corner and education to self-management of cultural spaces, through the practical act of painting, as an active contribution to the realization. The wall paintings, integrated with works of art, will make the three reading corners identifiable inside the building at each level, in order to attract both regular and occasional users.

Figure 1. 'Dante' Reading Corner (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

Since the 'F. Vivona' Grammar School library is a *BiblioPoint* of the Rome Public Libraries network, it was necessary to design the reading corners within a broader library system, which aims to characterize and enhance even the current school library and generate a 'Reading path'

through the building that contributes to increase the use of the *BiblioPoint*.

A fundamental point of analysis in the design of the reading corners was the sustainability of the intervention and the involvement of the school community in its implementation. Sustainability, not only economic, but also regarding spaces and types of use, was understood at the same time as a starting condition and a result to be pursued. This happens because the reading corners do not aim to be an indifferent addition to the school equipment compared to the current conditions, instead they are a way of enhancing the existing space, implementing its function and making the process of expanding the spaces of the culture congruous with respect of the building possibilities, avoiding the creation of new spaces and the detriment of others who would remain left to themselves.

Figure 2. The “School of Athens” Reading Corner (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

In addition, the reading corners are designed as a ‘light’ intervention and therefore their sustainability lies also in the possibility of disassembly and reassembly in the case of building renovation works, and thus avoiding a loss of both planning and economic resources.

Figure 3. Apollo and Diana (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

Artwork

Talking about design, the decoration of the reading corners has two objectives: to combine the shapes, design and colours of each 'corner' and at the same time pay tribute to some anniversaries related to the world of Italian art and culture.

In the entrance area of the grammar school, the red reading corner celebrates the 750th anniversary of Dante's birth, through the *Portrait of Dante Alighieri* by Sandro Botticelli (1495, oil on canvas, private collection, Geneva). In this portrait, Botticelli was inspired by the *Portrait of Dante showing the Divine Comedy* by Domenico di Michelino (1456, fresco, Santa Maria del Fiore, Florence), and also by the description of the poet in *Trattatello in laude di Dante* by Giovanni Boccaccio. This painting was chosen among the various portraits of Dante for his personality. The poet's profile is surrounded by a soft and clear line at the same time, emerges from the light of the background, highlighting the laurel crown, symbol of glory, which frames the red hood. It is a symbolic picture not only for the technique and the subject, but also for the message of welcome by the father of the Italian language at the school entrance.

Figure 4. Dante's Mural Decoration (Project by Archt. S. Rubino)

On the first floor, the orange reading corner recalls the 500 years since Raffello's death, with the reproduction of the *School of Athens* (1511, fresco, Stanza della Segnatura, Apostolic Palaces, Vatican). The fresco, commissioned by Pope Julius II, had the purpose of celebrating Roman civilization and the culture of classicism. Among the frescoes program of the Vatican Rooms, it represents Philosophy: the values of the good, truth and beauty were illustrated in the entire room. It is interesting to note that some characters have an appearance reminiscent of Raphael's contemporary artists: Plato remembers Leonardo and Michelangelo impersonates Heraclitus, in addition to the self-portrait of Raphael present in the work to emphasize his authorship. The *School of Athens* is a clear indication of the classical vocation of the grammar school, as well as an opportunity to celebrate the propensity to study, research and humanistic thinking.

Figure 5. The School of Athens Mural Decoration (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

Finally, at the second floor the petrol blue reading corner pays homage to Tiepolo, 250 years after his death, with *Apollo and Diana* (1757, fresco, Villa Valmarana ai Nani, Vicenza). This fresco shows the two divinities sitting on a cloud. Apollo, facing the spectator, holds the lyre in his right hand and his quiver full of arrows in the left. Apollo's golden yellow dress and the yellowish colour of the clouds allude to his being the divinity of the sun, but even more important are the other arts he protects: music and poetry. Once again, the purpose of the reading corner is to enhance the culture and symbolize the classicism of the studies that take place inside the high school.

Figure 6. Apollo and Diana (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

The reproduction of the artworks is matched with a geometric pattern, made out from triangular shapes, which takes the colour of each reading corner in different shades. The design was specially created to evoke three-dimensionality and to bring out the volume contained between the decorated walls, except for the one dedicated to the artworks as they only have a two-dimensions vision.

Figure 7. Ground Floor: 'Dante' Reading Corner (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

Figure 8. First Floor: 'School of Athens' Reading Corner (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

Figure 9. Second Floor: 'Apollo and Diana' Reading Corner (Project by Archt. S. Rubino).

Final Remarks

The project has pursued the search for a new spatiality within a pre-established perimeter, defining new places through furniture, materials and colour. The intervention, sustainable from different points of view, has set itself the goal from the beginning of enhancing the place,

through thoughtful planning and the use of design objects as added value.

The attention paid to the choice of colours was the leitmotiv that guided the other choices. The combination of materials that are soft to the touch, with a high texture and visible stitching, such as the fabrics of the cactus and the poufs, and smooth and cold touch materials such as the tables and shelves, was intended as a design opportunity. The aim is to encourage not only chromatic differences, but also different experiences to the touch, in order to support the function of reading. All of that is needed to accompany, isolate and accommodate the act of reading, as room dividers and seats are covered with fabric, with the aim of minding the feeling of calm and comfort, similar to reading on a comfortable sofa.

Instead, the tools to support books such as shelves and tables are smooth materials, in order to generate a contrast: the matte black tables perform their function of supporting the books occupying the minimum space and, thanks to the chosen finish, they avoid the reflection of the light coming from the large windows on the reading surface. The shelves, in transparent plexiglass, house the books showing the content, this is a colourless material but with its own brightness, given by the reflection of the light, which serves not only to contain, but also to highlight the function of reading corners.

A further important factor is the colour trend from floor to floor, starting from the red ground floor, we find orange and then petrol blue. This trend not only chromatically marks the path through the school, respecting a degree of discoloration, but also accompanies the historical path given by the works of art represented in the corners, in fact starting from Dante, the oldest character, the timeline it goes upwards passing through Raphael and ending to Tiepolo.

It is important to note that, although the reading corners have reference colours, there are chromatic points in common between all the interventions, such as black and the transparency of the furnishings, and the shades of beige and grey present in the wall paintings. This choice, necessary to give uniformity to the project, finds its goal in leaving open possibilities for the school building: in fact, if the school decides to expand the number of corners, this base consisting of transparent, black and neutral colours will be suitable for housing other reference colours for new reading corners. It will also be possible, one

day, to involve all the colours of the reading spaces in a possible renovation of the school library.

The development of the reading corner as an architectural object, that works both individually and in a system, allows the visitor to identify a typological element that can be exported to other places, being it adaptable and contextualised. This is a very important factor if one thinks of how many public and private spaces have underused minor spaces that could instead give a good service to users as reading spaces. Finally, it is interesting to note that with three interventions in a low-cost budget, but with a strong expressive charge, it is possible to bring a breath of fresh air into school buildings that are unfortunately affected by the passage of time, the evolution of teaching methods and use of space. This data brings with it positivity regarding the many cases of impossibility to build new school buildings, and focuses on the enhancement of the building heritage of Italian schools.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Prof. Mario Panizza¹⁰⁰ and Prof. Lucia Nucci,¹⁰¹ supervisors of my master thesis research on the reuse and re-functionalization of Block E in the *Speicherstadt*¹⁰² of Hamburg, where I also designed a library.

Heartfelt thanks go to Prof. Luisa Marquardt¹⁰³ for suggesting the design project of the reading corners with great enthusiasm and introduced me to the IFLA and CNBA.

I would like to take the opportunity and thank Prof. Daniela Benincasa, Headmistress of 'F. Vivona' Grammar School, for the design opportunity and its success, together with all the school staff involved in this design and construction process.

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¹⁰² *Speicherstadt*: from German language 'city of warehouses', it is a complex of 17 warehouses in the old port of Hamburg, built between 1884 and 1927 on an area of approximately 330,000 square meters. *Speicherstadt* is the largest warehouse complex ever built, and in 2015 it was named a World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

¹⁰³ Professor of Library and Information Science at Roma Tre University, Department of Humanities and Department of Education.

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Session 3

Reading between Print and Digital

Chapter 3

Between Print and Digital: New Challenges and Opportunities for Reading,¹⁰⁴ by Flavia Cristiano¹⁰⁵

Abstract

The speech introduces the third session of the Seminar dedicated to reading, the change in reading behaviours and the different ways of using reading in the light of technological innovations. In particular, it focuses on the importance of reading in childhood and on the opportunities provided by new media. In emphasizing the need for overcoming the distinction between reading printed books and the use of digital resources, it refers to the strategic role that educational institutions, first of all school libraries, should play.

Keywords: reading; digital resources; school libraries.

¹⁰⁴ Translation by Luisa Marquardt.

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Introduction

I would like to recall, in the introduction, the words that Michèle Petit dedicated to the importance of reading in childhood at the meeting organized by IBBY Italia at the Bologna Children's Book Fair on March 27, 2018.¹⁰⁶ Anthropologist and scholar with international experience, Petit, who has been working for years on reading practices and the relationship with written culture in the places of informal education and social hardship, first of all emphasized the value of reading in creating a feeling of individual harmony, 'a feeling of living, of being in one's own place', a harmony between the inner world and the surrounding world.

‘Leggere, o ascoltare leggere, permette prima di tutto di creare uno spazio accogliente, soprattutto in coloro che non dispongono di alcun territorio personale’, consente inoltre, anche nelle situazioni più difficili, ‘un salto in un altrove dove il sogno, il pensiero, il ricordo, l’immaginazione di un futuro, diventano possibili’.¹⁰⁷

Books,

‘e particolarmente le opere letterarie, possono essere delle dimore prese in prestito’,¹⁰⁸

a shelter, a den, a house of words to live in, for this reason reading remains an essential value for children and adolescents who allow them to live a wider, more intense, richer present while it nourishes and increases their daily life. In order to set the beauty and power of life inherent in books free, there is a need for what Petit calls ‘smugglers’, necessary mediators to make the images of literature, art or science, reach out young people through the words of reading: let's talk about educators, readers, animators, teachers and librarians.

Books, works, readings stay in the centre, while families, schools and libraries are the indispensable mediators. The crucial and fundamental role of *passseurs* (i.e., smugglers) for adolescent reading is well illustrated

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.ibbyitalia.it/eventi/elogio-della-lettura-leggere-tra-spazi-privati-e-pubblici/>; speech published at URL: <https://www.ibbyitalia.it/2020/04/01/elogio-della-lettura-limportanza-della-lettura-nellinfanzia/>.

¹⁰⁷ *I.e.*, ‘Reading, or listening to reading, first of all allows you to create a welcoming space, especially in those who do not have any personal territory’, it also allows, even in the hardest situations, ‘a leap into an elsewhere where dreams, thoughts, the memory, the imagination of a future, become possible’, *ivi*. (TN)

¹⁰⁸ *I.e.*, ‘and particularly literary works, can be borrowed residences’, *ivi*. (TN)

in the interesting contribution by Beatrice Eleuteri that closes this session.

Integrating Print and Digital with No Merit Rankings or Unnecessary Regrets

Mediation tools and meeting facilitators are on the one hand traditional techniques, such as, for example, reading aloud, an essential and irreplaceable way to convey stories and words: Giovanni Moretti and Bianca Briceag precisely focus their speech on the importance and effects of shared reading-aloud.

On the other hand, new tools and innovative digital projects to induce reading are becoming increasingly interesting, such as those described by Gino Roncaglia, who presents ‘Read Twinning’, a sort of continuation of ‘The Living Book’ Project, which aimed to promote augmented reading in a perspective of integration between print and digital, and by Arianna L. Morini who presents in her contribution an integrated and interdisciplinary model of reading education, developed as part of an empirical research that aimed at promoting the creative and divergent thinking of students using picture books, art books and new practices reading with illustrated and interactive e-books. In today’s world, necessarily interconnected and increasingly immersed in a virtual dimension, the old contrast between print and digital no longer makes sense: today reading, even on paper, implies a school and a library that know how to combine and integrate print and digital with no merit rankings or unnecessary regrets.

I take advantage of the birth centenary of a great innovator like Gianni Rodari to refer to the fun, and brilliant, re-reading of his famous article on ‘9 ways to teach children to hate reading’,¹⁰⁹ that Ugo Guidolin¹¹⁰ provides us in the Ibbly Italia’s blog (‘post’ of March 10, 2020).¹¹¹ In his

¹⁰⁹ Article originally published in «Il Giornale dei Genitori», i.e. «Parents’ Journal», (1964, October), No. 10, later merged into *Scuola della fantasia*, i.e. *School of Phantasy* (Roma: Editori Riuniti, 1992), as well as quoted by various authors, such as, for example, Denti, R. (1982). *Come far leggere i bambini*, (Libri di base: 46). Roma: Editori Riuniti, and available online at URL: <https://www.ilpiaceredileggere.it/nove-modi-per-insegnare-ai-ragazzi-a-odiare-la-lettura-gianni-rodari> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 09:54).

¹¹⁰ Partner of Koo-koo Books, he deals with media education and digital literacy, teaches Cultural Anthropology of Digital Media at IUSVE University of Verona and Venice.

¹¹¹ <https://www.ibbyitalia.it/2020/03/10/9-nuovi-modi-per-insegnare-ai-nativi-digitali-a-odiare-la-lettura/> (ultima consultazione: 18/12/2020 ore 09:54).

‘Nove nuovi modi per insegnare ai nativi digitali a odiare la lettura’¹¹²
Guidolin lists:

1. Presentare il libro come alternativa allo *smartphone*
2. Presentare il libro come alternativa al videogioco
3. Dire ai bambini di oggi che noi da bambini leggevamo di più
4. Ritenere che i bambini abbiano troppe distrazioni digitali
5. Dare la colpa ai *digital media* se i bambini non amano la lettura
6. Trasformare il libro in strumento di tortura e i *media digitali* nel paese dei balocchi
7. Rifiutarsi di leggere sui dispositivi digitali assieme ai bambini
8. Non offrire una scelta di qualità
9. Educare i bambini a leggere i nuovi media (ossia educare i bambini all’uso dei media sin da piccoli, seguirli e giocare con loro nella rete).¹¹³

New digital technologies are a necessary tool to help us educate girls and boys to read stories in all of their dimensions, while digital platforms are able to offer quality resources and make them available for free even to disadvantaged groups or those who live in remote areas. In an easy summary, we need quality school libraries and we can only think of them as innovative.

International studies assign a strategic role to school libraries, as addressed in the first session of this seminar: the data illustrated by Albert Boekhorst confirm that students who have a good school library perform better than those without a school library. The same happens in Italy: Ornella Papa with Rita Marzoli refers to an INVALSI research which detects the best academic performance of students who attend schools with well-functioning libraries and with a rich book heritage. Unfortunately, the Italian situation is not encouraging: quality school libraries are few in relation to the number of existing libraries. The

¹¹² Nine new ways to teach digital natives to hate reading. (TN)

¹¹³ 1. Presenting the book as an alternative to a smartphone.
2. Presenting the book as an alternative to the videogame.
3. Telling today’s children that we as children read more.
4. Feeling that children have too many digital distractions.
5. Blaming digital media if children don’t like reading.
6. Transforming the book into an instrument of torture and digital media in the Land of Toys.
7. Refusing to read on digital devices with children.
8. Not providing [children with] a quality choice.
9. Educating children to read new media (i.e., educating children to use media from an early age, follow them and play with them on the net). (TN)

survey carried out by the Italian Publishers Association¹¹⁴ certifies the limited dissemination of school libraries adequately equipped with paper and digital resources; if it is true that 84.8% of schools have libraries (with a decrease compared to the 89% surveyed in 2011), the average holdings do not reach 4,000 titles, and, if the book holdings increased in quantity between 2011 and 2019 (but the new titles that entered the library hardly reach the 0.2 rate per student), the weekly opening hours are decreasing, as well as professionals, recognized as competent collections' managers and ensuring their full use, continue to be lacking.

However, there are some positive signs: firstly, the extraordinary opportunities provided to schools by the MLOL portal, the first and only one digital library available 24/7 on the web, able to provide Italian schools of all kinds and grades with digital lending services and the access to major newspapers and periodicals, tens of thousands of e-books (over 70,000), music and audio books, as well as databases and open source resources.

Precious data are provided by Paola Pala and Giulio Blasi in their contribution on the *Digital lending of e-books and other resources in Italian school libraries*.

Even the presence of 'good practices', such as the Turin 'widespread library' project described by Laura Di Perna, offers models to imitate and induces a moderate optimism.

Final Remarks

Encouraging prospects are opened above all by the recent entry into force of the Law 13 February 2020, No. 15 (Provisions for the promotion and support of reading), which recognizes and underlines the value of reading as a basic competence for school learning at all levels, and devotes an entire article, Art. 5, to reading at school. The law confirms and strengthens the recent ministerial attention to the development of innovative school libraries (made the subject of specific MIUR¹¹⁵-MIBAC¹¹⁶ funding in the last two years), putting the variegated set of school libraries into a system through the

¹¹⁴ The results of the data processing were presented in Rome on 5 December 2019, during the book fair 'Più libri, più liberi: fiera della piccola e media editoria', <https://bit.ly/381V6fl> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10:04).

¹¹⁵ Ministry of Education. (TN)

¹¹⁶ Ministry of Cultural Heritage. (TN)

establishment of ‘Hub Schools’, that are responsible for the local school library service.

The ‘Hub School’ - an expression that immediately recalls me the SBN [National Library Service] Hubs – is appointed of the coordination of the related libraries in a networked system also open to a coherent relationship with the local system of public libraries.

We await the Action Plan envisaged by the law which should transform the legislative dictate into reality, with the hope that Italian school libraries can find valid support in their relationship with local libraries and institutions, as well as in the possibilities offered by digital services, and be able to represent such a fundamental reference point for the promotion of reading at school, which is an essential element for training children and adolescents in quality literacy.¹¹⁷

¹¹⁷ cf. in this regard, the European Declaration of the right to read and write prepared by Elinet: European Literacy Policy Network European Literacy Policy Network (ELINET). (2016, March). *European Declaration of the Right to Literacy (Full version)*. Köln: Elinet. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/2NOLAG6> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10:00).

Chapter 3.1

An Integrated and Interdisciplinary Model for Reading Education to Promote Creative and Divergent Thought in Students,¹¹⁸ by Arianna L. Morini¹¹⁹

Abstract

The contribution presents an integrated and interdisciplinary model for reading education developed in the context of empirical research aimed at promoting creative and divergent thinking in students (Biasi *et al.*, 2019; Biasi *et al.*, 2020; Moretti & Morini, 2020; Poce, 2020). The research aimed to verify if and how it might be possible to enhance the didactic offer by introducing artistic activities, experiences, and materials to integrate with and support curricular content in a school context. The study involved four fifth-grade primary school class groups, two of which were experimental and two served as control groups. The classes were identified in educational contexts focused on the promotion of books, reading, and the appreciation of authors' original illustrations. In the experimental class groups, teachers participated in a training program that emphasized picture books, art books, illustrated and interactive e-books, and art-focused apps. The research outcomes confirm that the integrated and interdisciplinary approach to reading education was effective, producing a statistically significant result in the experimental group compared to the control group.

Keywords: picture books; pedagogy of reading; illustrated and interactive e-books; creative and divergent thinking; empirical research.

¹¹⁸ Translation by Antonio Lenzo.

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Introduction

The contribution examines the results of a study where an integrated and interdisciplinary model for reading education in primary schools aimed at encouraging forms of aesthetic experience (Biasi *et al.*, 2019; Biasi *et al.*, 2020; Moretti & Morini, 2020; Poce, 2020) was applied. National and international research has found that the introduction of picture books, art books, and illustrated and interactive e-books in a school context can contribute to developing creative and artistic thinking in students (Kiefer, 1986; Dank-McGhee & Slutsky, 2007; Moretti, 2017; Morini, 2017).

Picture books have seen widespread diffusion in the past thirty years and have also become the object of study and analysis in an academic context. Nodelman, with his volume *Words about Pictures* in the 1980s, launched a debate on the implications of the quality of picture books and proposed an initial classification in terms of features. Lewis (2001) defines illustrated albums as the result of a dynamic process characterized by high degrees of flexibility and complexity, profoundly conditioned by continuous technological developments, social and cultural changes, and artistic innovation. The aesthetic appreciation of picture books involves the development of what is termed ‘visual literacy.’ By ‘visual literacy,’ we mean the ability to decode and interpret visual messages; it also comprises the ability to internally visualize, visually communicate, read, and interpret visual images (Bramford, 2003). The multiple communicative codes and iconic languages at work in picture books invite the reader to participate actively not only in the reading process and decoding of meaning but also in filling out ‘empty spaces’ through the personal interpretation of text and image (Bader, 1976; Lewis, 2001; Dallari, 2008).

The empirical research into picture books and illustrated and interactive e-books as useful tools for contributing to aesthetic formation and the development of creative abilities in students represents a field still unexplored in a national context (Campagnaro, 2012; Morini, 2015). The use of picture books in the early educational cycle is strategic for learning how to integrate text with image and develop more complex skills necessary to become a future reader. An integrated and interdisciplinary didactic model should particularly encourage the development of certain skills across the board, as deemed necessary for significant learning in students, including the ability for expression and communication and creative and divergent

thinking (Biasi, Bonaiuto & Cordellieri, 2009; Wikström, 2011; Moretti, 2017).

Research Aims

The methodology chosen is empirical research of an experimental nature, aiming to verify the impact of introducing an integrated and interdisciplinary model for reading education on the development of creative and divergent thinking in students. The study involved four fifth-grade primary school class groups, two of which were experimental and two served as control groups. These class groups were selected from a school network that has long been active in promoting reading in the metropolitan area of Rome (Roma Città Metropolitana), participating in initiatives and projects devoted to children's reading and literature, as well as the appreciation of original artwork by illustrators for children and young adults.

The model conceived (showcased in the following paragraph) was shared with the teachers of the experimental class groups, who participated in a blended educational process with in-person meetings and remote formative activities via a dedicated Moodle platform.

The aim of the research was to verify if and how it might be possible to enhance the didactic offer by introducing artistic activities, experiences, and materials to integrate with and support curricular content in a school context.

The Integrated and Interdisciplinary Model for Reading Education

The integrated and interdisciplinary model for reading education, developed in the context of this study, involved the introduction of picture books, art books, illustrated and interactive e-books, and art-oriented apps in a school context. Teachers from different disciplinary contexts emphasized the quality of the presented content and learning strategies, allowing students to fully appreciate and understand the unique aspects. In training meetings, both print and digital books were analyzed to reveal the elements that contribute to the development of a sense of aesthetics and creative thinking, as well as to encourage students' motivation to read. For example, albums with illustrations by renowned authors, using unique artistic techniques that enhance the aesthetic aspect, or with illustrations that extend the text's meaning and

invite the reader to discover new information among the graphic elements, were deemed to be of high quality. Besides consolidating the teachers' skills in identifying suitable content, attention was devoted to developing more effective mediation strategies to promote students' interest.

The integrated and interdisciplinary model for reading education involves incorporating artistic activities, experiences, and materials into didactic methodology to integrate with and support curricular content. It is a flexible model that aims to invite students toward deep reading of text and image, promoting both the enjoyment of reading and creative and divergent thought (Biasi, Bonaiuto & Cordellieri, 2009; Wikström, 2011; Moretti, 2017). Teachers are specifically asked to devote special care to the fitting of environments, timings, and modes in which students are offered the chance to interact with the book as an object, in its various forms. In experimental classes, over 30 texts, including picture books, art books, silent books,¹²⁰ and over 10 illustrated and interactive e-books for reading and engagement on mobile devices, were made available.

Regarding digital offerings, illustrated and interactive e-books may be considered strategic resources for fully leveraging new technologies in educational contexts (Moretti & Morini, 2014). They are 'interactive artefacts' (Wikert, 2012) and 'multimedial' (Murray, 2011; Gasparini, 2014) that extend the reading experience, allowing active interaction with the text and images. Strategies must be activated to develop creative and interpretive skills to read with awareness.

Among the e-books selected from a national and international context as particularly interesting for introduction in the study are *La grande storia di un trattino* by Serge Bloch and *Double Double* by Menena Cottin.

La grande storia di un trattino, adapted from the printed book *La grande storia di un piccolo tratto* by Serge Bloch, was selected to invite students to engage with images and the aesthetic experience. In the e-book, the child-reader is called upon to be a co-protagonist of the story, participating actively and with awareness in certain crucial moments. The book metaphorically tells the story of a child who meets a 'small hyphen' and establishes a poetic dialogue with it that lasts through various phases of his life until he becomes an artist as an adult. It is a

¹²⁰ By *silent book* we mean wordless picture books, where narration is represented exclusively through images, without the aid of the text.

crossover¹²¹ work that can be read and interpreted on several levels. Among the e-book's high-quality features, one of the most interesting is the possibility of drawing and developing parts of the plot alongside the text. The user's graphic representation is sometimes guided and sometimes free-hand, as the child chooses what and how to draw, guided by artistic inspiration and creativity.

Fig. 1: The e-book adapted from *La grande storia di un piccolo tratto* by Serge Bloch

The graphic style is simple, using only black and red; black is used consistently, while red is reserved exclusively for the little hyphen. The narrative, in the digital audio version, is slow-paced, encouraging the reader to take their time for careful listening and attentive reading.

Experiencing the story in both print and digital formats supports the application of the integrated model for reading education. Another illustrated and interactive e-book used with the experimental class groups is *Double Double* by Menena Cottin, which was short-listed for the Bologna Ragazzi Digital Award (2014) in the 'Non-fiction' category. The e-book, by the author of the celebrated *Il libro nero dei colori* (2011), plays with the concept of 'contraries' or 'opposites' through interactive images.

¹²¹ By *crossover* we mean intergenerational books addressing readers of all age groups.

Fig. 2: Cover for the e-book 'Double Double' by Menena Cottin

The author employs visual perception to invite the reader to reflect on the importance of assuming different points of view. The drawings are white on a black background, allowing the reader to observe how the same image, when viewed upside-down, can change meaning. The illustrations, conceived as reversible images, were considered especially interesting and suitable for the study's context as they may contribute to developing an important aspect of divergent thinking: flexibility, which is the ability to observe and produce original thoughts by changing one's point of view.

To illustrate the e-book's logic at play, an example opening is presented below (Fig. 3).

Figure no. 3: Example of an illustration from 'Double Double' e-book before and after interaction.

In the left image, a book is shown as a story yet to be read. The images are accompanied by a single word, in this case 'begin'. When the reader interacts with the illustrations touching the book, the illustration is turned upside down. The book, which in the first image was yet to begin, once upside down is a finished book, followed by the word 'end'. The two illustrated and interactive e-books presented are to be considered examples of materials that distinguish themselves quality-wise in their projects and realizations. The integrated and

interdisciplinary model for reading education presented in the experimental class groups makes use of a variety of texts, in different formats (Moretti, 2017), which allows teachers to individualize their offer and to respond to the specific needs of each student.

The Test of Divergent Thinking

Data were recorded in both experimental and control class groups before and after the didactic intervention. In this contribution, we will examine the results related to the *Test of Divergent Thinking* (Williams, 1994).

In a national context, Williams' *Test of Divergent Thinking* (1994) is a valid and reliable instrument for measuring the creative abilities of students in relation to both verbal and visual-perceptive skills. The test's theoretical underpinnings reference Guilford's analytical studies (1954), followed by Torrance's (1959), Williams's (1966), and Meeker's (1977). The test involves the administration of two protocols (A and B), before and after the didactic intervention, which, in this case, was included in reference to the experimental class groups.

The two protocols consist of twelve frames containing shapes of graphic elements from which the students are asked to produce the greatest possible number of drawings within a set time (20 minutes). The *Test* reveals a combination of features in the student that together define creative thought, creative process, and creative production.

The *Test* was chosen because, unlike other tools, it measures both cognitive and emotional components, evaluating divergent semantic transformation and divergent figure transformation. Besides graphic production, students are also asked, once they have finished drawing, to pick an original title by choosing a witty or interesting phrase.

Another feature of the *Test* is that it offers an initial graphic stimulus. Studies in the field have found that being able to take advantage of a clue, instead of having just a blank sheet as a starting point, is important to encourage the development of creative thinking. The diversity of graphic shapes proposed thereby provides students with a broad range of possibilities in drawing. Scoring is conducted according to precise information given by the author. Following guidelines, for each frame it is possible to attribute a score for each of five factors involved in the *Test*: Fluency (F_1), Flexibility (F_x), Originality (O), Elaboration (E), and Titles (T). The student therefore gets an overall score for divergent thinking and a separate score for each factor.

The *Test* can be used directly by teachers, educators, or researchers, once they have gained familiarity with the tool and examined the score-attribution system. In the context of research, to ensure result reliability, scores were attributed contextually by several researchers, triangulating recorded data.

Having access to results for each factor besides the overall score constitutes a further advantage of this tool, as it allows one to individualize the didactic intervention based on individual students' scores by situating the best strategies for encouraging the development of each factor.

3. Analysis and Result Interpretation

The *Test of Divergent Thinking* was employed in both experimental and control class groups with Protocol A input and Protocol B output. The *Test* measures students' divergent thinking, producing an overall score and sub-scores in reference to the difference factors composing divergent thinking.

The first analysis to which the resulting data was subjected focused on overall scores in the input phase in both groups (experimental and control). In table 1, average scores, standard deviation and one-way ANOVA results¹²², which measures whether the difference in average between the two groups are significant.

Test of Divergent Thinking	Input average	Standard deviation	One-way ANOVA	F.
Control	76.4	7.4	0.298	1.096
Experimental	74.2	11.0		

Tab.1 *Difference between the input average for control group and experimental group.*

At input, the two groups achieved different average scores (76.4 for control and 74.2 for the experimental group). Variance analysis, conducted with a one-way ANOVA, confirms the two groups can be

¹²² ANOVA (*Analysis of Variance*) measures are statistical analyses that allow to compare results between two or more groups of data (in this case, control group and experimental group) so as to verify whether the difference is significant or not.

considered homogenous, as the difference between the two is not significant¹²³ ($p=0.298$).

To conclude the didactic intervention, which involved the introduction in experimental class groups of an integrated model for reading education, ‘Protocol B’ from the *Test of Divergent Thinking* (Williams, 1994) was administered.

As evidenced by data shown in Table 2, at the output the increase in average score is larger in the experimental group than in the control group. Furthermore, the difference between groups, calculated through an ANOVA, is significant ($p=0.045$). It is therefore possible to say that the two groups performed differently following the intervention.

Test of Divergent Thinking	Output average	Standard deviation	One-way ANOVA	F.
Control	77.8	6.5	0.045	4.165
Experimental	80.8	6.5		

Tab. 2 *Difference between output averages for control group and experimental group.*

Further investigating the factors that contribute to ‘divergent thinking’, it becomes apparent that one in particular distinguishes the two groups: ‘Titles’. The ‘titling’ factor refers to the students’ ability to use language in an intelligent, original and creative way. The highest score for each frame (3 points) is achieved when a fancy title is presented as expressing something not self-evident in the drawing. In figure 4, two drawings are shown, to which a title expressing a lexical synthesis skill-set in reference to a creative use of vocabulary was attributed.

¹²³ The probability level adopted in this study for the verification of statistical significance is $p \leq .050$.

Fig. no. 4: Example of two drawings that were given titles that scored the max for the ‘titling’ factor.

Within this factor, as shown in Table 3, the experimental group obtained a higher average score than the control group (27.4 *versus* 23.4) and the difference between the two groups appears to be statistically very significant ($p= 0.000$). The experimental group distinguishes itself for having developed greater skill in the use of language by attributing drawings with more creative titles as compared to the control group.

Test of divergent thinking: titling	‘Titling’ output average	Standard deviation	One-way ANOVA	F.
Control	23.4	4.83	0.000	13.586
Experimental	27.4	4.87		

Table 3 Difference between output averages between control and experimental groups within the ‘Titling’ factor.

The study’s aim was to verify not only whether the two groups had performed differently, but also between the improvement between input and output would be significant. For this reason, we used *Student’s T*¹²⁴ statistical analysis, that allows for evaluation of change between an earlier and a later measurement, as effected on a single sample (in our case, experimental and control groups), over a time interval.

¹²⁴ The Student's T is used in statistics to measure the significance of a change detected at two different times (e.g. before and after an educational intervention) on the same group of subjects.

In the case of the control group, as shown in Table 4, the improvement recorded in the *Test* between Measurement 1 (T1) and 2 (T2) is not significant (0.298) while the improvement recorded between T1(average 74.2) and T2 (average 80.8) for the experimental group was statistically significant (0.001).

	T1 – Average divergent thinking	Standard deviation	T2 – Average divergent thinking	Standard deviation	t	gl	Sign. (two- way)
Control	76.4	7.4	77.8	6.5	1.116	38	0.272
Experimental	74.2	11.0	80.8	6.5	3.677	34	0.001

Tab. 4 *Difference between input and output average for both control and experimental groups in the Test.*

In the experimental group, yet another interesting piece of data emerged (Table 5). The increment between input and output in the factor of ‘Originality’ ended up being statistically significant in the experimental group. Specifically, the group switched from an average score of 27.7 at input to an average of 33.4 at output.

	T1 – Average ‘originality’ factor	St. Dev.	T2 – Average ‘originality’ factor	St. Dev.	t	gl	Sign. (two- way)
Experimental	27.7	6.2	33.4	3.5	7.112	34	0.000

Tab. 5 *Difference between input and output average in the experimental group for the ‘Originality’ factor.*

The ‘Originality’ factor examined the students’ abilities to integrate the lines and graphic shapes proposed in the different frames in an original and creative way. Each frame presented a closed shape, represented by a so-called stimulus line. For less creative individuals, this enclosed shape acts as a boundary. Those who can work both within and beyond the closed shape, as well as around it, are deemed more creative. In attributing a score, a higher score was given to drawings in which a

synthesis was achieved, meaning the students were neither stiffly guided nor blocked by the line (Williams, 1993).

Figure 5 shows an example of a drawing that received the highest possible score (3 points): the drawing incorporates both the inside and outside of the closed shape (shown in the left figure).

Figure 5: Example of a drawing that scored the highest score in 'Originality'.

The didactic intervention applied to the experimental group contributed to an improvement in the students' skills in interpreting and producing original drawings. In this sense, it is possible to say that the exploration and use of quality materials, such as picture books, and illustrated and interactive e-books, may have contributed to developing this specific aspect of divergent thinking.

Final Remarks and Future Perspectives

The research outcomes confirm the possibility of enhancing the didactic approach by integrating artistic activities, experiences, and materials with curricular content in a school context. In particular, the study has demonstrated that didactic innovation, enriched by an integrated and interdisciplinary model for reading education aimed at fostering the development of creative and divergent thinking in students, proved effective and produced a statistically significant result in the experimental class groups compared to the control group.

The application of the integrated and interdisciplinary didactic model in a school context encouraged the development of expressive and communicative skills, as well as creative and divergent thinking in

students (Biasi, Bonaiuto & Cordellieri, 2009; Wikström, 2011; Moretti, 2017), all of which are essential for significant learning.

The model for reading education, developed with the teachers as part of research-formation, was applied in experimental class groups and involved the use of a broad range of text types and formats (Moretti, 2017). The availability of a variety of texts allowed the teachers to adapt their didactic approach to each context, individualizing the educational intervention and effectively responding to the needs of each student. Furthermore, the possibility of accessing stories in both printed and digital forms enabled the application of the model itself.

The study highlights the need, as expressed by teachers, for accessible and reliable tools for data recording, which can help identify specific factors related to students, often underrated or ignored, but now considered fundamental in teaching-learning processes. The *Test of Divergent Thinking* (Williams, 1994) proved to be a useful tool to address these needs, as it allows all participants (teachers, students, and families) to access both overall scores and specific factor scores. Such features can support a formative evaluative approach, recording information central to both curricular improvement and the individualization of the educational intervention and the reshaping of didactic projects. By considering the recorded scores for each student in the *Test*, teachers can identify better strategies to foster the development of skills related to each factor (Fluidity, Flexibility, Originality, Elaboration, and Titles). The study confirms the significance of these factors concerning important aspects of divergent thinking and suggests the need to focus on flexibility, i.e., the ability to observe and produce original thought starting from the ability to change one's point of view.

The experimental group distinguished itself from the control group in their developed use of language, attributing more creative titles to drawings than the control group did. The didactic intervention applied to the experimental group contributed to an improvement in students' abilities to interpret and produce original drawings. Based on the recorded evidence, it is possible to say that the exploration and use of high-quality materials, such as picture books and illustrated and interactive e-books, contributed to developing certain specific aspects of divergent thinking.

The inquiry verified that the two groups, control and experimental, could be distinguished from each other, and that the input and output discrepancy was significant. The potential future developments of the

line of inquiry described above should include the use of longitudinal studies, to observe developmental trends in creative and divergent thinking in the short- and long-term and to verify the effectiveness of training interventions and professional development adopting an integrated and interdisciplinary didactic model, emphasizing picture books, art books, illustrated and interactive e-books, and art-oriented apps.

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Shared Reading as a Strategy to Promote Educational Continuity within the Integrated System for Education and Instruction,¹²⁵ by Giovanni Moretti¹²⁶ and Bianca Briceag¹²⁷

Abstract

The contribution examines shared reading aloud practices conducted with children in early childhood, as fundamental for their cognitive and emotional development and as a useful tool to promote educational continuity in the context of educational services for the 0-6 age range, as prompted by the institution of the integrated system for education and instruction (D.Lgs. 65/2017). Eleven ‘Spring Sections’ (2-3 age group) associated to as many schools in Lazio were involved in the survey. The co-planning and realization of a shared reading aloud practice path with educators and teachers was pursued in the context of a Research-Formation activity conducted by Roma Tre University, in collaboration with USR Lazio (i.e. the Regional Education Agency). The study confirms shared reading aloud practices as a winning strategy for the promotion of educational continuity, as well as for children’s active participation in educational activities in the 0-6 age range. Furthermore, it goes to show that discussion among peers and with experts on shared reading aloud practices contributes to the formation and professional development of educators and teachers.

Keywords: shared reading; reading aloud; early childhood; educational continuity; Sezioni Primavera; Research-Formation.

125 The contribution is the result of cooperation between two authors. In particular, G. Moretti wrote paragraphs 1 and 4; B. Briceag wrote paragraphs 2 and 3. Translation by Antonio Lenzo.

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1. Introduction

Services for early childhood, alongside family environments, constitute the first formal educational context for preschool-aged children. In Italy, there has been a longstanding debate about the need to establish a unified, integrated system for education and instruction to provide high-quality services for children from birth until the sixth year of age. The Decree no. 65/2017, which established the integrated system for educational and instructional services for children aged 0-6, recognizes the importance of promoting educational continuity and identifies specific actions to achieve these goals. In particular, the decree refers to planning activities, preparing joint educational activities for children in the 0-3 and 3-6 age ranges, and ensuring a coordinated approach to formative interventions and professional development for educators.

A significant example in Italy that could inform the realization of the integrated system for the 0-6 age range is the ‘Sezioni Primavera’ (SP), i.e. ‘Spring Sections.’ The establishment of SPs has allowed for the experimentation with innovative didactic activities and the consolidation of effective professional practices aimed at integrating educational actions in the 0-3 age range with those in the 3-6 age range (Bondioli & Savio, 2012). To intentionally promote continuity at a systemic level (Penn, 2011; Bondioli & Savio, 2018; Zaninelli, 2018), it is necessary to utilize specific educational tools. The choice and flexible use of these tools, considering contextual features, should enable children in SPs and associated schools to have meaningful experiences that support personal growth, skill development, and relationships with peers and adults.

Considering nationwide and international research, we believe that targeted interventions in reading and early acquaintance with books, particularly through shared reading aloud practices (Lane & Wright, 2007; Cunningham & Zibulsky, 2011), can significantly contribute to promoting educational continuity between nurseries, ‘Spring Sections,’ and kindergartens. These interventions enable new synergies between different educational contexts (Freschi, 2008; Catarsi, 2011). The relevance of these interventions depends not on their duration but on their quality, specifically how they are planned to ensure positive experiences for child-readers in sharing books and stories. The quality of children’s experiences is related to the questions educators ask during dialogic reading and the depth and openness of the relationships supported. Early and recurring exposure to activities involving books

(printed or digital), conducted collaboratively, helps construct a positive image of reading as both an individual activity and a pleasurable social practice shared with adults and children.

Reading aloud, pursued by one or more adults for young children, promotes emotional literacy, develops written text decoding skills, and positively influences *reading enjoyment* (Bettelheim & Zelan, 1982; Valentino Merletti, 1996; Cardarello, 2004; Bortnem, 2008; Moretti, 2017; Morini, 2017). It is essential for language development, vocabulary enrichment, and encouraging imagination and fantasy (Cunningham & Zibulsky, 2011; International Literacy Association, 2018). Children between 0 and 6 do not yet master written text decoding skills and thus require adult mediators. Therefore, it is crucial to plan reading practices that encourage a positive relationship with writing and books, whether printed or digital, from early childhood. Books should be familiar objects to touch, page through, read from, and ‘pretend’ to read; an interlocutor for active listening and comprehension (Chiantera, 1989).

In building a positive relationship with writing and books, both family environments and formal and informal educational contexts play a role. The quality of the mediating relationship established by adults with children should be the central focus if we aim to encourage continuity between play and learning environments, such as sharing stories and books in different formats (e.g., picture books, illustrated stories, play-books, or illustrated and interactive e-books).

‘Shared reading aloud’ practices, with their many features, especially the opportunity to introduce children to shared reading practices that build a community of readers, are valuable educational tools for promoting educational continuity between ‘Spring Sections’ and kindergartens (‘Scuola dell’infanzia’). These practices (Cardarello, 2004; Bortnem, 2008; Moretti, 2017; Morini, 2017) qualify early childhood curricula and promote educational continuity by planning experiences where children of different ages and educational services share the same story or book. Shared reading paths foster social, cognitive, and emotional development through peer interactions in a playful and trusting environment. By ‘educational tool,’ we mean ‘instruments’ and ‘technologies’ that mobilize resources and activate intentional processes to achieve specific objectives (Agamben, 2005; Moretti & Giuliani, 2016; Giuliani, 2019).

For children aged 0-6, reading aloud is an effective strategy for inviting them to read, as it is essential to establish an affective relationship with books from the earliest years. The desire to imitate adults in childhood can promote reading motivation. Reading aloud extends attention spans and stimulates the construction of mental images (Valentino Merletti, 1996; Cardarello, 2004). In educational environments, children find themselves in peer groups where story-sharing experiences can be introduced through reading.

This contribution presents the results of the ‘Lettura condivisa ad alta voce’ (i.e. Shared Reading Aloud) path, realized as part of a broader Research-Formation (R-F) project by the ‘Laboratorio di Didattica e Valutazione degli Apprendimenti e degli Atteggiamenti’ at the Department of Education, Roma Tre University, in conjunction with the ‘Ufficio Scolastico Regionale (USR) per il Lazio’ (the Regional Education Agency). The R-F plan (Magnoler, 2012; Moretti et al., 2017; Asquini, 2018) was designed to promote a reflective, critical, and aware approach to formative activities among participating educators and teachers, as well as to encourage active engagement and mutual learning among peers.

2. Objectives and Structure of the ‘Shared Reading Aloud’ Path

The ‘Shared Reading Aloud’ path, realized in the context of the broader Research-Formation project, engaged educators and teachers at ‘Sezioni Primavera’ (SP) and kindergartens to which the SPs are linked, hosting children between 24 and 36 months of age. The educational institutions pledged to encourage continuity in educational paths between 0 and 6 years of age (art.1, L. 296/2006, art. 2, comma 3b del D.lgs. 65/2017).

The main goals of the co-planning and implementation of the path were:

- Observing how ‘shared reading aloud’ with children between 2 and 6 encourages peer relations;
- Observing how ‘shared reading aloud’ with children between 2 and 6 encourages continuity between ‘Sezioni Primavera’ and kindergarten;
- Verifying the sustainability of specific educational tools, especially ‘shared reading’, with the aim of encouraging children’s growth and the qualification of learning processes.

The R-F and the ‘shared reading aloud’ path as a whole involved 24 educational operators, mainly educators or teachers in kindergartens working in ‘Spring Sections’ or collaborating with them. All participants, belonging to 11 educational institutions, showed interest in adhering to a research and formation path in a blended mode over 18 hours. Educators and teachers involved in the shared reading path are responsible for different professional roles: eleven were educators in ‘Spring Sections’, eight were pedagogical coordinators and six were teachers in kindergartens linked to ‘Sezioni Primavera’. Participants were operating in four out of five Provinces in Lazio Region (Frosinone, Latina, Roma e Viterbo) within state institutions, private institutions or institutions in convention with the local administration. The ‘Sezioni Primavera’ involved on average numbered a minimum of 10 children and a maximum of 20. Overall, the children involved were 168.

The Research-Formation path involved in-person meetings for microplanning and online activities in which various related themes were examined, as well as the observation and evaluation of educational activities in the context of the integrated system for the 0-6 age group, and in which specific educational tools were introduced, e.g. ‘shared reading aloud’.

The pursuit of in-person microplanning activities went as follows:

- A plenary session, where the tool was introduced, various reading aloud practices were discussed and agreed upon and coherent observation systems were selected.
- A small-group session, in which the ‘Sezioni Primavera’ educators and the teachers in kindergarten co-designed the activities to be pursued with the children and developed data recording instruments.

In the plenary session, ample space was given to the knowledge-base for different shared reading practices. In particular, emphasis was put on the need to plan for specific spaces and times to pursue ‘shared reading aloud’ with both ‘Spring Section’ and kindergarten children. It was further agreed that the already-read books should be made available for the students to reread and explore directly and autonomously. During the in-person meeting, teachers and educators were confronted on the subject of how to plan for joint experiences that would allow children to engage with peers in thinking about the book they have read and listened to and that would encourage dialogue on shared reading in a climate of play and mutual trust. In the formation and professional development small-group session, educator/teacher couples picked the books, keeping in mind certain quality standards; they defined how to go about pursuing the ‘shared reading aloud’ path in each Section and they predisposed observation tools with the supervision of the research group at Roma Tre University. Over discussion, the hypothesis of offering the children a shared reading experience of a text in digital format was considered. The immediate accessibility of printed books in the Sections with which the

operators were involved prompted them to begin the activity with printed books, nonetheless without barring the use of digital formats in further developments.

3. ‘Shared Reading Aloud’ in Early Childhood Services

‘Shared Reading Aloud’ (Cardarello, 2004; Bortnem, 2008; Moretti, 2017; Morini, 2017), as described in paragraph 1, was identified as a useful tool to qualify a formative curriculum aimed at early childhood.

The contribution presents the findings from the ‘Shared Reading Aloud’ path as pursued during the 2018/2019 school year, with *Mary Poppins* ‘Sezione Primavera’, active within a private comprehensive school in the Latina province. During the small-group work session, the educator-teacher couple, supported by the research group from Roma Tre University, discussed ways to set up an environment that would allow ‘Sezione Primavera’ and kindergarten children to establish mutual relations and to recognize each other as subjects belonging to the same readerly community.

In designing the ‘Shared reading aloud’ educational tool, the educator-teacher couple at *Mary Poppins* Spring Section took into account the theoretical model proposed by the research group at Roma Tre University, which included several focal points accompanied by operative indications, in regards to:

The design of the educational setting, that is the setup of a specific space in the Section or within the school library devoted to reading in order to promote concentration, story-listening and the exploration and manipulation of the book as an object, as well as to allow the Primavera children to bond in couples or groups of three with the children from kindergarten, in order to enter into a relation with them and recognize themselves as members of the same group.

The identification of books as objects or high-quality reading formats (albums, illustrated stories, game-books or high-quality e-books, so as to develop interest in reading and listening;

The choice of the ‘shared reading aloud’ strategy, so as to acquaint children with active listening, with the assumption of selected roles and with the participation in dialogical reading experiences;

The identification and realization of artefacts, identifying products or realizing artefacts that would make the different phases of the shared activity explicit for the children, as well as markers for the same readerly community (e.g., the use of badges or pins);

The manner of conducting ‘shared reading aloud’ activities, in order to contribute to the beginning of significant reading paths that could promote *reading enjoyment*, to develop active listening skills and to encourage active exploration of the book as object;

The planning of a concluding phase in the sharing and discussion path, aimed both at stimulating reflective skills beginning with reading-listening of a shared text, and at developing verbalization abilities, also with simple forms, the subjects and actions found in the shared story.

Keeping these points in mind, the educator-teacher couple produced a micro-project which focused on the ‘shared reading aloud’ practice. The project’s relevant aspect consisted in the development of a path aimed at engaging children from both the ‘Spring Section’ and kindergarten by relying on a specific setting within the Section, customized to the goals of the reading practice. Table 1 shows the different application phases in the microproject for *Piccolo blu e piccolo giallo* picture book by Leo Lionni (1959), indicating the actions pursued by the educators and by the teachers and those asked of the participating students.

Activity phases	Actions to be developed
1. Activity explanation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educator (Sezione Primavera) and Teacher (Kindergarten) - The educator reminds children of the shared reading space’s function. - The educator gathers all children together and informs them that a new activity will begin shortly, involving kindergarteners. - Kindergarteners welcome Sezione Primavera children, show them around and explain the function of the reading corner.
2. Know your place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The educator and teacher set up the environment and materials to facilitate shared reading: the book, color paper sheets and background music. - Children sit comfortably on the soft carpet and form pairs (Sezione Primavera + Kindergarten) in the reading space. - Kindergarteners give a yellow play-dough ball to Sezione Primavera children, while they keep a blue one for themselves; they make sure Primavera children are keeping the ball.
3. Shared Reading Aloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The educator and the teacher take turns reading the picture book <i>Piccolo blu e piccolo giallo</i> [i.e., <i>Little Blue and Little Yellow</i>, by Leo Lionni] - The educator and teacher display the colored paper sheets according to the story’s plot and enhance listening with audio cues (e.g., ring-a-ring-o-roses, sounds of children in a park). - The educator asks children to use the two play-dough balls to represent blue and yellow hugging.
4. Exploration and manipulation of the book as object	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The educator and teacher present the class with materials. Using two copies of the book, they allow for manipulation in turns with groups of six children. - Teachers guide the children in exploring and manipulating the book as an object.
5. Dialogued rereading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The educator rereads the story as a dialogue, introducing points for discussion and asking questions such as, ‘What color is it? What does it do? Where will it go now?’ The

	<p>educator repeats what the children say and encourages responses.</p> <p>- The teacher invites children to express their appreciation of the day's reading through dialogue and specific questions.</p>
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Table 1. The microproject relevant to 'Shared Reading Aloud'.

In the context of the Research-Formation path, 'Shared Reading Aloud' was monitored through participant observation. This approach allowed educators and teachers to actively engage in the activities, effectively 'living within the research situation' (Luciano & Salerni, 2002, p. 176). The workgroup, comprised of educational personnel for childhood services, developed specific instruments for observing the children's activities. Under the supervision of the research group from Roma Tre University, an observation grid was designed. This grid aimed to record behaviors exhibited by the Spring Section and kindergarten children, as well as by the teachers, during the 'Shared Reading Aloud' sessions. The behaviors were noted using a four-point Likert scale.

The educator and teacher took turns practicing peer observation and used the observation grid. Table 2 displays the observation grid for the 'Shared Reading Aloud' experience conducted at the Mary Poppins Spring Section in Latina, including annotations made by the workgroup.

Phase 2 – Know your place				
The educator/teacher:	OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A. Makes children help with tidying up	X			
B. Collaborates with the teacher group to set up materials	X			
C. Verbally assigns seats for each child.	X			
D. Collaborates with the teacher group to couple children.	X			
The children:	OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A. Move around/look at the teacher.	X			
B. Keep playing without paying attention.		X		
C. Follow the rule and form couples.	X			
Phase 3 – Reading aloud				
The educator/teacher:	OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A. Reads in different tones depending on context.	X			

B.	Collaborate and coherently align reading and backing soundtrack.	X			
C.	They take turns reading aloud.	X			
The children:		OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A.	Listen carefully.	X			
B.	They show interest in the book.	X			
C.	They show interest in the audio tracks.	X			
D.	They interact with each other. (Sezione Primavera and Kindergarten)	X			
Phase 4 – Exploring the book as object					
The teacher/educator		OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A.	Facilitates access to books.	X			
B.	Invites children to approach the books		X		
C.	Allows children to touch and observe books	X			
The children:		OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A.	Approach the reading space.	X			
B.	Start ‘exploring’ the books.	X			
C.	Show interest.		X		
D.	Remain indifferent.		X		
Phase 5 – Dialogical rereading					
The educator/teacher:		OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A.	Rereads the story asking relevant questions.	X			
B.	Take turns in dialogical rereading.	X			
C.	Answer children’s questions.	X			
The children:		OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
A.	Answer the educator’s questions.		X		
B.	Show interest by asking questions.	X			
C.	Interact with one another making observations.	X			

Table 2. Observation grid for Shared Reading Aloud

In conclusion to these activities, the educational personnel relied on observation results to self-evaluate, discussing strengths and weaknesses in the micro-project for ‘Shared Reading Aloud.’ Analysis of the recorded data shows good participation by the children in the *Mary Poppins* Spring Section in Latina. Indeed, in all four phases of the shared reading activity, the ‘often’ indicator recurs: children often become interested in the book and its contents, often show interest in the space devoted to reading, and often explore and manipulate the books. From the grid, it also appears that educational staff engaged positively: they often involve the children in tidying the materials, invite children to explore and manipulate books, and answer children's questions. Specifically, in the *Mary Poppins* Spring Section in Latina, the ‘rarely’ and ‘never’ indicators were not used.

The Research-Formation path also involved discussion between educational personnel and the research group at Roma Tre University regarding the actual sustainability and effectiveness of introducing the ‘Shared Reading Aloud’ tool as a resource for promoting continuity between ‘Spring Sections’ and kindergartens. The shared micro-project and the grid setup in a collaborative mode (both between educators and teachers and between them and the research group) allowed for the tool to be used within the SP in the agreed-upon times and manners.

The educational personnel of the *Mary Poppins* Spring Section were invited to express their considerations on the different phases that characterized the tool’s introduction. Their feedback confirms the importance of continuing to reflect on the ways of co-designing high-quality educational paths aimed at children between 0 and 6 years of age. The introduction of the ‘Shared Reading Aloud’ tool was deemed especially effective in developing educational continuity in childhood services (Table 3).

	OFTEN	SOMETIMES	RARELY	NEVER
Shared planning with colleagues	X			
Introduction of the tool during class	X			
Monitoring and observation of activities		X		
Elaboration and analysis of recorded data	X			

Evaluation and reflection for re-planning	X			
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Table 3. Perception of educational personnel (Mary Poppins Sezione Primavera) on the sustainability of the Shared Reading Aloud project.

The results obtained through participant observation and discussions between educational personnel and the research group about the phases of the micro-project confirm that the tool was effectively conducted and managed by the educator and teacher. Both reported a very positive perception of their project, analysis, and reflection skills for the purposes of re-planning. The educator and teacher emphasized how their previous personal experiences with reading aloud to young children played a decisive role. Reflection on these past experiences, enhanced and revisited in the context of the Research-Formation, contributed to the consolidation and development of engagement skills in children of various age groups through shared reading practices.

Final Remarks and Future Perspectives

The results obtained from the path within the broader context of the Research-Formation project confirm the effectiveness of ‘shared reading aloud’ in promoting both the enjoyment of story-listening and exploring reading, as well as educational continuity and a sense of community belonging. Specifically, children between the ages of two and six were encouraged to establish peer relationships and were stimulated to actively participate in the educational activity (Penn, 2011; Bondioli & Savio, 2012, 2018; Zaninelli, 2018). The direct engagement of ‘Sezione Primavera’ educators and kindergarten teachers highlighted that co-designing activities, when conducted through confrontation and collaboration, can be an effective strategy for promoting educational continuity in childhood services. Educators and teachers verified the tool's sustainability and effectiveness in its introduction. Sustainability is also supported by the co-designing activity and professional knowledge sharing.

Overall, ‘Shared Reading Aloud’ proves to be an effective tool for acquainting children in the 0-6 age group with printed writing and the book as an object, fostering curiosity and attention dynamics that positively affect the development of positive feelings towards books in both the short- and long-term (Mantovani, 1989; Cardarello, 2004; Lane & Wright, 2007; Cunningham & Zibulsky, 2011). The inquiry also suggests that activities should be carefully planned to introduce

children to albums, illustrated stories, or interactive e-books, which might otherwise seem less accessible or harder to comprehend if engaged with individually.

From a methodological perspective, the choice of the R-F (Magnoler, 2012; Moretti et al., 2017; Asquini, 2018) proved to be functional in achieving the initially planned goals. This strategy allowed for more active engagement of participants and the development of a systemic, reflective, and self-aware approach in both SP educators and kindergarten teachers. Discussions with university experts throughout the R-F process, and peer dialogue, especially during the co-design and contextualization of educational curricula, contributed to consolidating didactic skills and developing critical abilities in participants.

Future developments for the R-F might focus on educational continuity between shared reading activities pursued within educational services and those led in the family, to enhance parents' direct engagement.

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Augmented Reading, Reading Pals and the Role of School Libraries,¹²⁸ by Gino Roncaglia¹²⁹

Abstract

The paper examines the connection between reading promotion practices in schools and the new digital ecosystem, based as a starting point on the experiences of two different European Erasmus + projects: ‘The Living Book’ and ‘ReadTwinning’. The project ‘The Living Book’ (2016-2019) was based on the concept of augmented reading, a reader-oriented strategy of systematic and competent connection between reading a book and using online resources and contents, with the aim to improve both the text comprehension and the quality of the reading experience. The ‘ReadTwinning’ project (2019-2022), which has recently started, is based on the idea of reading pals, who are connected each other through shared interests and an online platform. The methodological guidelines of both projects assign a central role to school libraries, considered as the best environment to promote both augmented reading (primarily through reading groups oriented to the participants’ interests) and the identification of ‘reading friends’ (reading pals) who share specific interests and books that are most relevant to them.

Keywords: augmented reading; social reading; reading group; school library.

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Promoting School-Age Reading

In this paper I will briefly present the Erasmus+ *ReadTwinning* project¹³⁰. The project was launched in autumn 2019, and I am in charge of it behalf of the Forum del Libro, lead partner of the initiative.

Alongside the Book Forum, the project sees the participation of six other European partners: three educational institutions, the Scoala Gimnaziala ‘Constantin Parfene’¹³¹, Romania, the Agrupamento de Escolas de Vila Nova de Paiva¹³², Portugal, and the Dimotiko Scholeio Makedonitissas 3 – Stylianou Lena¹³³, Cyprus; the English firm Gryd¹³⁴, specialized in platforms and tools for e-learning and education; the European University Cyprus¹³⁵; the Italian NGO ‘ProgettoMondo Mlal’¹³⁶.

Most of the partners had previously collaborated in another Erasmus + project, ‘The Living Book’, which ended in 2019. The two projects, although independent, move on a common ground: that of promoting reading in school age (and more specifically in the range between 9 and 15 years of age). In both cases, moreover, the attention focuses on reading promotion strategies that:

- start from the personal interests of the girls and boys involved, promoting reading strictly related to those interests, rather than based on top-down reading indications;
- use network tools to accompany the reading activity, connect it organically to potentially useful network resources, and stimulate participation and motivation;
- pay specific attention to the creation of reading groups;
- consider the school library as a privileged location and at the same time a fundamental resource for the planned reading activities;
- focus in particular on reading books and therefore on the role of the book-form - considered as essential for the development

¹³⁰ Reference website: <http://readtwinning.eu> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10.54).

¹³¹ <https://www.scoala3cparfenevaslui.ro/re.do?cmd=mainPage> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10.54).

¹³² <https://escolasdevnpaiva.pt/> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10.54).

¹³³ Δημοτικό Σχολείο Μακεδονίτισσας ξ – Στυλιανού Λένα, <http://dim-makedonitissa3-lef.schools.ac.cy/> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10.54).

¹³⁴ <https://gryd.com/> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10.54).

¹³⁵ <http://cerides.euc.ac.cy/> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10.54).

¹³⁶ <https://www.progettomondomlal.org/> (last visit: 18/12/2020, h 10.54).

of skills oriented to the selection, understanding, evaluation, production of complex information content, narrative or argumentative - while being easily adaptable also to use other types of complex information resources, including audio or video content.

Features of ‘ReadTwinning’

The specific strategies proposed (which can be easily integrated) differentiate the two projects: while ‘The Living Book’ focused on the idea of augmented or enriched reading, providing methodological indications and functional tools for deepening the books that were read, through the selection and organized collection of relevant content found on the net (thus operating on the idea of an expansion of the traditional notion of intertextuality, made possible by the interaction between written textuality and the network ecosystem), ‘ReadTwinning’ focuses on the idea of encouraging the connection between two or more ‘reader-partners’ (or ‘book pals’) with common interests, engaged in the contemporary reading of the same book. The focus of the new project is therefore mini-reading groups, consisting of a minimum of two and a maximum of four-five people and called ‘tandem’ in the terminology adopted by the guidelines. The project aims at providing methodological indications for:

- building ‘tandems’ by linking girls and boys with close interests; this operation can take place through interest survey questionnaires (the guidelines offer some models that can be used for this purpose) and/or through the interest profiling tools that will be made available through the platform;
- facilitating the selection of books to read, through suggestions provided by thematic experts (‘gurus’, in the terminology adopted by the guidelines) recruited from school librarians, teachers and parents participating in the project (who will detect their specific skills, favoring the creation of a shared database). Consistent with the methodological assumptions adopted by the project, the final choice of the book to be read is in any case always made by the tandem;
- providing tandems, through the creation of a special platform, with on-line tools that help motivate the participants and enhance their ‘parallel’ reading activity, through the construction of the tandem’s reading journal (including each participant’s

personal space, too), the organized collection of shared contents linked to the book read (by connecting in this way to the idea of augmented reading explored by the previous project), the definition of reading ‘challenges’ both within the tandem and in conjunction with other tandems;

- providing tandems with a friendly and safe online environment where to compare, share and discuss the reading activities carried out, through an interaction capable of involving multiple tandems and multiple participants.

Changes in Progress and Prospects

The project works, started in the first transnational meeting,¹³⁷ were obviously affected almost immediately by the COVID-19 emergency. However, the partners agreed to consider the situation determined by the emergency, and in particular the forced closures of schools in all of the participating Countries, as a challenge to be faced positively, by developing and proposing reading activities consistent with the project goals and achievable also from home or remotely. It was in fact considered that the creation of small thematic reading groups - manageable both in the presence within families, and remotely through network tools - was also a possible response to the need for keeping on training activities during the lockdown period.

Given that the health emergency occurred at a very early stage of activities and the on-line platform was not yet available, more traditional questionnaires for surveying interests were developed, as well as specific indications and suggestions for the creation of small reading groups within families (particularly indicated in the case of girls and boys in the age group between 9 and 11 years).

A first summary of the ReadTwinning methodology was then prepared, articulated in a seven-point FAQs structure, that can be also used in a remote working context. This document, in the original English version, is included in the appendix to this paper; it should be noted that the final version of the guidelines will be much more articulated, and may partially modify the indications provided in the first version of the FAQs.

¹³⁷ The ‘kick-off meeting’ was held in Rome, November 21-23, 2019, at the Polo Didattico (Teaching Hub) of the Department of Education, Roma Tre University.

The second transnational meeting (forcibly online) of the Project, scheduled for October 2020, constitutes an opportunity for an initial assessment of the experiences made during the lockdown by the partner schools, and will coincide with the release of the first version of the guidelines, and with the start of the online platform construction.

Appendix

FAQ - Preliminary suggestions for ReadTwinning Activities

1. What is ReadTwinning?

ReadTwinning is a European Erasmus+ Project promoting interest-based reading by **matchmaking two ‘reading pals’ (or a *small group of reading pals*) in order to read the same book together, with the help of an on-line platform** which provides tools specifically designed to connect the reading pals and facilitate shared reading. The target of the project is constituted by 9-15-year-old students.

2. How should the ReadTwinning reading pals be matched?

In the final version of the project, **the on-line platform will include specific tools to facilitate the matchmaking** by means of a (gamified) set of questions and activities aimed to identify users’ interests, reading habits, preferred books. In this preliminary stage, school partners are encouraged to **involve teachers and students in the matchmaking process, asking them to help match students with similar interests**. Since the project aims to connect students from different classes, schools and countries, it is recommended (albeit not required) even in the preliminary stages to **match students from different classes**. In the preliminary stages, it is suggested to **work mainly with couples of reading pals, but to experiment also small mixed groups (i.e. composed of teachers, students, family members)** that meet a few times on the basis of previous affinities or of practical factors (neighboring homes, compatible schedules, etc.). The main purpose of these groups is to prepare, accompany and verify reading activities at school and outside.

Small groups are also recommended in order to better understand if and how well the tools provided and the ReadTwinning methodology work. Within the project, each couple or small group of reading pals connected in order to read the same book is called a **‘reading tandem’**.

3. How should the books be chosen?

In the final version of the project, **the platform will provide book suggestions based both on the users' profiles and interests, and on recommendations by 'topic gurus'**, advanced users of the platform (teachers, parents, students) with a specific competence on the topic which constitutes the reading tandem's specific interest. In the preliminary stages of the project, partners are encouraged to **involve students, teachers and parents in preparing a list of topics of interest (being as specific as possible), in enrolling topic gurus and in collecting topic-specific book recommendations from the topic gurus**. The platform will include asap tools to facilitate this preliminary step, which will be useful in order to collect a first, shared set of data. **It is very important, however, that the final choice of the book to be read is left to the reading tandem, and not imposed upon it.**

4. Which tools are available to the ReadTwinning reading tandem?

In the final version of the project, each reading tandem will be able to use tandem-oriented social reading tools, such as a **shared reading diary**, a **shared board for collecting reading-related content** (both validated on-line content and user-generated content), a **message system**, and (through embedding) a **web-conference system** for book-related discussions and activities. In the preliminary stages of the project, partners (especially school partners) are encouraged to **experiment with their own templates for the reading diary**, and to share them with the other partners through the project mailing-list and Google Drive: Suggestions and proposals on the template of the reading diary (especially if proposed by reading tandems) will be of invaluable help in order to finalize a common template and to implement it in the platform. In the preliminary stages of the project, available on-line tools such as The Living Library platform, Padlet, etc. can be used as shared board. Please, share experiences and evaluations on the tools used!

5. How does the ReadTwinning reading tandem work? What are the reading challenges?

At the beginning of its activity, each reading tandem could define a set of goals which, taken together, constitute its '**reading challenge**'. What is their deadline for completing the book? Which kind of shared activities (such as: create a book trailer; create a given number of

Instagram stories describing the reading habits, discoveries, activities of the tandem; create a playlist of music related to the book, or to be listened to while reading it; create book-related bookmarks, ...) are expected? Each reading tandem can also define its own **reading stages** (such as: completing the first section of the book) and **reading strategies** as part of the reading challenges. In the final version of the platform, it will be possible to include the reading (sub)challenges in the template of the reading diary, and **the platform will award badges (both for the tandem and for its individual participants) when the reading (sub)challenges are completed.** In the preliminary stages of the project, teachers and topic gurus will award challenge-specific rewards to the tandems and their participants. Each reading tandem can challenge other reading tandems through shared **multi-tandem reading challenges.**

6. How to use augmented/enhanced reading in the ReadTwinning reading activities?

Reading tandems are encouraged to use the Living Book approach based on augmented/enhanced reading, **including in the shared reading activities and in the reading challenges also activities based on enhanced reading.** The Living Library platform can be also used within the activities of reading tandems.

7. Connecting ReadTwinning reading tandems

While each reading tandem has its own specific, book-related and topic-related challenges and reading activities, the ReadTwinning methodology should also provide spaces and times for **common activities involving different reading tandems**, such as: sharing with other tandems the challenge results, implementing multi-tandem challenges and rewards, common meetings and discussions.

Chapter 3.4

E-Lending of e-Books and Other Digital Resources in Italian School Libraries: Statistics and Experiences, by Paola Pala¹³⁸

Abstract

The current situation of school libraries in Italy is examined and a reflection is carried on the serious structural and financial deficits and on the territorial differences, highlighted by the data relating to heritage, service, increase in collections, staff, space and workstations available in school libraries, although these are present in 89% of schools (AIE, 2019).

The conversion to digital lending services can represent an opportunity to enhance the school libraries already effectively functioning on the national territory and at the same time offer a public reading service and access to new titles to schools with no library or with libraries, whose services need to be enhanced. This is demonstrated by the increase in digital loans and MLOL users, which has more than quintupled in the period under review (24 February-24 March 2020).

Keywords: digital resources; e-book; e-lending; school libraries.

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Introduction

Today, a school library is the basic tool to develop in children and teenagers the habit and the pleasure of reading, and, at the same time, promoting the integration between their school curriculum and the new teaching fields in order to acquire the so called ‘key competences’, including informational, digital and multimedia ones.

However, whereas school libraries are playing an even important role in other European Countries and in the United States, in the field of teaching and education to media as well as in the development for the competences necessary to lifelong learning, Italian school libraries are virtually not existing, poorly financed and their basic role for the promotion of reading among children and teenagers can hardly be recognized.

The Current Situation of Italian school libraries

According to a recent survey carried out by AIE (Italian Publishers Association) on school libraries in our country and published in 2019 (Peresson, 2019) about 89% of the surveyed schools have a library. However, the data concerning their facilities, services, acquisitions, staff, spaces and available stations reveal very serious structural and financial limits as well as territorial heterogeneity that make it clear how school libraries quite often consist of a small locker located in a corridor or a small room without resources and very limited opening times.

The amount invested by schools in their libraries – less than 6 million euro a year – affects less than 0,001% of the total expenses. The average collection in Italian school library consists of about 3000 volumes, just 0,4% of the titles on the market. Paradoxically this is the age in which the highest percentage of Italian readers can be detected,¹³⁹ and, therefore, the efforts and the investments to promote the habit and the pleasure of reading should be focused on such age.

In the end, despite various appeals and initiatives by AIB (Italian Libraries Association) and MIUR (Ministry of Culture), there is no specific legislation about librarians and libraries in Italian schools. Until 2012 libraries in schools were run by teachers deemed unsuitable for teaching, mostly for health reasons. Since 2012 a Decree law limits the

¹³⁹ ‘Over 50% of readers in the population between 11 and 19 years. Most readers in the age between 11 and 14 years (53,5%).’ ISTAT lettura in Italia National Statistics.

use of teachers unsuitable for teaching, transferring them to administrative and technical offices. As a consequence, libraries have been closed down or at best, opening times have been drastically limited and services are run by volunteers.

It's now clear that campaigns promoting reading in general are not sufficient and there is still a serious need of strategies and specific communication systems to intercept and satisfy all users' needs and requests. In this respect some remarkable and commendable initiatives and projects for children have taken shape.¹⁴⁰ But, as it has been quite often pointed out (Cantatore & Marquardt, 2015) any initiative to promote books and reading proves ineffective unless there is a good infrastructure, necessary to support it.

Toward the Digital School Library Services

As things stand, it is quite evident that MLOL and digital loan could be a good opportunity, if not the only one, to bridge the gap of the lack of Italian school libraries in order to provide a real 'infrastructure for reading' to Italian students.

Building a digital school library guarantee services to a much larger number of users, widening the space to be used by abolishing territorial limits well as creating collections for the students to have access to best sellers and new publications. By automating some processes such as loan procedures, the acquisitions of bibliographic metadata and – in the case of some services such as the Digital Interlibrary Loan – the development of collections, MLOL solves in the twinkling of an eye lots of problems depending on lack of staff extending the access to the contents well beyond the space of the school library as well as its opening time.

Students and teachers, after getting the credentials to access the site, can enjoy the loan of digital resources any time and from any location. Therefore, digital resources can be used not only in the library, but also in classrooms, in laboratories and at home, through any fixed or mobile device. In this way MLOL widens and diversifies the perimeter of the libraries, pushing it well beyond the physical space where books and other documents are confined, making real a sort of 'wildly circulated/distributed library' accessible anywhere by connected teachers and students. This is a fundamental aspect because students,

¹⁴⁰ For example, *Nati per Leggere, InVitra*.

in this way, can feel themselves fully inserted into a digital context overcoming the conflict between the hyperlinked world outside their school and the digitally isolated space inside, which is perceived as a thing of the past (Dominici, 2015). In addition to that, MLOL is going to become a valid support for teaching in classrooms, that is a real 'Infrastructure for teaching', not just for reading. Teachers can connect their PC/tablet to their LIM (Interactive Multimedia Blackboard) and use MLOL together with the whole class to read a passage of a book, comment on an article or translate it from a foreign newspaper, browsing the museum databases and select multimedia images and files that can be used (in compliance with present copyright laws) to build conceptual maps, for instance.

In the last month, then, the restrictions on movements due to the Corona Virus epidemic (SARS-CoV-2) and the consequent closure of schools have brought to light the potential that was previously little evident - perhaps because perceived as less necessary - of digital libraries. A secondary side effect of this emergency is in fact that on e-book library loans: between February 24 and March 24 the e-book loans on MLOL increased by 104% compared to the same period in 2019: in average times it would have been expected an increase of about 20% from one year to the next.

New users have also increased, i.e. people who have started using the service recently: about 100 thousand - a number equal to that of single annual users of a large library - more than last year. According to MLOL data for past years, the number of new users normally increases from 15 to 20% a year: in the last month an increase of 20 thousand new users would have been expected; because of the current situation they have been five times as much.

Final Remarks

As evidenced by Angelo Bardini, the coordinator of 'Biblòh!', the network of territorial and digital school libraries which has the particularity of collect schools spread all across the Italian peninsula, there are many schools that with total closure discovered their potential and in this moment they are taking action to allow their students and teachers to access the contents of the digital library (De Carli, 2020). Such schools are providing their users with a useful tool - mostly in the current crisis - to deepen determined subjects of school or personal interest, or simply for spending a few hours in the company of a good

read. Definitely, these are services and practices that could also be adopted by other schools, guaranteeing a widespread access to information service and reading.

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Chapter 3.5

The Reader's Ghost. Books and Libraries in Teen's Imagination, by Beatrice Eleuteri¹⁴¹

Abstract

A crooked being, too thin or too fat (anyway unfit because, of course, he doesn't practice any kind of sport), bent on a desk, in the darkness, alone, only with the fainting light of a lamp to illuminate the yellowy pages he's losing his sight on (therefore he usually wears bottle bottom thick glasses). He doesn't have any friends, or girlfriend/boyfriend, wears out of fashion clothes and has already lost any kind of contact with reality, so that when he speaks nobody understands. He's the reader, or better, the image of him that emerged from the words of 100 teenagers involved in a 2018's survey on reading motivation. Who would ever want to end like this, especially during adolescence, when our body bursts of energy and has to be shown, pumped, shaken, used in all the possible ways? The question is, of course, rhetorical. We often believe that a child, yet a young adult, only needs to be taught how to read and write for us to feel in the right to reproach him if he doesn't actually do it or if he's not really good at it. Well, knowing how to read is not enough to motivate reading. Reading is an 'habitus', a suit that could fit tight, or loose, that we need to try on a couple of times in the dressing room before choosing to buy it. The school library is a guesthouse, a place in which kids, especially culturally deprived ones, must feel safe and welcome to talk about stories, experiences, opinions. A forum to meet books of course, but also readers. A workshop meant to sew our personal reader's habitus, rejuvenating it from its old mousy image and preparing it for us to grow inside it.

Keywords: adolescent; teenager; reading; reading behaviour; reading promotion.

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A Premise: Teenagers and Reading

First of all, let us dispel a myth, according to which teenagers do not read.

Kids' increased cognitive and linguistic competence¹⁴² and their need for experiences (physical or mediated) makes them ideal readers. Reading satisfies their need for competence, epistemic curiosity and empathy; gives them a private space in which they can build themselves, find shelter, get scared, lost and found, to experiment safely from the inauspicious consequences they could get run over in the real world, always looking for a balance between two cultural primary instincts: social attraction and anthropopoiesis.

We know they read and that the age between 11 and 14 years old is the one, in Italy, that collects the greater number of readers at all¹⁴³.

But teenagers do not only read books: they exchange text messages, interpret memes, listen, watch and sometimes create videos, music, art, follow personal blogs, get involved in fan fictions; a carousel of multiple editions and remediation¹⁴⁴ declined in different shadows and modes, all answering to the same primordial need: to tell and listen to stories.

Between all modalities, kids use to look for themselves and what they need, the book (in paper or bits) still has all the space it needs to insert itself between virtual and physical life, both to consider as real learning and experiencing environments, getting through the web of digital friendships and material feelings, managing, today more than ever, to satisfy the search for new worlds, new ideas and characters to see ourselves into, fiction in which we can find the truth.

A teenager can seek in the book what he looks for in movies, music and videogames: stories, characters, adventure companions. But what happens in a specific cultural behaviour, reading, and its representatives, readers, books and libraries, come to be socially and psychologically associated with disadvantage, boredom, elitism and judged as old and laughable?

It's in the age range immediately following the one we examined before that a slow but continuous decrease of readers starts and, as adulthood

¹⁴² On adolescence neuronal discoveries: Bainbridge (2009) and Steinberg (2014).

¹⁴³ ISTAT. *Produzione e lettura di libri in Italia*, Anni 2010-2018.

¹⁴⁴ On the remediation concept: Bolter & Grusin (1999).

approaches, against any advice, the wave of non-readers gets bigger and higher.

Something happens, between 13 and 19, which defines the relation future adults have with the book and qualitative surveys made to analyse motivational factors behind adults and teens' reading behaviours seem to bring out a serious anthropological and sociological phenomenon that undermines reading motivation: the rise of an aversion, a growing negative connotation of the book and the reader which brings into a deconstruction of literary imaginary and destruction of the social thrust to read and pursue information.

The Reader's Ghost

A prejudice arises when a single experience is generalized into a law, easily spreadable because it is superficial (Aneddotic fallacy). It can become popular and be used as a base for an argument (bandwagon fallacy), bringing more and more people to believe it without further proof, following the 'common judging' bias. In the end, id a prejudice is about an activity or a group of identifiable people, it can become a stereotype: a character image which the category gets associated to.

The stereotype of the reader that has been created in the centuries is pitiless: a crooked being, too thin or too fat (anyway unfit because, of course, he doesn't practice any kind of sport), bent on a desk, in the darkness, alone, only with the fainting light of a lamp to illuminate the yellowy pages he's losing his sight on (therefore he usually wears bottle bottom thick glasses). He doesn't have any friends, or girlfriend/boyfriend, wears out of fashion clothes and has already lost any kind of contact with reality, so that when he speaks nobody understands¹⁴⁵.

Studying how and why this image of the reader emerged in the years certainly needs a serious and deep study. Could it be because of the unforgettable descriptions by which we met Italian greater writers, first of all, the sad and lonely Giacomo Leopardi? Could it be because maybe, in the deep, there's something real in this neorealistic portrait? Anyway, it is a fact that since silence and lonely reading started to appear the reader has been looked at with more and more suspicion,

¹⁴⁵ The description is a patchwork reconstruction of motivation revealed by a 2018's survey, described further on in this paper.

because of the subversive boost hidden in the act of reading for ourselves¹⁴⁶.

Who would ever want to end like this, especially during adolescence, when looks and sociability are very important tools for identity building? The question is, of course, rhetorical.

Surveys and investigation often underrate the importance that prejudice can have in conditioning what people think to be wanting or wanting to be. The image that we have of a certain habitus¹⁴⁷, or object, infects the way we sense and approach it.

In May 2018 an experimental survey¹⁴⁸ has taken place in Rome to test a new method of qualitative research funded on debate sessions. Aim of the project was to investigate what could hide behind the declaration of boredom and indifference that ISTAT reported for non-readers between 11 and 19 years old¹⁴⁹ and what brought teen readers to insist in their behaviour instead.

Using focus groups, interviews and extracting prepositions from the debates records, it has been possible to divide arguments in defence or against reading in four macro-categories: Logistic (which reunites practical arguments such as reading devices' choice), Preferences (which reunites superficial arguments, not so different from the ones reported by larger quantitative surveys), Psychological and Cognitive Experience. Those final two, which rose as particularly relevant and in need of further research, reunite deeper and sometimes unusual arguments, such as semantic perception of reading and books, their social value and the stress/pleasure degree experienced in reading.

¹⁴⁶ Among others: Cavallo & Chartier (2009).

¹⁴⁷ As in Pierre Bourdieu's conception.

¹⁴⁸ A complete report for the survey is available at the library of the 'Scuola di Specializzazione in Beni Archivistici e Librari', Sapienza University: Eleuteri (A.Y.2017/2018).

¹⁴⁹ Bologna (2018).

Figure 1. Total of the arguments in defence (PRO) and against (CONTRO, i.e., contra) reading per classroom in the 2018's survey. (Eleuteri, A.Y. 2017/2018).

The survey, which is just a first step to deeper analyse reading motivation, suggests how, in the reading field as in others, boredom and apparent apathy are often masks for anxiety and fear for negative judgment, especially related to the value system promoted by the sociocultural environment, which changes with the individual sense of belonging to his group.

Figure 2. Macro-categories of arguments in defence of reading per classroom in 2018's survey. (Eleuteri, A.Y. 2017/2018). Legenda: Blue=Preferenze; Orange=Psychological Experience; Grey=Cognitive Experience; Yellow=Logistics.

The lack of correct learning strategies could comport to take more time and excessive effort compared to the offered benefits and that could lead to considering reading a too tiring and obsolete activity, preferring other kinds of leisure and sources of information. At the same time, the internalization of beliefs regarding our reading ability or the impossibility to change it (a wrong concept of intelligence, for example), may be related to a bad experience such public reading that determines the association between reading and a state of anxiety, could lead to a low perception of competence and fear for failure, then adopt strategies of self-defence that could range from simple avoidance to mockery or even aggressions due to a sense of inferiority¹⁵⁰.

Figure 3. Macro-categories of arguments against reading per classroom in 2018's survey. (Eleuteri, A.A. 2017/2018). Legenda: Blue=Preferenze; Orange=Psychological Experience; Grey=Cognitive Experience; Yellow=Logistics.

The attractiveness of a determined behaviour, such as reading, is therefore defined by a whole series of rational, relational, emotional and sociological factors, that produce the social and affective value of the experience, and only, at last, its usability, considering it all one with the object book/text.

¹⁵⁰ A good explanation of motivation styles can be found in: De Beni & Moè (2000).

While we concentrate (rightly) on defining the best school methodologies to improve reading and writing learning strategies and to avoid a wrong perception of competence in pupils, we also often underrate, or worse endorse, the acritical internalization of society's value systems. That leads kids to experiment with an inescapable feeling of detachment between institutional paternalism ('reading is good') and real social convenience ('reading is for losers').

Speaking through the kids' mouths, the beautiful, angelic and reassuring voices of 'Nati per leggere' and 'Libriamoci'¹⁵¹ are replaced by the resigned and reproaching tones of many fathers and mothers¹⁵², fundamental parts of a society that decided that reading is useless, tiring and unproductive, that firmly believes in the Camel Theory¹⁵³, except then contradict itself, without too much conviction, when it says to its kids that they have to study, putting them in front of an important choice for their growth: adapt to the 'common judging' or defy the stereotype and distinguish?

This phenomenon, that we could call the 'Epiphany of the non-reader', is stronger and more visible as weaker and sporadic was his reading behaviour, especially if matched to the difficulties previously described.

It is useful to remind, in fact, that the range of age between 11 and 14 certainly collects the greater number of readers in comparison with the others, but they are mostly (understandably) weak readers, which we have the mission to transform into strong ones by making reading evolve from fascination to love, from a way to satisfy the teacher to a passion to satisfy their desires for discovery and wonder. It is a sensitive operation, aimed at preserving the act of reading for pleasure and

¹⁵¹ Cepell's (Italian Centre for the Book and Reading) virtuous campaigns, such as others promoted by other national and local agencies, sure aim to sensitize about reading issues but seem to be too much concentrated on childhood, not reaching with success adolescence thorny but fundamental age. A new (2019) and we hope fruitful initiative in this direction is the Cepell's project *Io leggo con te* (I read with you) which, likewise Hamelin's *Xanadu*, puts in place a good amount of means to involve teens, teachers, families and professionals in a participated and multimedia channel.

¹⁵² From 2018's survey data (soon to be compared with further investigations) emerges a process of transformation of reading and readers' image more and more influenced by adult's value systems and qualitative references appropriation, especially (but not only) in specific contexts subject to low education rates and early school leaving.

¹⁵³ The thought according to which, before beginning our life journey, we receive all the mental feeding we need to deal with the entire track, so the adult, once passed his school years, doesn't need reading and studying anymore. Ranganathan (2010).

letting it grow, avoiding the danger of turning every book into torture and pass the idea that, after childhood, reading's only use is to memorize and summarize, that they only have to get through school age to have the freedom to never ever have to open a book anymore. This duty is not simple, and it gets harder and harder as adulthood approaches.

Reading and Value Systems: Whom Do We Learn not to Read From

To specify that book derivative anxiety, reading negative connotation as illusion and, most of all, the social stigma¹⁵⁴ observed by the 2018 survey are unreleased motivations (as for their being taken over because they probably have been existing for a long time), not yet included in big quantitative surveys like ISTAT's, is useful to understand how much these de-motivational factors are underestimated or partly misunderstood, hidden behind more bombastic (even if also important) investigations on literacy and reading comprehension¹⁵⁵ or purchasing and reading statistics¹⁵⁶.

To analyse non-readers motivation is not only a matter of how many and what kind of information people can obtain and store, but also a purpose to investigate why the same people don't recognize the search for knowledge as worthy anymore. Knowledge intended as continuous learning, mental flexibility and communication awareness; as a base for a healthy, conscious and participated society.

It is useless to spend ourselves in right tirades about the importance of education from the top of a long academic career if education itself is not perceived as desirable from the ones who have to do the effort to obtain it. In the living present we assist to a constant cultural debasement which often manifests itself as a depreciation of the symbolic value of knowledge, once considered a prestigious tool for freedom and emancipation.

Many people think, wrongly, that technology can compensate for the loss of alphabetical skills and abilities, at least when it comes to profit and individual success, while it should be used to enhance their benefits

¹⁵⁴ Three of the major motivation categories emerged from 2018's survey.

¹⁵⁵ For example, the famous OECD's PISA, PIRLS e PIAAC. For a deeper analysis of the phenomenon a reading by Eleuteri (2019) could be interesting.

¹⁵⁶ ISTAT's report on publishing and reading rates comes out every year.

instead. Also, the loss of one of the only recognized reinforcement for capitalistic societies, the economic recognition of education, seems to impoverish not only the value of studying, research and personal intellectual growth but also the professional recognition of academic degrees and qualifications.

This whole value system spreads through people, impregnates them and from family and individuals gets to new generations, suggesting that to read and to create imaginary worlds are not useful activities, unless someone pays you enough to do it. In the same way homework's only purpose is to get good grades, as work's one will only be to buy things. If you cheat, copy and paste or make someone else do it for you or study for it is not important, the aim is to obtain a prize, a golden star, a bonus or some kind of social recognition, delegating our own motivation to grow and improve to external factors.

To underestimate the psychological and social elements that sustain the act of reading has often brought to put in place not really effective solutions, based on secondary factors like books' cost¹⁵⁷, tech races¹⁵⁸ or paternalistic campaigns, without considering the elephant in the room: the desperate need for reading promotion actions based on solid and deep studies and common guidelines, carried on by professional and competent figures enabled to operate with the right tools and from the right places, schools and libraries.

Long term actions that should get over the simple concept of target and have the power to spread on the entire society, acting on the main factor of choice: the relationship we are enabled to experiment with reading¹⁵⁹.

The Reader through the Looking Glass

The voices of teen readers (especially girls) who took part to the survey, together with wonderful and personal stories about how reading helped them to overcome difficult moments in their lives and enthusiastic

¹⁵⁷ Lastly, the 2020 Reading Act dedicates a large amount of space to regulating book prices and establishing prizes and medals, but very little to addressing the extremely needed common regulations for natural reading promotion agencies and agents: libraries and librarians.

¹⁵⁸ Economic resources are often allocated to encourage innovation, but most of all, they are used to purchase new technologies. Very little is spent on educating and refreshing promoters' competencies to truly enhance the quality of services.

¹⁵⁹ Chambers (2001; 2015).

description of imaginary worlds they explored thank to books, agree on the same single point: to start loving reading you need to read, you need to find the right story which will transfigure a pile of paper, glue or bits in a flow experience, pure pleasure. But how can we meet the right book?

It is extremely difficult to let a non-reader understand the sensation a text can arouse. Differently from a lot of other enjoyable and addictive activities, reading doesn't show itself out of the act of doing it, it doesn't have the spectacular nature of ancient great speeches anymore, it is an intimate and silent process which needs time and dedication.

All the activities that can be done together, participating in collective rites¹⁶⁰, are amplified and even just watching someone doing it can boost a desire to be part of it, motivating us to try it personally thank to the action of mirror neurons¹⁶¹, the basis of our empathic and learning through imitation abilities.

But what does seeing someone reading induces in a non-reader observer? What we can see from the outside is a human being concentrated on a device (a mobile, a book or an e-reader), not particularly expressive, deaf to external inputs because soaked in a flow experience, in a world far from phenomenal experience.

In front of this image, the non-reader has to make a choice: strive to understand why that simple activity seems to catch so much of the reader's attention, taking up the challenge with a book himself or, especially if he has been signed with negative experiences associated to the act of reading (frustration, struggle, no external encouragements), simply judge the reader and his cryptic behaviour bringing him back to the friendless egghead stereotype.

They could be driven to try the activity if the reader is an authoritative or influential figure, and that's the reason why it is fundamental to see parents, teachers, partners and personally important people reading, especially if considered successful people. More real people (with a life, a job, a family, interests) we see reading and speaking about reading, weaker the antisocial stereotype of the reader will become, blurrier the image of the library rat, the ivory tower intellectual will get.

The right parallelism we can do is with music. I challenge anybody to find a teenager who doesn't possess a listening device, from basic

¹⁶⁰ According to Max Weber's meaning of it.

¹⁶¹ Rizzolatti & Sinigaglia (2006).

mobile functionalities to bigger and bulky boomboxes. We see them everywhere: on the streets, in the underground, lying down on beds and sofas, concentrated and a little frowning while listening to some pop, rock, indie or trap music. But yet, none of their peers would call them misfits, pointing them out like weirdos, friendless or out of the world. Why should reading be different?

Schools, libraries, school libraries

We often believe that a child, yet a young adult, only needs to be taught how to read and write for us to feel in the right to reproach him if he doesn't actually do it or if he's not really good at it. Well, knowing how to read is not enough to motivate reading.

A teenager coming from a bookless home experiment stories and texts at school and there he will move his first steps towards the literary world. At school, as may be among his family he will meet people who will tell him that reading is useful, it is healthy, it is a duty. Someone will maybe try to explain to him that it can be a pleasure as well, but if he'll never see them read he will unlikely believe it for a long time.

And that's the moment when the institution who should have the mission to make up to the disadvantages origins of the pupils coming from culturally deprived families becomes the setting in which the good book transforms into the bad one and little novice readers, who used to get excited when the teacher read them out loud, turn into teenagers with an indifferent, if not even hostile, conception of the text and its manifestations.

Then there's the library, public or scholastic.

Many kids enter a library for the first time only to find a place to study, dragged in by friends or desperately looking for a quiet place to do homework without distractions. The frequent lack of appropriate facilities and services for teenagers¹⁶² and the intolerance many librarians demonstrate to this kind of users (which they consider as 'inapposite users') won't help to unbuild the idea of library they had in their mind, coming from common judgment and movies: an old and

¹⁶² The name itself 'children's literature' or 'kids room' leaves interpretation space to what could be the real age group addressed to. In most Italian libraries we can often recognize a special room destined to younger readers and their activities, but teens usually only have maybe a shelf or two in which we can find different materials (mostly comics, graphic novels and educational novels), but without a real common standard.

silent book depository, a giant study-room inhabited by elderly and hysterical university students, ruled by librarian too often on the edge of misanthropy¹⁶³.

Italian librarians needed ages to start realizing there was an urge to increase opening hours, to create academic courses for future librarians, to accept the idea that the library is an active cultural aid linked with local agencies, that a library can be a noisy and living place, full of activities and readings out loud (not just for children!), an exchanging centre where knowledge and discovery wonders from books to mouths.

We are still working on it but it's tough to eradicate the elitist, boring and old image created among the centuries on libraries and librarians. In short, next to the reader's ghost there's an entire haunted mansion, a solid stereotype that is really difficult to dispel, especially taking a look to Italian libraries presence and services data¹⁶⁴.

To avoid handing down this prejudice to the next generations and to create a complete and continuous promotional pattern it becomes fundamental to highlight and empower the presence and action of living and active school libraries, connected to public ones.

Reading is a habitus that can be fitting tight or loose, that we need to try on before purchase. School libraries are those ideal environments where kids, even ones coming from culturally deprived contexts, must feel safe to talk about stories, experiences, opinions. An agorà meant to meet books, of course, but, above all, readers; a boutique where they can learn how to sew their reading habits, rejuvenating it from its mousy imagine, so they can grow inside it.

This mission implies comfortable reading spaces, big rooms, various and up to date collection, the presence of supporting teachers, good technologies and fast connections.

Teenagers, in the library, of course, need inputs, a choice of titles that can suit them, but, more than a shelf to contain them, they need a comfortable space to read them, talk about them, share them. A space where there is no silence rule, where they can feel free to read whatever they want without being judged for it, where, after searching the

¹⁶³ This small view still come from 2018 survey's data.

¹⁶⁴ In 2014 Italy had 6.042 public libraries (for about 8000 municipalities), with an average of 34 seats and 2,5 pc stations, only 54% of them has a wi-fi connection and the average opening time is of 24 hours a week (only 40% opens during the weekend) and 32% of the staff composed by (not always trained) volunteers. Cepell (2016).

shelves, they can shelter and experiment, knowing that that place is meant for them and not just to handle out vocabularies or show off the school's most prestigious collection.

Finally, the library needs to be managed by a competent and trained figure, the school librarian, which unfortunately doesn't exist in Italy.

This lack created huge qualitative gaps because it leaves school libraries management and initiatives (where they actually exist) completely to the willingness and the unpredictable critical spirit of the invested professor (often, but fortunately not always, reluctant to ask for qualified librarians' help).

To get out of this carelessness spiral, to allow libraries to smash their stereotype and do their irreplaceable job of coordination and promotion, especially helping schools to counteract the 'epiphany effect', it is required to define and clench the crucial importance of all the professionals who take part in this action.

Between saying and doing. To paint over the imaginary

Every high school professor who cares for his professional role, every parent who thinks about his or her children's future and every citizen who worries about new generations educational fate should pretend that they spend their learning years under the guidance of professionals specifically trained to educate them, stimulate their creativity and help them to develop self-control strategies and self-motivation, each playing a specific role: librarians, teachers or educators.

Everyone who wants to call himself a promotor needs three main traits: preparation, motivation and openness.

To motivate reading presupposes to know the field, the methods and promotional strategies but, most of all, to be motivated ourselves, to feed our passion to allow it to spread more and deeper, to embody the image of the reader we try to promote against the common judgment of futility of culture, study, effort.

Also, reading needs time, not only to read books but primarily to choose them, browse them, talk about them. We can't pretend that kids will read at home if we don't dedicate time and space to do that at school. That's why it is necessary to make a common effort towards the definition of a flexible program, which will allow educators and promoters to give time to the vital uselessness of art, that gives space to the kids' proposals, their desiderata, talking about them in class,

creating testimonials of the specific book, at first, and of reading itself in the future.

There are no particular themes that need to be selected or chosen, maybe the styles, communication modes from different authors, in a process that can lead the unripe reader from a simple and linear style to a more complex and stimulating poetic, never sacrificing contents, quality, experiences and the emotional charge. Without censures, with enough time, the most precious gift we can offer them.

Establishing an hour for reading every day should be a common practice, at any age and in every context, especially educative ones. An hour (more!) to dedicate to all kinds of readings: comics, illustrations, novels, non-fiction, without obligations made of essays, desks and spelling; a time reserved for readers, in which teachers and educators first should read what they like and experiment different story-telling.

Openness, at last: first to new technologies, which are not that new after all, to analyse them, discompose them and then incorporate them in school and library practices, to use new forms of communication critically, following new paths but never abandoning the millenary tradition of the written word.

But openness also means transdisciplinary and cooperation between professionals, a habit that we should increase to allow institutions to develop long term educational plans and carry on projects based on more than just one person's enthusiasm. Reading is a transversal ability and it crosses sciences, art, even sports. So why confining it to literature classes? Reading is not a subject among the others, it is a tool with thousands of facets, purposes and uses, which from schools and libraries can expand into houses, gardens, chats and groups. In fact, we need to keep in mind how deep is the influence of peers in defining a teenager's conception of pleasure and aesthetics. It is the most important magnetic pole for kids (and not only for them), as well as the more difficult field for a promoter to influence.

Dialogues, also intergenerational, reading circles, social reading, are all places of a social dimension of reading that often stays unnoticed to non-readers, which feeds the famous antisocial prejudice. Meetings and exchange moments are needed to give birth and action to Daniel Pennac's passeurs¹⁶⁵, knowledge 'riders' and curiosity farmers.

¹⁶⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e_tOoQIwLMc (last consultation: 17/03/2020, h 16.00).

Final Remarks

Teachers, librarians and parents have then the very sensitive task to build the path towards contexts and activities which carry a high probability of meeting same age readers, acting from the start as role models and encouraging kids to gather and attend theatres, libraries, cinemas and reading, writing and artistic clubs, not forcing them or imposing it to them just as ‘right’ and ‘healthy’ activities.

The encounter with the written word can be very slow and difficult. The important thing is to set the stage for the right book, the right story, so that people, not only kids, can make the revolutionary choice to declare themselves as readers, destroying stereotypes.

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Session 4

Enhancing the School Library and its Profession:

The Role of Institutions and Associations

Chapter 4

Qualifying School Libraries to Improve Learning: Network Planning between Schools, Institutions, Associations and Local Contexts¹⁶⁶, by Giovanni Moretti¹⁶⁷

Abstract

The present contribution examines the accounts presented during the Fourth Session of the IFLA Midyear Meeting, identifying recurring elements for discussion. The aim is to contribute to the envisioning of the roles and functions that school libraries can fulfil in the future, as we confront both the current health crisis and emerging educational challenges.

Keywords: school libraries; infrastructure sharing; information literacy; health crisis; educational project.

¹⁶⁶ Translation by Antonio Lenzo.

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Introduction

The state of affairs for Italian school libraries is uneven. Numerous forward-thinking initiatives, with short-, middle-, and long-term projects integrating their actions with the contents of the educational three-year plan, coexist with many others struggling to maintain continuous and coherent activity.

The former have successfully navigated the health crisis by reconfiguring their assets to become versatile laboratory spaces for both class groups and hosting school institutions. They welcome more heterogeneous student groups on rotating shifts with flexibility, allowing them to pursue reading, study, and research activities.

The latter, undoubtedly the most critically endangered, encounter further obstacles to their functioning, risking closure and repurposing as additional classrooms or quarantine spaces. The health crisis's need to identify new spaces for continued educational activities while ensuring student safety through physical distancing may lead many schools to convert library spaces.

In Italy, the weak project and cultural identity of these spaces and services are not accidental but structural, due to the lack of emphasis on promoting books, reading, and the library system at a national level. After a meagre decade for both projects and funding, the 'Biblioteche nelle scuole' project began in 2004. Later, in 2010, the *Bibliorete21* project (<http://www.bibliorete21.it>) aimed specifically at building a reference meta-network to connect local school library networks and support their development. The author of the present contribution, a member of the technical-scientific committee for the project, noted the ministerial disinterest in financing and supporting the initiative.

Currently, the strategic significance of *Azione #24* of the *Piano Nazionale Scuola Digitale* (PNSD, 2015), i.e. *Digital School National Plan*, should be noted. It allows for the acquisition of digital content through access contracts for digital lending platforms, providing students and teachers access to digital books and newspapers. This action is crucial because, despite Law No. 107/2015 (the so-called 'Buona scuola', Good School) not considering reading or school libraries, and despite previous digital schooling initiatives not addressing the possible role of school libraries, the PNSD identified them as 'environments for access to information and documentary resources, for information literacy, for the promotion of reading and writing, characterized by the meeting of conventional and digital information' (Roncaglia, 2016, p.13).

Azione #24 of the PNSD also recognized the importance of promoting reading and developing skills for producing and comprehending complex informational content. This implies valuing the school library's role in information research strategies, promoting information literacy, and countering the spread of fake news (Falcinelli, Nini & Bianchi, 2018). Schools and school libraries can incentivize active citizenship by developing digital skills related to finding relevant information, identifying search engine keywords, distinguishing reliable from unreliable information, and participating in the 'development of a culture of verification' (Trincherò, 2015, p. 49). Recent studies also highlight better performance in Italian and Mathematics by students attending schools with well-equipped, well-functioning school libraries (e.g., Marzoli & Papa, 2019).

The New Educational Challenges

The Italian school system is called upon to face new, epochal educational challenges; nonetheless, it has long been a passive witness to a deep contradiction. Declining reading habits are also the 'paradoxical result of bookish schooling (90% of Italians does not know a library; over 20% does not own a single book; about a third never reads books)' (Manacorda, 1992, p. 251). So-called traditional didactic is still prevalent; in its pursuit, it relies on the affordances of textbooks, which are not the same for all students. The traditional approach is unable to instill any love of reading or reading comprehension skills, and it represents one of the main obstacles for the achievement of these goals.

Scholastic autonomy, though a significant achievement which should allow school communities to make choices aimed at qualifying their curricula and at improving school organization with reference to local contexts, has not received the necessary legislative or monetary support for the promotion of books and readings except in isolated instances.

Though several documents and contributions reference school libraries as a 'bridge' between the school and the families, between schools and local territory, between cultures and generations (e.g. Moretti, 2010; Indicazioni nazionali per il curricolo della scuola dell'infanzia e del primo ciclo di istruzione, 2012; Marquardt, 2016), many school libraries are ignored or underused even by the teachers who should be promoting them. Many library-hosting schools tend to underuse them or to consider them marginal assets, scarcely influencing the quality of

the school curriculum or the students' learning process. It follows that, in Italy, during a health crisis, school libraries risk closure more urgently than elsewhere, also because they never received such formal legal status to ensure stable, solid activity through time.

The seriousness of the situation does not only involve school libraries, but it also extends to the entire library system. For example, over the last eight years, in the 46 state libraries depending on the Ministry of Culture, library staff decreased by 33%. This negative record was also noted by well-known journalist Stella, who asks whether 'a country like ours can face a world undergoing such quick shifts only temporarily interrupted by Covid-19 with a university, school, library system which has been performing ever worse for years?' (2020, p. 23). Truly, Stella's question is urgent because the health crisis is actually accelerating change, with unforeseen outcomes that ought to be expertly handled, not simply inflicted upon us, so as to positively reconfigure conventional working and educational, cultural and informational service access activities.

The Future of School Libraries

It is therefore urgent to revisit the global debate on the future of school libraries, but it is even more necessary to examine it with an awareness that it should evolve alongside the current discussions on the restructuring of the school system, on its new organization and its new functions, in the perspective of building a society of inclusive knowledge, at once responsible, democratic and global. We know, in fact, that it is not so much about planning a simple restructuring of educational practices, nor about pledging to uphold restructured processes for good practice diffusion. Rather, it is a matter of systemically identifying the essential aspects of educational work and of recognizing the crucial elements that could contribute, at a middle and low level, to the qualification of the necessary learning processes for the new generations.

The questions we need to ask should help us understand how complex organizations like schools and, more generally, formal educational environments could succeed in setting up the necessary conditions to motivate children and young adults to the acquisition of culture in a reasoned, systematic way, which is thought to be necessary for awareness in pursuit of one's role as an active and responsible citizen. Useful questions help us comprehend if and how formal educational

contexts could effectively guarantee that the learning process for ‘citizenship’ skills could be pursued safely, that is in respect of a plurality of sources and points of view, in full awareness of the scientific method and of the problematic, open meaning of doing science, with the aim of exercising and developing dialogical skills and critical thinking.

While, on the one hand, intergenerational exchange and knowledge transmission take place effectively, consisting in the acquisition of guiding principles in an ever more complex and dynamic world, on the other hand there is a broad portion of society, globally, who distrusts competence, knowledge, and who even distrusts the validity of scientific thought. It is therefore the case that the breadth of knowledge and information potentially accessible to everyone does not constitute, for many, a personal or collective resource, but a hardly ignorable factor of anxiety and insecurity.

The relation many people establish with knowledge is often fragmentary, decontextualized, impressionistic, scarcely thought through, manipulative. For many, even in their formative years, what matters most is not focused study or deep inquiry, but momentary impressions, what they hear through the grapevine, and the enjoyment of content and information which are immediately reshared on digital platforms.

In many such informal contexts, ‘cognitive patience’, connected to the need for verification, confrontation, argumentation and deep inquiry, is not at all practiced because it is not mandated by the different forms of informational exchange. While quick thinking is appreciated, slow cognition and the investigation of an object’s or document’s signification are considered to be unfitting behaviors that represent an obstacle to virtual contact. Such a situation, moreover, in Italy as well as elsewhere, has contributed to the spread of populism and of contempt for argumentative thinking and for critical and scientific approaches.

The educational challenges and urgencies before us prompt us not to limit ourselves to formulating questions on the specific role for school libraries in the school of the future. This role, in fact, not only is not guaranteed to exist, but it could not be there at all, especially if we fail to highlight the reasons for supporting the development of libraries in a school context. These reasons are the same that prompt schools to redefine their role and future prestige: the opportunity to lend attention

to structured knowledge, to sources, to the exercise of critical thinking based on the use of different types of public documents, which have passed peer reviewing and which are potentially democratically accessible to all.

Our main issue, therefore, is the amplification of the school debate and the enrichment of discussion with arguments aimed at reinforcing the importance of the ‘culture of which libraries and librarians are bearers’, as a generative thought, useful to face, with greater rigor and force, the new challenges for the future formation of the youth facing formative systems and school institutions.

How and Why to Improve School Libraries

Interventions effected during the fourth session at the IFLA International convention, titled ‘Migliorare la biblioteca scolastica e le sue figure professionali: il ruolo delle istituzioni e delle associazioni’, help us identify some of the reasons that should prompt us to act to defend the interinstitutional practices, experiences and relations which have so far fuelled the ‘culture of which libraries and librarians are bearers’ in Italy and internationally. The fourth session, hosted virtually, involved six international contributions.

Irina Nehme (Director of the School Library at Hölty-Gymnasium, Wunsdorf, Germany, and member of IFLA School Libraries Section) spoke on the subject ‘Quo vadis, school library?’, remembering that in Germany the so-called ‘digital treaty for Schools 2019-2024’ generated hopes and expectations within schools and other actors in the field of education, such as public libraries and multimedia educational facilitators in public libraries. In this process, however, some issues arose which deserve attentive consideration: the separation between culture and instruction as competence fields, which caused serious clashes between municipal libraries and internal school libraries; instructional federalism, which means there is no national library system and, therefore, no hierarchy for infrastructure beyond the Länder that could guarantee the strategic development of school libraries; the need to identify different school library models, not reducible to the Frankfurt model, the most widespread in Germany, involving a public library with centralized competence on local school libraries; the possibility of opening up school libraries to external users, usually opposed by both schools and local administration.

The contribution by Svetlana Chazova (International Gymnasium of the Skolkovo Innovation Centre - Moscow state Institute of culture, Russia) titled 'Through library services, equal opportunities for different school communities', reflected on the school library system in the Russian Federation. In Russia, the school library network is handled by regional institutes for the development of education. At a methodological level, assistance and consultancy for school library administration is offered through the Russian Academy for Education Information Centre. The contribution noted inequalities in the quality of regional centre administration and highlighted efforts made by the school library communities and by federal and local departments in facing various administrative, technological and relational obstacles. Overall, several core features of a modern school library are found to be necessary, such as: offering increased opportunities to develop school subject knowledge; developing intellectual and creative abilities in students; helping to choose methods and strategies for research; improving knowledge of Russian and global languages and cultures.

Irina Nehme (Germany) and Svetlana Chazova (Russia) also presented a joint contribution titled 'International collaboration to support multicultural and interreligious dialogue through the school library'. The 'Cartonera' project by the IFLA Group Relendial excited interest in two school librarians from different countries, Germany and Russia, prompting them to develop a joint project to support multicultural and interreligious dialogue through the respective school libraries. Online collaboration and cultural contact beyond national boundaries emerge once again as a useful base to support international dialogue and to encourage discussion and pacific comprehension across countries.

Eva Pasqualini (School principal, Istituto Comprensivo 'Bruno Munari', Roma), Elisabetta Valente (Parent Association President - Artù, Roma) e Alessia Gargano (doctoral researcher at Università degli Studi Roma Tre), through the contribution 'Cultura della condivisione in rete: scuola, associazioni e territorio', presented results for online activities carried out in the context of the Eastern Metropolitan Roman area. The participating school library network collaborates locally with parent associations, publishers, illustrators, writers, arts didactic experts and Roma Tre University, in the context of book, image and reading promotion. The experience also confirms the need to promote systematic initiatives engaging multiple actors that would promote reading by means of planning and realizing thematic activities, ritualized and recurrent through time. Some aspects characterizing the

network's initiatives include: the engagement of students and families, the itinerant exhibition for illustrators, the day of shared reading, the poetry prize, the organization of laboratories with experts and an emphasis on the relation between action, formation and research.

Giovanna Micaglio (Responsabile Scuola, Studi e Università e Referente Bibliopoint at Istituzione Biblioteche di Roma Capitale) presented 'L'esperienza BiblioPoint di Roma', which 'Biblioteche di Roma' (the public library system in Roma Capitale) has been developing for around twenty years in collaboration with schools of several levels to the end of providing integrated access to reading, information and cultural events to both school and local communities. The experience is a positive example of collaboration between municipal libraries and school libraries, serving as local BiblioPoints, with the aim of promoting reading.

Finally, the fourth session devoted particular emphasis to the 'dispositions for the promotion and support of reading' (L. n.° 15, 13 Feb. 2020¹⁶⁸). The norm deals specifically with article 5 on reading at school and school libraries, envisioning both the institutionalization of school library networks and the identification of a reference figure with specific skills for each network.

The interventions contributed to the fourth session at the IFLA international convention show some elements of continuity of serious relevance, hereby listed:

- a) Schools and school libraries benefit from the possibility to act in a collaborative and cooperative way in the context of an integrated educational and cultural system with access to open and shared infrastructures.
- b) Schools and school libraries can act more effectively in collaboration and cooperation if they have organizational autonomy and if they have the possibility to apply different service models that would take into account features and needs in a local context.
- c) School curricula can benefit from a synergy with school libraries, especially in developing *information literacy*, promoting the comprehension of complex digital texts, supporting 'cognitive patience' and focusing students on themes such as interreligious dialogue, intergenerational and intercultural confrontation, art education, artistic beauty.

¹⁶⁸ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2020/03/10/20G00023/sg>

- d) Schools and school libraries can enrich and qualify their curricula if they act collaboratively and cooperatively with all interested parts (state and city libraries, local institutions, associations, experts, publishers, universities, etc.), with the aim of planning culturally secure initiatives, supported by open and stable partnerships and accompanied by monitoring and research actions (Moretti, 2017).
- e) Large cities and metropolitan areas represent the ideal context in which to experiment with and practice integration between schools, school libraries, city libraries and educational-cultural or recreational service, with the aim of planning for innovative and sustainable modes for infrastructure sharing as well as resources accessible to citizens without exclusion or limited access.
- f) The development of school libraries' roles and functions requires a specific legislation, dedicated to the promotion of books and reading, but it also implies a systemic vision which would allow for synergies, integration and infrastructural and resource sharing.

Increased emphasis on these aspects, in an Italian and international context, could help school libraries to overcome the so-called 'missing piece' syndrome (Marquardt, 2003) and to fully express their vocation as educational spaces balancing reading and research, aimed at promoting the enjoyment of reading, through literature and the use of digital sources and resources (Lombello Soffiato, 2009; 2017). In this sense, the so-called 'room of books' ought to be rethought as a reading and cultural space to be cared for with adequate internal communication and integration with school educational practice (Bignamini, 2006). The fourth session evidences that the improvement of school libraries and of their personnel involves careful planning, devoted organization and flexible administration.

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Chapter 4.1

Quo Vadis, School Library?, by Irina Nehme¹⁶⁹

Abstract

The national program ‘Digital Pact for Schools 2019 – 2024’ has generated hopes and incentives for schools and other educational stakeholders, including municipal libraries, in Germany. However, the separation between culture and education as distinct areas of competence has led to competition between municipal and school libraries. Additionally, federalism in education has resulted in the absence of a national school library system and a lack of infrastructure to support the strategic development of school libraries. Centralization, which consolidates infrastructure and future development, was highlighted when the most prestigious German Libraries award in 2018 was given to the School Libraries section of the Frankfurt Public Library, sending a political signal. The Frankfurt model, where the public library coordinates local school libraries, is the most common approach in Germany and has notable advantages. However, mandatory implementation of this model could pose existential challenges for school libraries by limiting their direct access to infrastructure, such as digital resource consortia. An alternative model could involve aligning school libraries with academic or special libraries instead of municipal ones. The pandemic has unexpectedly created opportunities for partnerships, allowing school libraries to integrate into the academic libraries section of the Librarians Association (BIB) and engage in various innovative projects and collaborations within and outside the school community. Under normal circumstances, such developments might not have occurred or been approved as quickly. Notably, an entire school library was dissolved in its old branch and reestablished in a new branch.

Keywords: school library models; public library; academic library, collaboration, advocacy.

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Introduction

The ongoing digitization process, started in the 2019/2020 school year, changed the landscape of school librarianship drastically. It is clearly noticeable in the annual statistics of 2019, to a threateningly alarming extent. While the school librarians were still busy reorienting and repositioning themselves in the face of these changes, the pandemic came and these challenges brought many unexpected opportunities. During the national lockdown in Germany in Spring 2020, all types of libraries were instructed to close. Yet, during the second current lockdown from November 2020 to

Figure 5 (left) and 2 (right). Clearing of books and, after whitewashing the library, relocation of the books.

January 2021, it is interesting to observe that those school libraries which consider themselves as branches of public libraries were forced to close like all public libraries did. However independent school libraries still function like university libraries do. Does the Protection against Infection Act (IfSG) leave out school libraries intentionally or do the school libraries ignore IfSG?

The confusing legal circumstances create a unique situation within the German librarianship when the school libraries seem to benefit from being under radar. The example of the independent school library at the Hölty-Gymnasium in Wunstorf demonstrates how the school librarians made use of the pandemic to further develop the library, their own professional skills and the opportunity for advocating school librarianship in Germany and abroad. Throughout the pandemic period, the four core concepts could be implemented as the best practice example in a condensed way: and quality of library space, digitalization, open library and teaching library.

Quality of Library Space: Cleaning and painting work, new media locations, studio, lighting improvement, Christmas tree, oasis

As part of the hygiene concept, the library removed certain furniture and is rearranged to be airier according to the current social distancing rules. This

temporary solution turns out to be very appealing to both the library team and the visitors. The cleaning staff, who continued to come to work every day during the shutdown, cleaned the library thoroughly, they particularly dusted the books. Such an operation took place eight years ago and is indeed urgently needed. All the curtains were washed and aired again after a long time. During the lockdown, a new floor plan was drawn for the library. The magazines, DVDs and audio books were rearranged to make them more accessible. Some urgent construction works were carried out. According to the current fire protection regulations, an additional door to the emergency exit was installed in the former classroom within the library. When the renovated library opened again after the first lock down, it was cleaner, safer, better organized and so more inviting. This former classroom was transformed later during the year into a studio. The professional equipment for the lighting, including the green screen, a tripod for web-cam with the holder for a tablet and another tripod for a microphone which enable professional photo, video and audio recordings. Alternatively, the room with enough seats for one class can also be used as a cinema. The library has been repainted for the first time since its opening in the Hölty-Gymnasium 32 years ago. After years of efforts, a ceiling spotlight was finally installed during the pandemic. The real three-meter tall Christmas tree was a highlight in Advent season of 2020. 10 children answered the call to decorate the tree and the library for Christmas. The decorated library with the magnificent Christmas tree formed a fairy-tale-like backdrop for the reading competition of the sixth graders and many other activities and projects during this Advent. The festively inviting atmosphere in the school library during the Advent season provided a little comfort to the pupils, helped them get away from the limitations and privations in the dreary time of the pandemic.

Figure 3. Christmas Tree 2020

Figure 4. A cosier environment after renovation.

The newly furnished oasis with a hammock and the Thai mat with a triangular reading pillow does not only ensure relaxing or exciting reading experience, but also serves as an invitation to dream about distant countries and upcoming adventures after the pandemic.

Digitization

The new button in our OPAC 'Digital' this year opened up the world of digital media offers to our library users: e-papers, e-books and e-audiobooks to download and films to stream.

Sora is a brand-new product from the American company Overdrive for German schools. Hölty-Gymnasium Wunstorf is the first German school that is testing this bundled digital media package as a pilot project in cooperation with the Reading Foundation. All school members and guests with a library card of the Hölty-Gymnasium can log in with the login data of their school libraries and immediately access over a thousand e-books and e-audiobooks on PCs and portables.

The launch of the license pilot project with the scientific publisher Friedrich-Verlag with access to the digital academic journals for all teachers, rather than just the Department Heads could not have come at a better time. The accessibility of digital magazines was particularly appreciated and praised by the teachers this year. As a result of this project, the library did not only receive new subscriptions to additional periodicals for teachers, which were requested and ordered by the departments, but also expanded its readership among the teaching staff.

Another innovative project was to introduce the digital product Filmfreund from the German company Filmwerte to the library. It is a novelty for this company to have won its first school library as a customer. As films, analysis and production play an increasingly important role in the classroom, there is great potential for the company to put a stronger focus on schools, regarding the product content and the licensing rights. The possibility for various users to watch filmic content at the same time, opens up undreamed-of possibilities for lessons, whether in Distance Learning or as homework in face-to-face lessons.

A lot of publicity was carried out for these products and they are widely adopted by our users. Never before has the school library staff been able to take part in so many advanced training courses as in 2020. The transfer of the advanced training courses to digital format makes it possible.

Understandably, there are some disadvantages with the webinars compared to the physical training courses, but the possibility alone is simply revolutionary, particularly for school libraries with very limited human resources.

Due to the close cooperation with those who are responsible for digitization in schools, coordinators, school assistants, IT department of the city of Wunstorf, working group network, the school library takes an active part in the digitization process and drives it forward in some areas. As a committed parent representative in the digitization working group of the neighboring school which my children attend, opportunity for cooperation between the two largest secondary schools in the city is opening up.

Open Library

Cooperation between the school library and the German National Library of Science and Technology (Technische Informationsbibliothek, hereafter: TIB), which is awarded as the Library of the Year 2020.

The cooperation of the school library with the scientific library TIB was an important experience. All academic libraries in Hanover and elsewhere in Lower Saxony canceled their guided tours and training courses at the beginning of this school year. Since the school librarian had anticipated this unpleasant scenario in advance, she took the following measures at the end of the last school year to enable access to academic literature for the high school students:

1. Webinar appointment
2. Training documents from TIB for on-site training in the school library
3. Institutional ID card for the school library, in order to guarantee the possibility of borrowing in the event of the complete closure of the TIB, which took place during the lockdown in April
4. Inter-library loan account in the GBV (Common Library Network), so that literature can also be ordered from other libraries via inter-library loan.

1. Unfortunately the webinar ‘Research on the Internet’ for the seminar courses of the 12th graders did not work out as we at Hölty’s had planned and hoped for. The technical requirements of this TIB webinar stated that it can only be carried out on PCs and not on portables, the number of participants is limited to approx. 70 participants.

At Hölty, there are 140 pupils who should attend this webinar. However, we could not get two webinar appointments high school coordinator and the school librarian decided to include the entire 140 pupils with the 50 PCs in the two PC rooms and with all iPads in other three locations in the school, in the hope that the digital infrastructure, which was improved in the library and in one wing of the school building in summer 2019, would be sufficient to support the webinar. Unfortunately, this hope has not been fulfilled.

The system was clearly overwhelmed by the fact that 140 pupils tried to dial in at the same time. A quick fix to project the webinar onto the screen with

only one device, each in the five different event rooms, has only rescued this event to a limited extent. In both PC rooms it functioned a little better than in the library and the two other classrooms, where the transmission via laptop and iPads was set up.

Just like us, the TIB carried out a crisis analysis after the unsuccessful event and informed us that the problem came probably from our side. For TIB, the award-winning 'Library of the Year 2020', it had successfully conducted dozens of webinars per year with other schools, such difficulties surfaced for the first time.

As a result of our analysis, we believe the only possibility of such a webinar is to offer it only for selected participants instead of the whole grade, as there is usually a maximum of two available dates in the TIB during the short period between the summer and autumn holidays and 'only' 60 existing LAN PC workstations are available at our school.

2. The training materials from the TIB, on the other hand, were very helpful and used extensively. They were adapted to the local conditions of the school library and supplemented with exercises with the own OPAC, the FIS Education specialist database and the GBV catalog. In this way, our pupils were taught with more knowledge and research skills that they had missed due to the cancellation of the on-site training in TIB.

The service of ordering and procuring scientific literature for pupils from the TIB with the school library's institutional ID was and will only be offered in the future to courses that have participated in the research training in the school library. It is to ensure that they have thus learned the bibliographical information correctly and completely to make the order, as well as to carry out the preliminary research in our OPAC.

As a result, a total of 73 books were ordered, for at least 60 of them, alternative and even more up-to-date titles could have been found in our school library, 3 of the ordered were available directly in our library, one of them even as a class set with 60 copies.

Overall, this service cost the library staff around 20 hours of working time and 80 km of distance to transport the books, but saved the individual pupils time and money. What is even more important is, during the pandemic, it only requires one person travelling to Hanover and back, instead of 140 people making the same trip. Whether this tested service would continue and be maintained depends on many factors.

The new free inter-library loan service has not yet been used by any user of the school library, but the first order for a DVD from the Garbsen City Library came last week. The desired DVD was sent right before the Christmas lock down.

Master of cooperation - the MediaLab

The foundation of the MediaLab Wunstorf exactly two years ago was based on cooperation between the libraries of the Hölty-Gymnasium, the Otto-Hahn-School, the media center of the Hanover region and the Reading Foundation. During the lockdown when the MediaLab, like many other facilities, had to pause, the supervisor of the MediaLab, Irina Nehme, took the opportunity to find new ways to gain partners for further development. Internally, the former intern, a trained computer scientist with media pedagogical experience with young people, and the social pedagogue of the school could be reached out as co-supervisors. During the lockdown, the social pedagogue who was in charge of the emergency care of children, came with the children to the library. He was inspired by the media-educational activities the school librarian showed him. After the lock down he continued his involvement in media-educational activities such as 'Reading in Motion', the escape game 'Lock Down Agents', quizzes with Kahoot and board games in the MediaLab.

The agreement with the cafeteria to supply the participants of the MediaLab with its freshly prepared but unsold snacks, serves both the idea of sustainability and the welcoming culture.

In the summer and autumn holidays, the MediaLab took a new route outside the school library and participated in the project 'Lern(I)räume' (Learning Rooms/Dreams) of the 'NetzWerk – Wunstorf', which took place on the premises of the IGS Wunstorf. In order to allow the participants from the IGS to visit the MediaLab in the future, the date has been moved to Fridays from 2:00 p.m. to 4:00 p.m. Thus, the contractually stipulated goal of the MediaLab to work across schools is fulfilled.

A new partnership is now being announced. A MediaLab participant from the Otto-Hahn-School brought in the brilliant idea when she expressed the desire to read aloud. Since the age and literary tastes of the current MediaLabs participants are very different from one another, the idea is revised to read for the kindergarten children instead of reading to each other.

St. Bonifatius day care centre is in our neighborhood and in the KOV (cooperation network for the promotion of special talents), which is currently coordinated by a Hölty teacher and school library fan (or friend) Lars Kreye, it is only natural for us to offer our reading services to this kindergarten. The director of the kindergarten immediately expressed her interest and willingness to cooperate, which will be discussed and organized in detail after the Christmas holidays.

All potentially interested story-tellers, whether in German or other native languages, are welcome to contact the school librarians and practice reading aloud during the Christmas holidays with suitable reading materials for children from 2 to 6 years of age. A crash course for reading aloud will be offered in advance for all interested, but perhaps even less experienced readers during the MediaLab appointments.

As a surprise, the children and youth center Bau-Hof e.V, an old partner in the reading club project, which we set up eight years ago, demonstrated interest in the MediaLab. The interfaces and potential cooperation options will be explored after the Christmas holidays.

Another partnership that is becoming increasingly important is the one with the Lower Saxony library headquarters. By participating in the 'Fake Hunters' training course, the simulation game of the same name for recognizing fake news is first tried out in the MediaLab and experience is gained before it should be integrated into the information skills training from 8th grade.

The MediaLab Wunstorf is also planning to apply for funding from the 'Neustart Kultur' program of the German Literature Fund to hold literary events such as author reading sessions next year.

In December, when the number of library visitors is always the highest, but this year the number of infected people has also skyrocketed, the library had to remain closed during the two major breaks. Instead, the library team took the media out to the users in the school yard and into the staff room. The school community responded with surprise, interest and gratitude.

A further project to open the school library for new experience is about providing the school community with an external yoga trainer, as a health project. The yoga trainer and the school librarian agreed that the library, in terms of its ambience and the mandate to preserve yoga as a World Heritage Site, is a more suitable place for yoga classes than a sports hall. After the pandemic, the project will be implemented.

A Teaching Library

Inquiry-based learning is the starting point, the basis and the educational goal in the school library of the Hölty-Gymnasium.

A particularly successful example of the 'Teaching Library' is the result of a creative solution for the linguistic promotion of a new student from Poland. One of the long-term volunteer library assistants, who is a Polish native speaker and devoted to passing her C2 German test, decided to offer free tutorials to the new student. The win-win-win outcome was:

- the pupil was transferred to the 9th grade despite initial difficulties and even shone with a grade 2 in Maths
- the DaF tutor passed the C2 exam with flying colors and is now allowed to teach German as a foreign language
- the school library once again served as an irreplaceable place of learning.

The children's book author THiLO has developed the escape room game 'Lockdown Agents: in the virologist's laboratory' to combat boredom during the Corona shutdown. With THiLO's instructions, the school library became a tricky escape room the last 4 days of school year, during emergency care and for the 8 groups of 3 to 4 agents each from winning class of 'Antolin', an

internet-based reading contest. Children were challenged to think outside the box and to work in a team.

All our other Teaching Library formats like ‘Reading in motion’, ‘Cartonera’, ‘Antolin’ could be offered according to the hygienic concept.

Advocacy ‘Who writes, stays. Who speaks, leads’

True to this motto, the school librarian and IFLA member Irina Nehme has produced a large number of texts for publicity and lobbying, involved in countless conversations with customers, colleagues and partners in digital, telephone and physical form. For the first time she took part in the first digital general meeting of the professional association BIB.

She proposed to found a commission or working group for school librarians and immediately set the process in motion. The invitation from the OPL commission to get involved with the prospect of an independent commission would be followed in the near future. As a first action in the OPL group, a webinar is planned for school librarians to get familiar with the IFLA guidelines and its Manifesto.

The first webinar for the Lebanese Library Association as a joint program

Figure 5. Engaged students in the ‘Cartonera’ IFLA Project

with IFLA colleagues from Italy and Great Britain entitled ‘Pandemic as a Portal to an Online Mindset’ was a complete success. Following the webinar, the moderator’s suggestion from the Lebanese Library Association to set up a separate division for school librarians within the association was very welcomed by the participants in the webinar.

The lobbying for school library projects and campaigns like ‘Cartonera’, ‘Reading in Motion’, ‘Fake Hunters’ could be done in

chats with the colleagues during the meeting. The appointment with the main editor of the leading library journal BuB to write three different articles with school library content was also made during the meeting and in the correspondence afterwards.

In collaboration with an IFLA colleague from the international high school Skolkovo, an intercross interview consisting of 11 questions was created for a Russian school library journal. A new, exciting format like that, thanks to the international comparison, provides insights into other countries and provides valuable information for one’s own use.

Abstracts for the school library lobbying work at the symposium ‘Must-have school library’ in Leipzig in May 2021 and for the librarian day in Bremen in

June 2021 were submitted. The mobilization of colleagues in Germany and abroad to participate in these events was also successful.

The collegial communication for the purpose of exchanging experiences, mutual support, possible partnerships, cooperation and bundled lobbying was livelier than ever during the pandemic year. Old contacts were reactivated and many new ones were made. The result is a better network that helps overcome the Robinson Crusoe syndrome¹⁷⁰ and gives each other courage and hope.

The modules 'News' and 'Knowledge Base' of our school portal iServ have been mainly filled with news and information from and about the library. This predominantly positive news in contrast to the many restrictive and negative messages ensured a progressive image of the school library among the users and were very much appreciated, to motivate them and inspire them in their school life.

The possibility to lobby for the four-pillar concept among the teaching staff and the school management was offered more than ever in personal discussions in 2020. The reorientation of the library on the foundation of inquiry-based learning with a focus on library pedagogy is always a topic of conversation. Some users and observers are critical, others benevolent and supportive. It is important to involve the critics and convince them with facts.

Final Remarks

The relationship between schools and thus also between school libraries, public and academic libraries as the digitization process, is accelerated this year by the pandemic, and can even be defined as a positive case. For school libraries and school librarians it won't be easier in the future, but it will be more exciting and challenging.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank my family with all my heart, who often share myself with the subject of school libraries in our family time, as is currently the case right before Christmas for the purpose of writing this text.

Without the motivation and persistence of my dear IFLA colleague and friend Luisa Marquardt, this contribution would not be possible. Thank you for your professionalism, constant collegial support and being a role model to me. A big thanks also goes to my school librarian

¹⁷⁰ That is, isolation, solitude, self-referentiality, the fear of confronting the new. See: Marzec, R.P. (2002). Enclosures, Colonization, and the Robinson Crusoe Syndrome: A Genealogy of Land in a Global Context. *Boundary 2: An International Journal of Literature and Culture*, 29(2), 129-156. DOI:10.1215/01903659.29-2-129. (Ed.N.)

colleague Staphany Wang in the neighboring school, who made this text linguistically more readable, just the day before Christmas Eve.

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Equal Opportunities for Different School Communities by Means of Library Services in Russia, by Svetlana Chazova¹⁷¹

Abstract

The school library system of the Russian Federation is the largest library union in the Country (in 2019 more than 41,000 school libraries for 16,100,000 learners). Strategies for improving the quality of Russian main education are assigned to the basic elements of the educational system, which include school libraries - a binding upon the department of the school area. Prioritized tasks of student information support are defined in Russian national projects and state educational standards. The school libraries network is managed through regional educational development institutions. Assistance for school library management departments is provided through the Information Center of the Russian Academy of Education. The findings of the empirical study, based on the analysis of 35 regional educational portals (41% of the total list of 85 entities of Russian Federation) clearly show persistent inequalities in the quality of management of regional information and methodological centers. The consolidated efforts of school library communities and federal and regional education management departments will help to overcome administrative, technological, and personnel barriers. A modern school library has to provide every learner and teacher with opportunities to deepen knowledge of school subjects, develop intellectual and creative abilities of learners, assist in choosing research ways and methods, study and improve knowledge of cultures and languages of Russia and the world.

Keywords: school library; professional skills; support of learning; access to information; educational information resources; website analysis.

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Introduction

In the modern world, childhood is always associated with studying. The space for teaching a modern child is multi-varied and multifaceted. Digital technologies replace, complement, surprise and engage modern young researchers. In such a situation it is very difficult for traditional school foundations to have competition. But the school remains a leading social institution that allows each child to open up basic knowledge and enter the adult world on an equal footing. It is especially important to ensure this in a geographical space with different climatic, economic, ethno-cultural, linguistic circumstances.

In the Russian Federation, learners from Sakhalin Island meet their parents from work when learners in Kaliningrad are just going to school. And this is not the biggest difference in the lives of learners in Russia. Sometimes the difference in school practices occurs at a distance of 100 km and sometimes in the same street of one community.

Russian School Libraries: Legal Framework

Modern education uses many approaches to learning, various concepts and conditions of movement towards mastering knowledge. In the Russian Federation, with all the variety of pedagogical approaches, the level of the educational development path determines the complex of strategic governmental action items and legal instruments. We denote these points by defining the location of the school library there:

National project 'Education' of the Russian Federation (2019-2024).

Here, in terms of the possibility of school library success and obtaining priority conditions for the implementation of their basic functions, two directions of the education system development can be distinguished: 'creating the necessary modern infrastructure' - we see providing school libraries with the necessary technological equipment and updating library collections, including multimedia resources and access to educational information resources on national and world level; 'upgrade qualifications' - building up the activities of the school library in order to ensure the processor of education and self-education of school teachers in the field, without interruption from the workplace. Thus, the library acquires the dual 'teacher - teacher-librarian' relationship, which provides the first one with the necessary conditions,

and the second one with the objective inclusion in the complex of educational disciplines.

Federal Law 'On Education in the Russian Federation' (2012), which covers the mandatory and recommended conditions for information support of the educational process. Here, the school library appears as an affordable element of an educational area. Article 18 of the Law 'Printed and electronic educational and informational resources,' describes educational publications, sources of library collections, and the provision of textbooks for each student. Professional requirements for personnel performing this function remain open.

Federal State Educational Standards of the Russian Federation. A mandatory minimum of requirements for library services in schools has been formed as a guaranteed level of quality of work for each school library. The quantitative standards of educational editions per student and modern technological conditions of service are determined.

Federal Law on Librarianship of the Russian Federation (last edition 2019). It states the role, rights and responsibility of libraries of various levels, including educational institutions, regardless of their organizational status. There is an addition to the listed general points. Regional institutes for the development of education of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, departments of education of territories, republics, regions and cities create specialized virtual platforms for generating relevant educational methods and open access to digital collections to help teachers and school libraries.

Methodological Approach

The research methodology is the verification of information presented on the all-Russian educational portals and a regional resources comparative analysis that support school education. A detailed study of the school library activities was made possible thanks to the work on social media through the accounts of schools and / or school libraries.

Research hypothesis: each Russian school library, regardless of the community location (the school base) has access to modern educational information resources.

A necessary condition is the sufficient professional skill of the school librarian to search for and assess the quality of the necessary educational resources.

Accordingly, each school in the Russian Federation has equal opportunities by means of library services.

According to the Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation, at the end of 2018, 85 constituent entities of the Russian Federation together had more than 41,000 school libraries for 16,100,000 students.

Among these, more than 23,000 schools are located in rural areas. Accordingly, about 23,000 school librarians, and most likely school staff with the functions of a school librarian, should form and maintain the school information space in accordance with modern educational requirements. This is not only difficult, but in many cases with limited budgets and an insufficient level of information and computer technologies it is impossible.

How is it possible that progressive mankind is completing the first quarter of the 21st century, the federal budget and local education administration bodies are spending serious resources, and we still have an unsatisfactory active equipment condition of one of the most important elements of school - school libraries?

However, it didn't happen at once. For more than twenty years, the Russian Federation has been undergoing structural changes to create mechanisms for managing the modernizing school education and providing information resources and services.

If we trace the evolution of school automating over the past decades, we will see how the idea of information services directly in schools was 'washed out' and the idea of a centralized information service got its influence.

For example, methodological guidance and general consultation of all Russian school libraries are centralized by the Federal Information and Methodological Center (FIMC) of the Information Center of the Russian Academy of Education 'Library named by K.D. Ushinsky'.

The distributed communication of the center with the local education authorities is maintained through instruction. FIMC organizes webinars through Regional Education Development Institutes. School librarians have the opportunity to meet colleagues and see the best practice and share experience.

One of the first open access network projects to help education was the Federal Portal 'Russian Education' (created in 2002). According to

the developers, 'it established itself as a reliable assistant to schoolchildren and students'. The following resources are available on the Federal Portal:

- Federal Information and Educational Resources Center
- Unified Collection of Digital Educational Resources
- Single Window for Access to Information Resources.

We have analyzed one section from the last resource. The following sources are presented there:

The total number of regional educational portals is 35 sites, which is 41% of the total list of 85 entities of Russian Federation. Among these:

- a) 8 (22.8 %) links are inactive;
- b) 27 sites, with actual links including:
 - 6 of them are sites not related to school education,
 - 5 have not been supported up to date for several years,
 - 13 have administrative functions, and
 - only 3 (Khabarovsk, Orenburg and Ulyanovsk

Regions)

are formed as navigators of educational resources taking into account educational levels and school subjects.

The obtained statistics allow to suggest that projects at the Federal level do not undergo regular verification and are not updated (timely). This means that they cannot be used as the main source of information for solving the problem of information support for teachers and librarians. One of the significant projects can be called: Moscow Electronic School - MES (implementation since 2016). The virtual collection shared 769,000 audio, video and text files, over 41,000 lesson scripts, more than 1,000 study guides and 348 textbooks of publishers, more than 95,000 educational applications. The collection is replenished by teachers, methodologists, and school administrations themselves. Each material undergoes a thorough inspection. The possibility to evaluate the resource and comment on it allows you to create a rating of materials and edit published materials, improve them if necessary. The success of MES has passed to the national level. The information platform of the national importance project 'Russian Electronic School' was created on the basis of the Moscow virtual educational system.

National libraries of the Russian Federation will also help school librarians to be relevant assistants in education. The Russian State

Children's Library offers two virtual projects at once: the National Electronic Children's Library and WebLandia: a network resources navigator for a children's audience. If the author has a number of comments to the navigator, then the digital archive of the National Electronic Children's Library is actively used in the educational process in many subjects of the Skolkovo International Gymnasium of the Innovation Centre. This is not the only library that provides access to full texts for education and research.

Here it is necessary to mention the electronic thematic collections and network projects of libraries of the 'Boris N. Yeltsin Presidential Library', 'State Public Historical Library', 'Russian National Library' and others.

A lot of librarians like to use the portal of cultural heritage 'KULTURA.RF' (culture.ru). The materials on domestic history, literature, architecture, music, theater, cinema, museums and traditions are collected there. For involving school children into subjects and research, it is possible to use video lectures by leading scientists, cultural and art, game tasks, tests, and virtual excursions.

While researching the activity of school libraries on social networks it was noted that the borrowing of materials from the portal 'KULTURA.RF' is most frequent.

Literary museums actively conquer virtual space and create virtual museums and online encyclopedias about writers and literary heroes. For example, there is a digital project 'Lev Tolstoy' (<http://tolstoy.ru/>). Studying the biography of the writer and his works with the help of this site increases the level of competence of students in the subject 'Literature'.

Thus, the undertaken review of some virtual projects allows us to suggest that in the absence of a sufficient school collection, but the school librarian is able to offer the school community a fascinating study through online services and cumulative resources with a virtual design of the information space of school subjects.

The characteristic of Russian education is that parents are also active participants in the educational process. They actively monitor not only the learning progress, but also participate in the preparation of homework, research projects and extracurricular activities of schoolchildren. This determines the emphasis of school librarians on the parent audience. This is complicated by the requirements of parents for the procedures and quality of education of a very subjective nature, sometimes corresponding to personal experience from the past. Such

participation sometimes distracts school librarians from the basic functions. At the same time, the involvement of parents in the educational process allows school librarians to take into account the characteristics of each child, identify his/her strengths in reading activities and assists in mastering complex personal tasks. In our practice we use the opportunity to discuss educational resources with parents. This enriches the parties. The teacher-librarian shares information about the terms of use of the information. Parents discuss features of digital reading by the learner, cases of effective or unsuccessful work with digital sources.

Total management decentralization of school libraries in the Russian Federation through regional institutes of education development of its entities allows taking into account the peculiarities of regional educational policy, monitoring the quality of service and promptly interacting with the library community. Regularly the Federal Information and Methodological Center (FIMC) hosts webinars for school librarians. Each webinar gives an opportunity to share the experience of information service in one of the regions.

The best school librarians present topics and methods of their activities, examples of helping students in education, promoting reading, and conducting school events. This format gives every school librarian access to professional improvement. Librarians quickly ask questions and get detailed answers, have the opportunity to compare working conditions and general school requirements. The function of the Federal center to integrate and take into account the characteristics of each school library on a national scale is significant.

In addition to the above several professional periodicals provide equal opportunities to instruct school librarians and improve their professional skills.

The periodicals 'School library', 'Chitayka' (translated as 'Read more'), 'School library: today and tomorrow' have a direct focus on the development of school libraries.

The Association of the Russian School Libraries World (rusla.ru) publishes both magazines. In addition to materials about the life of school libraries, the results of creative workshops of schoolchildren, professional library competitions, and new resolutions of the governing departments of education and library management of the Ministry of culture of the Russian Federation are published.

The Russian librarians have personal preferences in the selection of these journals. The published materials reflect the activities of school

libraries in many regions of the country. Monitoring the content of issues allows you to determine the content of library activities and the degree of library participation in the school community.

Each school librarian is able to include examples from the practice of colleagues in their work experience.

Final remarks

Thus, the Russian school librarian has various opportunities to continuously improve skills. The professional information system allows you to monitor current changes in school public administration and school policy opportunities. The formed information platform of educational resources requires a radical transformation. At the same time, the imperative to include modern educational and supported resources in school practice makes it possible to provide information services regardless of the distance from the center. Every school librarian has a set of tools to design the information environment, to provide knowledge and technology, and every school community of Russian Federation has equal opportunities by means of library services.

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International German-Russian Cartonera Project on the Topic ‘Faith, Hope, Love = вера, надежда, любовь’, by Irina Nehme¹⁷² and Svetlana Chazova¹⁷³

Abstract

The contribution describes the joint project “Belief, Hope, Love=Vera, Nadezhda, Lubov”, that originated after the presentation of the “Cartonera” Relendial Project (IFLA WLIC 2019, Athens) and aims at fostering the multicultural and interfaith dialogue through the school library. Germany and Russia share a lot in common, but there are also many differences (e.g., time zone, the school system, language and religion). Both colleagues are convinced that school libraries are democratic spaces to encourage freedom of speech and expression, nurture creativity, promote education on sustainability, and create the sense of community, all of which are ideal and essential for an interreligious dialogue. They are also convinced that active cultural exchange goes beyond national borders, serves as the basis for an international dialogue and thus the way to mutual understanding of different nations. 13 participants from different schools in Germany, aged from 9 to 11, are organized by the “Russian Language School Club”, taking place in the Hölty Gymnasium. From the Russian side, 25 children from the fourth grade take part in the project across various school subjects. The topic of the “Cartonera” is chosen through mutual agreement. In this project, the famous Russian Troika of “Belief, Hope, Love=Vera, Nadezhda, Lubov” as the way to promote peace and international understanding was chosen as the title of the “Cartonera”. Throughout the project, we aim to experience many valuable human and professional insights that we would like to share and spread.

Keywords: school libraries; networking; Cartonera Project; interfaith dialogue; religious education; Germany; Russia.

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The role of religion and interfaith dialogue in society, education, at schools and at the school libraries

Developing a planetary cross-cultural dialogue and contrasting fanaticism have become more and more urgent in the last decades. Beside the access to the wealth of information and resources on different cultures, religions etc., what could libraries do more?¹⁷⁴ Danieli and Guerrini, underlining the main reason for a “Relindial” Special Interest Group to be established¹⁷⁵ within IFLA, affirm that “A good knowledge of the other cultures is a good way to promote peace all over the world, and libraries have a role to play in addressing this challenge”.¹⁷⁶ Father Noël Sheth points out that

“The purpose of interreligious relations is not merely to build peace and harmony, especially in a superficial way. True peace and harmony comes through self-transformation and the transformation of society and nature. Religion is meant to transform ourselves and is not just a subject to be studied. Interreligious relations promote mutual spiritual enrichment.”¹⁷⁷

and furthermore:

“(…) “internal” or “interior” or “inner” or “intra-” religious dialogue is a sine qua non of authentic and deep interreligious dialogue, which has to be accompanied by interior dialogue.”¹⁷⁸

The Special Interest Group on “Religions: Libraries and Dialogue”, i.e. “Relindial”, was formally established within IFLA (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions) in April 2012, to promote library actions in the service of dialogue between religions and cultures. In its first attempt, Relindial carried out the usual activities of an IFLA group by organizing annual calls for papers and sessions

¹⁷⁴ Cfr. Dupont, O. (2014). Note de rédaction. In O. Dupont (ed.). *Libraries Serving Dialogue* (p. 1). Berlin/Boston: Walter de Gruyter.

¹⁷⁵ The exploratory phase that led to the IFLA Relindial SIG started on the 24th of August 2009, during the IFLA WLIC in Milan.

¹⁷⁶ Danieli, S., & Guerrini, M. (2014). Relindial: The Birth of a New IFLA SIG. In O. Dupont (ed.). *Libraries Serving Dialogue* (Ch. 1, pp. 5-13: 7). Quoted.

¹⁷⁷ Sheth, N. (2014) The Role of Libraries in Peace Building through Interreligious Dialogue. *Ivi* (Ch. 2, pp. 17-31: 15).

¹⁷⁸ *Ibidem*.

within the international congress. These sessions showcased very diverse activities, both human and professional, technical or relational, at the service of interreligious dialogue (IFLA Relindial). Leaflets and instructions for use have been documented in French, English, Spanish (soon in German and Arabic) and posted on the IFLA website (IFLA Relindial, 2020) to enable anyone interested to develop a project. The early years' experiences led to very positive results, thanks to the enthusiasm of the participants and organizers. Since 2016 (Dupont, 2020). Within those successful activities, the “Cartonera Project” was launched. Since the beginning of the initiative, there have been 818 participants, 141 supervisors, four continents and five countries involved in the project, namely: France, Chile, Germany, Russia and Burkina Faso. Now the project is at a turning point: in the first years it was mainly implemented in France and Chile, but thanks to the project “Faith, Hope, Love = вера, надежда, любовь” it is developing in Germany and Russia and another project is starting in Burkina Faso. Relindial welcomes everybody who wants to take part in this beautiful adventure!

Figure 1. Cartonera Project Bookmark.

The situation in Germany and at Hölty-Gymnasium Wunstorf

German society is not as strictly secular as, for example, French society, but both the Christian religion and the influence of the two big Churches (Catholic and Protestant) are losing ground. The biggest Study for Youth, the 18th Shell Youth Study Germany (2019, October) documents this development clearly and simultaneously, exposes that compared with the Muslim children and youth, who pray more regularly and identify much more with their religion, children with the Christian background commit less to religion. Consequently, the German multicultural and multi-religious society needs a dialogue between different generations and religions in order to coexist peacefully.

The question whether Religious Education (R.E.) belongs to the school curriculum or not is highly controversial. The 16 German Federal

States (“Länder”) have answered this differently, as the German educational system is not a national issue but a federal one. In some states there is confessional teaching (mostly of Catholic, Protestant and, sometimes, Muslim faith) by a confessional (do you mean “religion teacher” here?) teacher, like in the federal state of Lower Saxony, where the “Cartonera Project” is carried out. At public schools the students have usually the choice between R.E. and subjects like Ethics or Philosophy or, at primary schools, substitute subjects. Due to the increasing number of private religious schools, more students are obliged to study religion but usually separated by the confession (do you use confession to mean “admitting one’s sin” or do you mean “becoming a believer” or “joining the religion”?). In this way Germany enables but does not guarantee religious dialogues at schools. Furthermore, another obvious obstacle for the open-minded, uninhibited, democratic interreligious dialogue during the classes is the pressure of the grades.

The moderation of this dialogue by the school librarian could contribute to the democratic education at schools and a chance for school libraries to strengthen their concept of teaching. The idea of the library as a democratic place has been ingrained in the German society since the end of the Nazi regime, but the idea of the librarians acting as an educator of democratic values still sounds progressive and revolutionary for German schools. However, the concept of teaching in school libraries is not a new one, but has not been successfully implemented at the German schools yet. Even teaching information literacy to students by librarians is not the norm and needs to be justified on a regular basis.

International IFLA projects like Cartonera could support German librarians in their endeavor to contribute to the educational process and to manifest their role as educators in addition to their established role as supportive and administrative staff. All in all, the experience of the project is highly recommendable and planned to be repeated at the Hölty-Gymnasium during the project week “School without Racism” in July 2020. A cooperation with the social and arts teachers could be an option, too.

The situation in Russia and at the International Gymnasium Skolkovo

Russian schools have the school subject "Basics of Religious Culture and Secular Ethics". It is taught at the last year of elementary school.

The subject may cover the following topics: a general overview of the world's religions, secular ethics and etiquette, and a single religion. Parents independently choose the course option for their children. Practice shows that parents often choose a general overview of the world's religions and secular ethics.

International Gymnasium Skolkovo is located in the capital of Russia. There are many families with different religious backgrounds. Parents usually choose a general course on all religions of the world. Families do not demonstrate their religious beliefs openly.

The values of kindness, peace, understanding and acceptance are important in today's tense social environment. Moral values are delivered in both religious texts and literature. It is important to educate children and teens to acknowledge and accept people from different cultures and religions. The library's function is to promote a variety of worldviews and moral values through texts.

The frame for the project initiatives

- Personal contact at WLIC Athens 2019 between Russian and German school librarians, based on sympathy and interest in professional dialogue and exchange
- The convincing idea, the charming person behind the idea (Odile Dupont) and the beautiful artistic products of the previous projects (about Forgiveness and Joy)
- German year at the International Gymnasium Skolkovo, Russia
- Interest of the Russian Club participants at the Höltz-Gymnasium, Germany, in having personal contacts with Russian students
- Contribution to the UN-Agenda 2030 (Aims 4, 5, 10, 13, 16, 17)
- 75th Anniversary of Peace between Russia and Germany (celebrating the end of WW II on May, 8th and 9th)
- Contribution to the reconciliatory peace process between the Russian and the German nations during the period of political tensions and sanctions against Russia
- Personal biographic relation to the topic interreligious dialogue (Irina Nehme).

The Projects: Aims, framework for the project initiatives

Aims of the Project

The Project aims can be addressed to two main target groups: the students participating in the Project, and the two Project Leaders (the participating school librarians).

Students' level

Among the participating students, the Project aims at promoting:

- critical thinking, intercultural and interreligious dialogue
- creativity, artistic and handcraft skills
- communication and social skills
- literacy and language skills (reading, writing, information research)
- foreign language skills
- positive personalities, such as empathy, helpfulness, frankness, curiosity, respect and many others, which help to connect people
- positive feelings like joy, appreciation, hope, confidence, love
- sustainable thinking and acting
- digital technology skills

Project Leaders' level

The Project aims at:

- advocating for school libraries, within the school community and among librarianship
- advocating for qualified and engaged library staff
- establishing the school libraries as a “third place”, not only for teaching, learning and cultural activities but a place for open and democratic dialogue
- enhancing the pedagogical collaboration of school librarians with the teachers
- stimulating a professional international exchange of ideas and experiences.

Implementation of the project in three phases: 8/2019 to 8/2020

Phase 1: Project preparation (Aug. 2019 to Jan. 2020)

- Promoting the idea of the Cartonera Project among teachers & finding partners and participants for collaboration
- Pre-test of the implementation of the idea with a recommended group of 14 students to the Cartonera topic “God” (at Hölty-Gymnasium in Germany)
- Pre-search and discussions of possible topics
- Discussion and reaching agreement regarding the book format and formal aspects
- Search for information and literature by school librarians.

Figures 6 and 3. A letter from the German participants to the Russian Club with signatures and stickers on the back. (Nehme).

Phase 2: Production of the Cartonera and Discussion of the Topic (February -March 2020)

At Hölty-Gymnasium Wunstorf in Germany (HGW)

Participants of the Russian Club: 2 adults (library volunteers) and 12 children aged from 9 to 13 with diverse religious backgrounds (Catholic, Protestant, Orthodox, Atheist)

The *Cartonera Project* was embedded into the topics of 4 lessons (90 minutes each):

1. the very special use and habit of Russian first names
2. Russian customs and celebrations (religious and not religious),
3. historical and current political context of the German-Russian relations
4. sustainability as our mutual global challenge
5. media and communication (print, analogous and digital).

Observations, which were made during the production process:

Participants

- grasped the idea and the objectives of the project quickly
- were motivated and concentrated on their own contribution
- demonstrated a high sense of responsibility and collaboration for the mutual production of the cover (what does “cover” here refer to?)
- exposed their beliefs, attitudes, religious habits and traditions in an uninhibited way
- discussed openly and frankly religious topics, the distinction between belief and superstition, the delicate difference between religious conservatism and extremism
- coordinated, accepted and implemented decisions democratically
- but revealed difficulties by writing a letter to the anonymous addressee group (or readers).

Figure 4. The Creative Process (©Nehme)

Figure 5. Books of the Library used in the Project. (©Nehme)

At the International Gymnasium Skolkovo (IGS)

Participants are students of the fourth grade of the Primary School (23 children) and teaching staff with the chief librarian as project coordinator

The Cartonera Project was implemented in the lessons “Literary Reading”, “Basics of World Religious Cultures”, “Creative Workshop” and free library discussion. 9 lessons (40 minutes each) were designated for this project.

- Religions bring global values to everyone, to express themselves and pass on to others.
- Belief in kindness and love helps people to survive through the most difficult historical times.
- It is important to preserve and increase the human values between everyone in times of political conflicts.
- The development of civilization, a country depends on the voluntary acceptance and replication of universal values.
- A book is an important source of preserving and transmitting universal values.

During the production process, it was possible to observe that participants:

- were interested in performing non-routine work
- were motivated to participate in an international project and evaluate their own contributions
- demonstrated sufficient creative potential to offer ideas to embody personal meanings
- made personal judgments about the need to develop ideas of kindness, help, forgiveness, and religious freedom
- disclosed difficulties in combining texts and drawings to the same meaning
- discovered a lack of personal time management.

Phase 3: Post Processing of the Project (April – December, 2020)

Project evaluation will be done separately by each participating school and also in comparison to each other.

The initiatives and the aims for the project unite both school librarians from Russia and from Germany, but what differences could be observed during the second phase?

Despite the possible differences the physical product of the project, the *Cartonera* will be the one uniting both schools and nations.

Figure 6. Project Presentation Board. (© Nehme)

Figure 7. Six pages of 'Cartoneras' (© Nehme)

Final Remarks

Despite the interruption of the project due to the Covid-19 shutdown, both school librarians from Russian and Germany are highly motivated to continue the project in the next school year. They believe in this project, the hope for the bright future are not only for our Countries - Russia and Germany -, but for the whole world. The love for our work and our library clients is stimulating us to continue the project as soon as possible.

Acknowledgment

Many thanks go to:

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- last but not least, of course, to the teachers and students of the both schools in Germany and Russia for participating in the project.

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The Culture of Network Sharing: School, Associations and the Local Context,¹⁷⁹ by Eva Pasqualini,¹⁸⁰ Elisabetta Valente¹⁸¹ and Alessia Gargano¹⁸²

Abstract

The present contributions present results for activities of promotion to reading steadily conducted over twenty years as part of a network in the local context in East Rome. The school library network involves schools of all orders and degrees, parent associations, publishers, illustrators, writers, and arts didactic experts. This long-standing experience confirms the need to spread and consolidate a sharing culture, avoiding extemporaneous, short-lived projects and instead focusing on systemic, multilateral initiatives valorising reading in all of its aspects through the planning and realization of ritualized, recurring, thematic activities through time. The network is characterized by the involvement of students and families, the broad range of initiatives offered (exhibitions, prizes, workshops, etc.) and a renewed emphasis on the relation between action, formation and research.

Keywords: parents' association; distributed educational leadership; reading promotion; school library network; University.

¹⁷⁹ Translation by Antonio Lenzo.

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1. Introduction¹⁸³

Cultural pluralism is one of scholastic autonomy's aims, which schools may pursue through network collaborations with institutions, associations or local agencies. Cultural initiatives joining the interests of several subjects at a shared network level promote the participation of all parts involved in educational projects, building up a sense of local belonging. The action of the Local Multimedia School Library interinstitutional network, began in 1999 within the context of the 'Program for the promotion and development of school libraries', can be read in this perspective.

Over the years, the network enriched cultural promotion opportunities in East Rome with several initiatives supporting collaboration and co-planning processes with other institutions, with the aim of qualifying, enriching and integrating curricula at a local level. It also placed particular emphasis, on the one hand, on favoring access to and critical use of several tools and information and formation sources for children and young adults between the ages of 3 and 15, and, on the other, on supporting and promoting socialization, intergenerational exchange and the building of a sense of community belonging in a local context with especially targeted initiatives.

Among the most significant cultural initiatives, the 'Exhibition and initiatives on Childhood Reading and Literature' has been ongoing for ten years. The initiative is characterized by a structure involving several institutions in a network – the University, publishers, schools, associations, illustrators and writers – and integrating a plurality of interventions aimed at valorizing reading. The network sharing culture which characterizes the initiative made the exhibition highly anticipated by children, teachers and families (Moretti, 2009; Barzanò, 2019).

For children, the initiative enriched the curriculum by providing learning occasions for basic cultural knowledges and languages in 'authentic' learning contexts and environments able to favour the acquisition of critical thinking skills (Cerri, Genta & Traverso, 2014). For teachers, cooperating in the shared recording of local cultural and formational needs, in close relationships of shared planning and knowledge building with other institutions (Universities, field experts, publishers, associations), promotes research processes that can encourage active and collaborative didactic modes and strategies.

¹⁸³ The present contribution has three co-authors. In particular, paragraphs 1 and 6 were written by Eva Pasqualini; paragraph 2 was written by Elisabetta Valente; paragraphs 3, 4 and 5 were written by Alessia Gargano.

By valorising the principle of proximity between cultural and artistic resources for people undergoing education, the initiative meant to offer high-quality cultural proposals to locals and families representing a shared space for action that would be accessible and inclusive (Ianes & Cramerotti, 2016; Castaldi, 2020).

2. Goals and Hypotheses for Observational Investigation

The present contribution meant to examine the results of an observational investigation conducted at the Istituto Comprensivo Bruno Munari, in the context of actions of promotion to reading linked to the yearly initiative titled ‘Exhibition and initiatives on Childhood Reading and Literature,’ now in its fourteenth year and collaboratively conducted within a local network in East Rome.

The initiative is characterized by a structure involving several institutions in a network – the University, publishers, schools, associations, illustrators and writers – and integrating a plurality of interventions aimed at valorising reading, relying on numerous professional, economical and human resources, also locally.¹⁸⁴

Such cultural activities are characteristic of schools that embrace the participation of multiple stakeholders and, seizing the opportunities offered by school autonomy, have initiated a process of educational innovation. They co-design sustainable educational pathways, accompanied by the presence of experts who propose workshop interventions designed with flexible structures that are easily transferable to other contexts.

One of the relevant aspects for the initiative is the involvement of parent associations, especially the ARTU Parent Association, a non-profit institution dealing with local cooperative work with schools and formational agencies, guided by the notion that parents and families ought to contribute to the improvement of curricula. Parent associations made notable efforts towards the planning of contexts that would promote reading aloud and towards the diffusion of practices

¹⁸⁴ As emphasised in *Indicazioni Nazionali per il curricolo*, relatively to the importance of valorizing local resources, ‘the network (...) has to be able to identify local needs (formative, project-related, administrative)’ (MIUR, 2012, p. 12).

and strategies to help adults, too, discover and transmit the pleasures of reading.

During cultural events ('Mostra e iniziative sulla Lettura e Letteratura per l'infanzia', Giornata della Lettura condivisa, Premio di Poesia), experts and operators from parent associations support each initiative curating, for example, the exhibition of illustrators' tables and the setup of an itinerating exhibition; devoting specific time slots to the planning of laboratory activities, the association favors a gamelike approach focused on multimedia practices, expressive languages and various communication channels. In laboratories, it valorizes individual expert contributions within groupwork, oriented towards a shared goal, such as the design of art books, tools for scientific examination, multimedia production, artwork creation. The materials used and produced during the childhood reading and literature promotion events are then grouped in thematic sections in the BSMT network libraries, where they can be rehashed and recontextualized for future initiatives.

Research conducted at I.C. Munari examined three practices characterizing the initiative: shared reading, the illustrator exhibition, the treasure hunt accompanying the exhibition. The aim was to verify the following hypothesis: the 'Initiative for childhood reading and literature' could be considered a strategic resource to encourage both students and teachers to assume responsibilities and active roles so as to exercise diffuse educational leadership (Domenici & Moretti, 2011; Earley, 2013; Harris, 2014), in the context of cultural projects or events co-planned by a mixed inter-institutional network of schools, associations and other local subjects?

A further objective for the examination was the recording of participation modes for activities of promotion to reading on both the students' and teachers' part, as well as non-teaching personnel, experts and families (parents, grandparents, caretakers, and other local subjects, who to varying degrees contributed to the project's successful realization. The sample consisted of a class group numbering 21 fourth-grade elementary school students ranging between 9 and 10 years of age.

3. Strategic actions in the context of the initiative for childhood reading and literature

The 'Initiative for childhood reading and literature' is promoted by Anicia Publishing House alongside Professor Giovanni Moretti,

Università degli Studi Roma Tre, Formation Sciences Department, in co-planning with I.C. 'Bruno Munari', I.C. 'Via Nicolai', I.C. 'Via Belforte del Chienti', I.C. 'Via A. Balabanoff', I.C. 'Casalbianco', I.C. 'Uruguay', I.C. 'Piazza Filattiera', I.C. 'Piersanti Mattarella', ARTU Parent Association, the Network for Local Multimedia School Libraries, Cooperativa il Carosello and, since 2019, I.C. 'Poppea Sabina' and MIRABILIA Cultural Association. Such initiative was pursued consistently over several years, constituting a recurring event to which school and parent association actively participate, beginning with co-planning, promoting flexible didactics helping the school overcome the boundaries of traditional methodology and allowing children to learn creatively (Domenici, 2015).

The cultural initiative represented the background against which interactions favoring access to schools, publishers, illustrators, writers and art experts were developed, facilitating flexible use in a school context with innovative strategies: meetings with external experts, laboratory activities, exhibition, writing competitions, space repurposing and advertisement of children's artwork.

In order for students to fully comprehend an initiative-event, it is necessary to flexibly plan for adequate times and spaces, so as to allow students to experience the cultural curriculum firsthand. Flexibility is a necessary aspect because of 'the notion of event in a space which, though circumscribed, defined and recognizable, opens up towards the unexpected, towards creativity, towards the deconstruction and reconstruction of paths and processes, towards the continued mutual play of planned objectivity and surprising subjectivity' (Cerri, 2007, p. 45).

The initiative's realization was made possible by the collaboration of several subjects and institutional realities. The network project proposes to valorise the autonomy of individual schools through forms of collaboration and resource sharing, be it human, financial or instrumental, with specific shared aims. To this end, the planning model attempted to integrate a plurality of resources and skill-sets in order to favour the effective promotion of reading in educational contexts.

In the context of the initiative, the many planned actions were all aimed at encouraging children to acquaint themselves with the book and with various reading and image fruition practices, before, during and after the activities. Here we intend to showcase the results of an investigation

in which we examined shared reading aloud, the illustrator exhibition and the treasure hunt that accompanied it.

Shared reading aloud is a widespread practice which allows all involved parts to interact. School curricula ought not to neglect shared reading as a fundamental practice for the development of the enjoyment of reading and of text comprehension skills. For best results in a school context, it ought to involve (Moretti, 2003):

1. Adequate spaces and timing;
2. High-quality texts of several kinds and easy accessibility in large quantities;
3. The chance to reread;
4. The chance to be both a reader and a listener;
5. The chance to dialogue with other readers in a playful climate of mutual trust.

Reading aloud is an inclusive practice helping children getting used to listen and increasing attention spans by stimulating the desire to learn how to read. In the context of the study, *Terra tra le mani* by Cristiana Pezzetta (Anicia, 2015) was the book chosen for the readings.

In the initiative, the reading's main themes were valorised in the illustrator exhibition, an itinerant initiative set up in schools belonging to the network in order to allow teachers, students and parents to visit.

The exhibition shows over forty original tables with the aim of allowing both children and adults to enjoy art. One of the main goals is that of setting up the necessary requirements for them to live through a satisfying, emotional experience while also stimulating curiosity and developing skills and competences in the context of expression, aesthetics and language.

Schools progressively devoted special emphasis to the quality of the table's showcasing, accompanying them with texts and organizing activities and reading laboratories to enhance the educational experience in perusing the tables in the exhibition.

Among the activities, the treasure hunt in particular relied on the artwork to acquaint children with the exploration and critical appreciation of art with its expressive and aesthetic value.

One of the goals for the treasure hunt was to replay a story told in 'Terra tra le mani' through play. The treasure hunt led children through exhibition by means of the identification of clues, specifically conceived

to valorize the relation between the text and the image, by decoding which children were able to go through the exhibition dynamically, until they could reach the treasure.

In this sense, it is important to note which visual references would be associated to words in the space. The clue's importance is central for the educational implications and effects on participants (De Simone & Muto, 2018).

4. Data recording tools

The data recording tools used in the study were a questionnaire for students, an observation grid and the conducting of interviews with students as well as with the author and the illustrator for *Terra tra le mani*, the book chosen for the reading practice.

The questionnaire

The questionnaire is a widespread tool used in several instances to acquire reliable information on behaviours, competences and attitudes (Bosco, 2006). The semi-structured questionnaire was compiled by students after the shared reading of *Terra tra le mani* by C. Pezzetta. It included nine questions, of which:

- Four, two-answer questions;
- Four closed-ended questions;
- One open-ended question.

The aim was to record the students' point of view in regards to shared reading aloud and to the initiatives promoting the enjoyment of reading in educational contexts.

The Observation Grid

The observation grid was used during shared reading. The grid was specifically designed for the inquiry with the aim to record information on the relation to the book as object and on children's behaviour during readings. The markers in the grid allowed us to record whether the child:

- ✓ Knows the book as an object;
- ✓ Wants to touch the book;
- ✓ Is attentive during reading;
- ✓ Asks to participate in readings;

- ✓ Waits for their turn;
- ✓ Observes and explores images;
- ✓ Demands the story's rereading;
- ✓ Actively participates during reading.

Data was recorded for each child who participated in the readings.

The Interview

We made use of three interview stages; the first was conducted with students after the treasure hunt, so as to record interest and enjoyment levels for the activity. The second and the third were respectively conducted with the author and the illustrator of *Terra tra le mani*, with an emphasis on the enjoyment of reading and with the goal of recording certain features relating to the text's content and to the images' relevance.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Data recorded through the questionnaire highlights that shared reading aloud practices were especially appreciated by children. The first question asked whether children did or did not love reading books: the answer recorded shows that 17 out of 21 children love reading. The promotion of the enjoyment of reading in a school context is therefore an essential activity, necessary for the development of engaged readers.

The second question asked whether children had participated in a shared reading activity before; all of them had. However, only some children had participated in such activities as readers (Graph 1).

Graph 1: results for the questionnaire on shared reading (absolute values)

The recorded data is promising, but it is necessary to contextualize it within the school network that hosted the initiative. The schools that participated have been devoting continuing emphasis to valorizing shared reading practices; the yearly initiative is the result of a project that has been ongoing for many years.

This continuity undoubtedly allowed children to acquaint themselves with the themes discussed and especially with a variety of reading practices, as well as to thoroughly know the several parts involved in the cultural panorama characterizing print and digital publishing (publishers, illustrators, editors, writers, cinema and art experts).

With the aim of ascertaining the degree of interest shown by students towards the participation in activities involved in the promotion of reading, we asked the following question: ‘Would you like to take part in an activity to deepen your knowledge of the book’s themes?’ (Graph 2).

Graph 2 *Interest in further approaches to the book’s themes shown by children (absolute values)*

We can say that over half the children would ‘really’ like to extend the shared reading activity with further book-oriented activities. Through the activities, children enthusiastically develop an interest towards the book as an object as well as the desire to retell the story from other perspectives and points of view.

In the last questionnaire question, we asked students to express their ideas on why shared reading might promote reading. Here we show some extracts from the most interesting answers we received:

'because, if someone does not like reading, I can explain the book to them, since I have understood it'. (L. T.)

'because reading provokes emotion and interest.' (A. G.)

'because by reading you can get to know fictional characters and unseen places.' (S. F.)

'because shared reading kickstarts my imagination and makes me want to be lost in reading' (R. D.)

Overall, data and answer analysis demonstrated positive results. Children engaged with the story told in *Terra tra le mani* and they found it interesting to continue their inquiry into the story by participating in further activities.

Observation Results

Activity observation was conducted through an observation grid which allowed the recording and encoding of a broad range of behaviours shown by students while participating in shared reading aloud (Graph 3)

Graph 3: Outcome for the student observation during shared reading (absolute values)

The marker with the highest incidence recorded evidences that the near-totality of children is interested in touching the book.

Exploration is thought by children to be an essential activity to getting to know the book in all of its parts. It is also instrumental for a tactile education that will promote the knowledge of objects, environments and situations.

The 'chance to reread a book' question also recorded a noteworthy result. Observation shows that 19 children out of 21 wish to again discover the story told in *Terra tra le mani*. The same enthusiasm is found in the children asking to participate in reading; only three of them did not participate in shared reading. A further result of interest involves children's ability to wait for their turn; only two children were misaligned with the speaker. Participation in high-quality reading practices allows children to be more directly involved in activities with their class group, facilitating increased attention on the part of participants who feel themselves to be active subjects in the learning process.

Taking into account overall behaviour for each child who participated, we can say that most of them actively participated in the shared reading activity, asking questions about the story's meaning, reading parts of the book aloud and answering questionnaire questions.

Interview Results

The study used interviews to ascertain participants' points of view after the treasure hunt which accompanied the illustrator exhibition.

Four children were interviewed immediately after the treasure hunt. Analysis of the interviews' contents highlights two relevant aspects.

The first involves the space in which the treasure hunt was hosted; children would like to participate in a treasure hunt that involves clues in both outdoor and indoor spaces.

The second aspect involves the importance attributed to illustrations, which allowed children to retell the story in several ways. In answer to the question 'If I asked you to summarize the activities conducted together with a few words, what would you say?', children highlighted the following concepts: *sharing, imagination, cooperation, emotion and adventure*.

The interview conducted with the author of *Terra tra le mani* highlighted important features. In answer to the question 'Why do you think this sort of initiative is successful in stimulating children's acquaintance with reading?', the author replied firmly, noting that the exhibition

made it clear what lies behind the book. ‘Through illustrations, we give an artistic experience back to children.’ The author compares the book to a magic door, separating the real world from the ‘surreal world.’

The second question we addressed to the author, on the other hand, focusses on inclusion; according to the author, the book centers the theme of hospitality: the co-construction of sense and meaning to help children understand the importance of listening.

The most relevant aspect confirming the initial hypothesis emerged in the following question: ‘*Terra tra le mani* was the object of a shared reading at the illustrator exhibition, and it was also used in the fourth-grade treasure hunt. How do you think the story told by the book and the treasure hunt might contribute to the development of a sense responsibility in children and in the class group?’ The author said that we ought to divorce the book from an insular conception of reading so as to contextualize it more broadly. The book, in fact, opens up paths that allow children to inclusively congregate through play like in this case. Overall, the author thought that ‘the book showcases how hospitality is not only lending your own point of view but listening to others’ needs’. The aim is the collaborative making of meaning and signification so as to show children the importance of taking up one’s responsibilities and establishing active roles in knowledge-making processes, accepting the risk of doing wrong, formulating hypotheses and conjectures in collaboration with peers and experts during significant experiences under expert supervision.

The last interview was conducted with Gioia Marchegiani, the illustrator of *Terra tra le mani*, whose original tables were shown at the exhibition. The interview discussed:

- The role of the image;
- The theme of hospitality;
- The exhibition’s relevance;
- The importance of taking care of oneself and others.

Answer analysis shows that, for Gioia Marchegiani, images are essential insofar as they extend the text’s meaning. According to her, there is no need to ‘represent the word, but rather to represent its interpretations. Illustrations trail after a text’s emotion, welcoming the child into a surreal world.’

The exhibition emerges as a strategic resource for children, as it allows them to have an innovative didactic experience contributing to the

development of cultural identity through an approach to artworks and the reading of high-quality books.

6. Final Remarks

Local cultural initiatives developed over the years by the Local Multimedia School School network mobilized material and artistic resources, engaging school-children, while also developing a taste for reading, satisfying the need for discovery and novelty, exercised aesthetic pleasure and the need to know oneself, also encouraging connection between children and with the other. These formational requirements are essential to the ends of both the achievement of an early and solid reading skill-set and the development of personal identity and critical and open-minded approaches to knowledge. In a time in which new forms of cultural illiteracy threaten to generate ever more frail and distracted readers, the planning and realization of local initiatives emerge as necessary requirements to ensure students have the opportunity to participate in significant activities of cultural diffusion aimed at promoting reading, valorising it, building a system of network collaborations relying on educational research and collaborations with the University, publishing and associations.

Research outcomes confirm the need to encourage formative experiences that would enrich school curricula with co-planned, shared activities with other local institutions. In the context of the present investigation of shared reading, the illustrator exhibition and the treasure hunt, it was possible to record active participation in students. Innovative tool design and the valorising of new learning strategies allowed children and young adults to develop leadership skills and the assumption of responsibility. Network sharing culture allows for the development of learning environments where it is possible to access a variety of resources, as well as to exercise diffused educational leadership and to approach different perspectives. All of this permits the enrichment of decisional and evaluative processes with the contribution of all parts involved: teachers, educators, parents, managers, non-teachers, students and experts. Overall, the reflection on initiative and research confirms the strategic relevance of synergizing the school network with the university, so as to allow for activity effectiveness monitoring; the positive value of collaborating with publishing and with field experts (authors, illustrators, etc.), which allows for the actualization of cultural experiences; the relevant

contribution supplied by associations which allows for the grounding of experiences in a local context.

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The BiblioPoint experience in Rome, by Giovanna Micaglio¹⁸⁵

Abstract

The contribution illustrates the experience that ‘Biblioteche di Roma’ (City of Rome Library Services) has been developing for about twenty years. With the collaboration of schools of different order and degree in order to provide integrated access to reading, information and cultural events for both the school and local communities.

The ‘BP Protocol’, the different types of BPs and the distribution of the current 43 BPs in the Municipalities of Rome are illustrated. The importance of networking and cooperation between School Library and Public Library is emphasized. The requirements that school libraries must have to enter the BP network are presented (proper spaces, shelves, organization of documents, assets’ treatment, openness to the public, human resources, financial resources). Finally, some examples of good practices are provided and some concluding reflections are presented, considering the monitoring conducted in 2020 through survey questionnaires.

Keywords: public libraries, school libraries, collaboration, reading promotion, BiblioPoint.

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BiblioPoints in Rome from 2003 to 2020, a growing trend

Facing the educational and cultural emergency, the *City of Rome Library Services* Institution replied with new strategies to involve a higher number of schools and enlarge their link with libraries. BiblioPoints (spaces where you can read, study, borrow books from the school library, participate in cultural activities) are first born in 2003 and there were just about ten; in 2020, there are 43 BiblioPoints.

Until year 2018, the BiblioPoint Protocol included a significant commitment from schools which had to ensure, in addition, extra-school hours opening for the neighbourhood. The conditions were therefore very selective and, if on one side it brought out the excellence of Roman school libraries, on the other it did not allow the weaker ones to connect directly to the *City of Rome Library Services* and develop their own potential.

For this reason, in 2018 it's been decided to provide two new types of BiblioPoint, including open to public school libraries with limited book stock, and also those school libraries that address their service to internal users.

By doing this, weaker school libraries with a potential to develop have been reached: a school library supported by ISBCC (*City of Rome Library Services*), regardless its level, can become a significant cultural resource for its neighbourhood. The big amount of requests from schools to become partner with ISBCC by activating BiblioPoint Protocol had a successful outcome, demonstrating that the collaboration between libraries and educational agencies is a really urgent goal to reach.

Even if the economic resources that ISBCC can invest for school libraries are dropping sharply, this does not discourage schools from applying for the agreement: many are in the waiting list.

While reshaping the connection with BiblioPoint, *City of Rome Library Services* increased the offer of highly qualified zero cost services like: refresher trainings for school librarians, cooperation in realizing cultural activities, book donations and production of bibliographies.

The BiblioPoint Protocols: a response to the educational emergency and the decrease of readers in Italy

BiblioPoints have an important role in terms of spreading the practice of reading in the territory and it can fill a gap in areas where the Institutions could not open a library.

For this reason, City of Rome Library Services responds to an increasingly pressing cultural emergency by multiplying cultural activities in the area also through school libraries. The alert on Italian citizens' competences emerges from data on reading practice and on comprehension and elaboration of a written text. The OCSE-PISA 2018 data returned a startling scenario: the reading skills of youngsters are unfortunately decreasing.

Third millennium's illiterates are unable to open up to new ideas because they do not grasp it through reading. They accept an easier solution and seek nothing but validation of what they already think.

It is necessary then, in order to stimulate consciences and minds, to respond to the cultural emergency by intervening on the educational emergency also. It is possible to make concrete actions starting from schools and school libraries, which are the places where youngsters can 'acquire the necessary skills for lifelong learning, develop the imagination and making them become responsible citizens' (IFLA-UNESCO School Library Manifesto). It is urgent to encourage youngsters rediscovering the passion for reading. In 2019 the AIE (the Italian Publishers' Association) estimated that 53% of Italian readers read a maximum of 1-3 books per year. If youngsters have the access to good books, to proper practices of invitation to read and to institutional interventions that effectively target their cultural growth, they will be able to give excellent results. Otherwise the result is unfortunately quite different.

In addition to schools and libraries another important element is the family: not only the presence of books in the house but having parents that read makes the difference, giving the child 2.8 more chances to become a valid reader. ISTAT estimated that 66.8% of children between 6 and 14 years old whose parents are readers read books and between children whose parents are not readers just 30.9% of them read books. This scenario fits the BiblioPoint experience in Rome.

BiblioPoints: The Experience of City of Rome Library Services

Collaboration between schools and libraries represents a unique opportunity for the promotion of reading and the strengthening of Roman's school Libraries. It is no coincidence that BiblioPoint project started from the collaboration between City of Rome Library Services and some Scholastic Institutes that showed their willingness to

strengthen and expand their libraries, opening them to the territory in order to create a service open to the neighbourhood.

Communication is important to spread the proposal to potentially interested schools. All the information to get in touch with the School Service and to know how to become a BiblioPoint are on the *City of Rome Library Services' website*.

Currently there are 43 active BiblioPoints in the city that can be added to the 40 Libraries of the Capitoline Library System. Bibliopoints are located in Comprehensive Institutes and High Schools.

As it can be seen from the BiblioPoints mapping published on the ISBCC website, BiblioPoints are spread in almost all the City of Rome, especially in the suburbs. This is an important information because it denotes a greater interest from schools located further away from cultural services and in some cases in the most at-risk areas. Suburban schools feel the urgency to take actions to contrast school's dropout and educational emergency.

Integrative activities are needed, starting from invitation projects to reading that can guide students to critical understanding written texts and developing personal opinions. Teachers know they need to be supported in order to properly reach this goal and are searching for others resources outside the school. Libraries can be strong allies and many schools understood how important ISBCC's collaboration and support is. This is the reason why there is a major number of suburban schools signing the *City of Rome Library Services' BiblioPoint Protocol*. Out of 43 BiblioPoints, in fact, 30 of them are those affiliated with suburban schools. Almost half of them are type C: only accessible to internal users from the school. This type of BiblioPoints are part of the new 2018 Protocol formula.

The aim is to use the Protocol to help them improving: about 10% of these school libraries have, in fact, been promoted to type B after only one year of service, with the help of *City of Rome Library Services' School Service*, sending staff that can work during the afternoon shifts (Civil Service Operators) and organizing professional meetings for the school staff.

Cooperation between school libraries (formal education) and public libraries (informal education) derives from a common aim: to respond to readers' needs and to gain new readers.

Children should be educated to passion for reading since the earliest years, while weak readers or non-readers should be reached by

attractive invitations to reading. Together Schools and Libraries can strengthen the cultural offer and also their active presence in the neighbourhood.

The signing of a joint Protocol between schools and libraries commits those institutions and constitutes a concrete work plan that offers better services in order to respond every age group's cultural needs.

Each BiblioPoint is associated with the closest public library, promoting the cooperation between two public structures and the joint planning of cultural activities, allowing optimizing time and resources.

The updating of the libraries' collection can also be planned in cooperation: the school library can take advantage of ISBCC librarian professional advices reviewing and discarding the inventory, while the school librarian can guide part of the book's purchasing based on the cultural and teaching/learning needs.

To promote the library's collection, it is also recommended to plan cultural events and activities related to the books owned by the School Library or the Public Library.

The events addressed to the school population organized by the Public Library have to be disposed in common agreement with the BiblioPoint in order to really meet students' need and so guarantee the success of the initiatives. Especially with regard to areas such as: PCTO (ex Alternanza Scuola-Lavoro), participation to public calls that require partnership agreement or signing to inter-librarian projects.

About the promotion to reading addressed to disabled readers, the ISBCC School Service started a partnership with schools to launch joint effective and long-term actions some years ago. The planning of cultural project and activities for BES readers carried by ISBCC School Service has led to: invitation meetings to reading both in Libraries and BiblioPoints, courses for teachers on CAA books, bibliographies for special readers. The Permanent Work Table for Special Readers is planned; teachers, professionals, ASL staff and associations already joined it.

The required commitment from the School is regulated according to the 3 BiblioPoint (BP) Protocol types.

Protocol BP type A concerns school libraries with at least a 5,000 books heritage and requires the commitment by the school to guarantee the opening of the school library to local readers at least two afternoons per week.

Protocol BP type B concerns school libraries with at least a 2,500 books heritage and requires the commitment by the school to guarantee the opening of the school library to local readers at least one afternoons per week.

Protocol BP type C concerns school libraries with at least a 1,500 books heritage and requires the commitment by the school to guarantee the movement and sharing of the volumes among students, without the obligation to open to the external users.

The ISBCC (City of Rome Library Services Institution), by signing the BP Protocol, is committed to supporting the new BPs. This commitment includes actions aimed at opening new library services, strengthening cultural activities, and offering professional support through training courses and economic consultancy.

Aims of the BP Protocol: space management, documentary heritage: classification and cataloguing

The decision to create a new form of collaboration with schools through the BP Protocol was made to support the creation and continuity of a powerful alliance between libraries and schools, favouring their autonomy. Libraries' goal is not to offer services to strong readers only, but also to reach potential readers and educate them to reading since the earliest years. Because of the agreement with schools, it's easier to directly reach the most receptive catchment area (the one that includes youngsters from 3 to 18 years old).

Another aim is to bring BPs closer to public library's standards, with proper library services in line with international guidelines, keeping in mind IFLA-Unesco Manifesto on Public Library, that gives detailed elements on the definition of 'public library'. It is important to remember how difficult is to establish a common model for all libraries: each one has his own needs, following the ones of his readers. Public libraries have specific characteristics (space, staff, collection) and are constantly evolving.

Before activating the Agreement, the School Service conducts an inspection to check whether the minimum conditions for signing the Protocol are met. From that moment, the School Service will implement all necessary actions to support the school and to achieve and maintain all the standards of the specific type of school library.

Unlike public libraries, school libraries are aimed especially for a specific target: youngsters. Therefore, its collections have to be directed to this target. It happens instead, that school libraries become receptacles of book donations without any selection, filling the shelves with obsolete books, unsuitable for youngsters. The collection of books must therefore be constantly monitored by the librarian, the teacher or other dedicated professional. If the School Library is efficient it will play an important role of connection between the school and its neighbourhood.

The School Library also has an important role in the school as it supports didactic and promotes reading as a fundamental part of the school program, in order to train citizens capable to use new information and process them in critical form.

The Requirements for a school library applying to become BP are: a dedicated space for the school library; open and compliant shelves; a book heritage appropriate to the signed BP Protocol; human resources (at least one referent); collaboration with ISBCC closest library.

The BiblioPoint's space must be furnished in order to be used by the target to which it is dedicated. Comprehensive Institutes have a wide target range from 3 to 12/13 years old and, with enough space, it is recommended to create dedicated spaces with appropriate furnishings designed with a colourful and captivating style.

Public libraries have furnished spaces dedicated to children and it is an advisable choice to organize them even in primary and nursery school libraries. Another idea is the 'soft corner': an equipped area inside the library with rugs and pillows.

In order to facilitate the access to document resources, it is important that school libraries also equip themselves with signs that will guide students searching for physical documents. The BiblioPoint external signal is usually provided by City of Rome Library Services which adds the logos and ensures uniformity within all the partner schools.

There are school that, despite having an adequate book collection, still tend to have closed shelves, sometimes even with a lock. It is common within BP's referents to be rightfully afraid that books could be taken away before the registration of the loan because of unattended areas, open spaces or student's bad habits. Yet, open shelves are still an essential requirement but, in the name of a collaborative spirit, training meetings to educate teachers and students are granted.

It is asked to the school library affiliated with ISBCC to possess a minimum level of book collection based on the BP's type. The goal is the growth of the BP itself and for this reason it is requested the renovation of the structure and the increase of the collections. Some BP's, thanks to the MIUR plan for Digital School Libraries, have a digital shelf connected with the loan service. The CELBIV classification is the one used to classify documents for target users from nursery to second grade primary schools: this classification is the same used in public libraries. DEWEY is used instead in High and Middle Schools.

It has been noted that newly acquired BiblioPoints (especially the ones acquired since 2018) have many deficiencies in terms of document management. This happens because it is asked to teachers to be in charge of the school library without any training: it happens that in an attempt to organize the books they literally invent 'imaginative' classification systems that could seem easy at the beginning but instead complicate their work. For this necessity the School Service annually offers free courses on DEWEY and CELBIV for teachers.

Cataloguing is a very delicate aspect because it is an operation that must necessarily be managed by competent staff.

When signing the Protocol, some BP type C still used paper catalogues and register of loans or, in the best cases, had a subscription to free cataloguing platforms. With the help of ISBCC School Service almost no BiblioPoints use the paper system anymore.

Access to free cataloguing platform was incompatible with the growth of BiblioPoints because this platform is made for little private realities and with the increase of school libraries' book collection it became difficult to manage the cataloguing. Romans aren't the only having this difficulties: it also occurs in other places because in Italy (according to a 2016 INVALSI survey) school libraries with an electronic catalogue are still rare.

BiblioPoints, through their agreement with ISBCC, have understood the importance of cataloguing book with reliable electronic systems and they obtained by school leaders resources to invest in this sector.

'Rete Regionale delle Biblioteche Scolastiche del Lazio' (i.e., the Regional School Library Network of Latium) has an interesting experience to share for helping dividing the opac costs. The first experience is the one carried out by the 'Liceo Giulio Cesare' (a 'first generation' BiblioPoint), which is also the only school library currently

included in the ISBCC OPAC. This is a unique example of bibliographic records integration at the moment, hoping it will be replicated by other BiblioPoints.

Each school library should have full-time employees dedicated to the BiblioPoint, but in most cases this does not happen. The Legislative Decree 95/2012, paragraph 13 of art 14 provides for teaching staff committed in other task, the possibility to become administrative, technical and auxiliary staff as technical or administrative assistant. In many cases, in Italy, the school librarian is a competent teacher assigned to the school library management. This figure is often the only resource that guarantees the functioning of the library: over the years they have updated themselves with self-training, specializing in the library sector. In other cases, the referent is a teacher which dedicates just few hours per week to BP or carries out a voluntary task after duty hours; it could also be a retired teacher with a zero-cost external collaboration agreement formula. If properly trained and supported by ISBCC, teachers who have to divide their time between teaching and managing the library are a valid support for BPs.

Retired teacher are highly motivated volunteers and they can guarantee more flexible hours than the school staff. The Italian Library Association (AIB) has advocated in several institutional forums for the need for the teacher librarian job position to be recognize in order to ensure the continuity and strengthening of this profession.

BiblioPoint's evolution from the first Protocols to 2020, monitoring and survey questionnaires. Some examples of BP best practices

The increase of BiblioPoints made necessary the introduction of some features to manage the relation between BP and *City of Rome Library Services*. To monitor the state of BiblioPoints and verify the performance of the services, it was prepared a questionnaire for BP's referents. From the data collected in the last two years, it has emerged that some BiblioPoints have grown in terms of collection, spaces and presence on the territory: they are slowly approaching public libraries' standards. The 'Liceo Giulio Cesare', for example, has entered the ISBCC OPAC.

With the introduction of the three types of Protocol, the relation with the ISBCC School Protocol has also changed and now plays a fundamental role of professional support and collaboration for cultural activities.

The Civil Service project 'Libraries go to school' (by the School Service) with its ten operators, was previously able to guarantee presence shifts in almost all BiblioPoints. Over time, BPs have quadrupled and the role of civil service workers is no longer the same as it was 17 years ago: being no longer able to ensure a volunteer for each BiblioPoint, it has been decided instead to channel the resources to the neediest school libraries.

ISBCC School Service's professional support has been crucial and also led some school to open more than one BiblioPoint. This is the case of the Comprehensive Institute 'Parco della Vittoria' and the Comprehensive Institute 'Salacone' which both have two BiblioPoints in two different complexes. This condition is gradually opening up to the territory and other BiblioPoints are following their path.

The Comprehensive Institute 'Salacone' with his two BiblioPoints, has become an important cultural garrison for the Centocelle neighbourhood (in the extreme eastern suburbs of the city), while the Comprehensive Institute 'Solidati Tiburzi', with his Cardarelli BiblioPoint (in the Portuense neighbourhood), is passing after just one year from type C (for internal users) to type B (for external users, open one afternoon per week).

The 'Martellini' Bibliopoint of the homonymous Comprehensive Institute (in the isolated neighbourhood of Malagrotta, in the extreme South-Western outskirts of Rome) is the only cultural centre in an isolated area close to Via Aurelia. The people of Malagrotta are very proud of their BiblioPoint and are personally committed in it. The dedication and the perseverance of the BiblioPoint referents in keeping up teachers' and parents' interest in order to create a support network around the school library is a decisive aspect in the BP developing. Elisa's BiblioPoint, in the 'Elisa Scala' Comprehensive Institute in the Finocchio neighbourhood, is one of the virtuous examples of project's developing: Elisa's BP is now planning to open a second BP, while the first one is born thanks to the commitment of two parents who unfortunately lost their daughter at an early age and dedicated the library to her. These were just a few of the positive experiences generated by the BiblioPoint project and it is important to remember that the BiblioPoint Protocol with ISBCC is giving great results even in Roman central areas like for example the Comprehensive Institute 'Parco della Vittoria' in Prati neighbourhood. This school put promotion of books and reading at the first place and became a BP in 2018, opening two of them with the help of the School Service.

Then there is the Comprehensive Institute Petrassi that does not seem to have any particular problem. It occurs though that, especially in the complex in Via Malvano (even if it is situated in a wealthy area in the Balduina district) there is a strong presence of students from the nearby gipsy camp. This is the reason why many families in the neighbourhood prefer to enroll their children in the Petrassi's headquarter. Facing this situation, the Institute decided to start a cooperation with *City of Rome Library Services* in order to create a dialogue between the two BiblioPoints and encourage a closer approach between the two school populations.

The list of good practices in Rome BPs would be long and it is not possible to list them all here.

It has occurred, on the other hand, that some BiblioPoints found themselves no longer being able to maintain their commitment and had to stop their agreement and close their school library.

Facing this circumstances some BiblioPoints found themselves unable to renew the agreement with ISBCC but with the update of the Protocol and the introduction of the three typologies they maintained their collaboration with ISBCC and they also could be supported overcoming the difficulties and being able to guarantee a proper service according to their possibilities.

In any case, compared to the starting point, nowadays the BiblioPoint service has a greater number of partner schools and many of them are approaching a higher library standard. In some cases, the BP users can receive the requested books from any public library and at the same time any library in the municipality of Rome can have the access to BP's loan service. To reach this result, a long preparation, a strong teamwork and an economic commitment from the high school and the ISBCC has been necessary.

Final Remarks

Most of these frontier School Libraries, thanks to the BP Convention, can join the many municipal and national reading promotion projects.

In more than 17 years of activity BiblioPoints have proved to be a constantly growing reality, deeply rooted in the neighbourhood and sometimes the only one institution capable of satisfying the cultural need of citizens, especially in the most isolated areas of the vast and sometimes problematic territory of Rome.

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Books, Libraries, Librarians Facing New Challenges¹⁸⁶, by Angelo Piero Cappello¹⁸⁷

Abstract

The book, the places dedicated to its conservation, the specialists in the sector and, ultimately, even the reading processes have gradually increasingly suffered the invasion and limitation of the spaces for intervention by the digital: the tragedy of the pandemic and the consequent displacement of many activities on the web, have ended up accelerating a series of processes that have already started in an irreversible way, which is why books, libraries, librarians and their social function will all be forced together, from here to forward, to deal with the virtual. The librarians - by profession or by passion, the ministerial or the school one - will have to rethink their functions and methods of serving the public. On the Net, often the realm of trivialization and insult, something new is happening, linked to the spread of virtual communities of readers who, with competence, linguistic mastery and ability to measure themselves with reading, the book and the methods of conservation 'cataloging' constitutes the new 'library' of Babel, the wider enclosure of that horizon at which traditional interpreters are able to look.

Keywords: reading promotion; readers' community; social media.

¹⁸⁶ Translation by Luisa Marquardt.

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Introduction

The 'short century', the one all of us we should have left behind us, has instead stretched its shadow at least over the first two decades of the 21st century. It seems to have been definitively archived in the past only by this dramatic pandemic experience which ended up being the only true and irreversible break between the twentieth century and the 2000s. In the first half of the twentieth century, as far culture and its diffusion, books, libraries and librarians continued to represent the role of outposts for the promotion of books and reading, real fortresses in the defense of our knowledge and our memory. However, books, the places dedicated to their conservation, their professionals, and, ultimately, even the reading processes have increasingly suffered the invasion and limitation of spaces for intervention by the digital: the tragedy of the pandemic and the consequent displacement of many activities on the web have ended up accelerating a series of processes that had already started in an irreversible way, which is why even books, libraries, librarians and their social function will all be forced, from here on out, to deal with the virtual.

Today, however, it must be said that in part, the essential function of the book has changed or, better, the methods and ways of using reading have changed: with the advent of the web and the techniques, methods and habits of reading in environments that are always the circulation of the cultural product - be it a magazine, book or any other product linked to reading or to the practices of cultural consumption - has also changed borders, trajectories, paths of diffusion and methods of consumption and fruition.

Today the library, as a space for the conservation of knowledge and memory, tends more and more to be digital or digitized. As if to say, that the web has in fact undermined the old division of tasks and roles and modalities of cultural consumption: nowadays, in the same free space, books, newspapers, magazines, blogs, e-books, websites, instant books, profiles and web magazines play much more complementary roles than in the past: this common agon that is the web, where the boundaries between one and the other reading habits have jumped, where paradoxically it is even possible to print on demand the pages you want to read, also forces librarians - by profession or by passion, ministerial or school ones - to rethink their functions and methods of serving the public.

Reading and the new 'library' of Babel

Let it be clear from the outset: my intention is not to advocate for a radical and complete replacement of paper by digital formats, but rather to propose a more integrated approach that enhances both forms in promoting and preserving reading. As someone born in the era of Gutenberg, I maintain a cautious perspective on digital tools, recognizing them as instruments whose effectiveness depends solely on our conscious and moderate use. While the internet can sometimes descend into simplification, populism, or vulgarities, it also fosters new opportunities in the realm of cultural exchange.

The traditional spaces of official culture, once dominated by established publishing entities, have evolved. Today, there is greater freedom for those outside the commercial and power structures to engage democratically in cultural discourse. I like to report here the definition that *Nazione Indiana* (i.e., Indian Nation, <https://www.nazioneindiana.com/>), perhaps the most famous of the collective blogs, gives of itself, through a Montalian¹⁸⁸ denial: *Nazione Indiana* is not a newspaper.

Mentre la situazione attuale è che ciascuno viene relegato nel suo ruolo e nel suo campo e trova uno spazio solo se accetta di rimanere confinato entro questi limiti, delegando a specialisti e mediatori il compito di raffigurarlo e di collocarlo in una apposita nicchia preordinata, in un piccolo gioco chiuso e – a noi pare – senza futuro.

La rete ci permette invece di tornare a una economia di scambio da Nazione Indiana dove contano soprattutto le cose che facciamo – che ognuno fa a suo modo scegliendo di volta in volta argomenti, stili, generi che lo attirano di più – e non la nostra 'qualifica professionale' preconfezionata.¹⁸⁹

¹⁸⁸ Eugenio Montale (1896-1981), Italian poet, writer, editor, translator, politician, senator, Nobel Prize Laureate in Literature in 1975. (T/N)

¹⁸⁹ See Section 'Chi siamo' ('About us'), all URL <https://www.nazioneindiana.com/chi-siamo/>; i.e., While the current situation is that everyone is relegated to his role and field and finds a space only if he agrees to remain confined within these limits, delegating to specialists and mediators the task of depicting him and placing him in a special preordained niche, in a small closed game and - it seems to us - without a future. The network, on the other hand, allows us to return to an Indian Nation exchange economy where the things we do matter above all - which everyone does in their own way, choosing from time to time topics, styles, genres that attract them the most - and not ours 'professional qualification' prepackaged. (Translated by L.M.)

Or rethinking the definition of itself that gives another online magazine, *404 File not Found* (<https://quattrocentoquattro.wordpress.com/>):

Siamo studenti, ma anche precari, attivisti, free-lance. Siamo un pezzo di quinto stato che prova a riconoscersi a partire dagli spazi in cui vive, dai saperi che produce, e dai desideri da cui è attraversato.

Ci confrontiamo quotidianamente, in rete e dal vivo, con i soggetti, le associazioni e le comunità che partecipano al dibattito culturale italiano.¹⁹⁰

In this context, it becomes evident that non-experts, particularly avid readers and contributors on social media or specialized platforms like *Mangialibri* (<https://www.mangialibri.com/>), often exhibit a deep understanding and eloquence in discussing books, the methods of conservation, cataloguing and reading. This challenges traditional critics and academics who may not engage with the dynamic conversations shaping the online cultural landscape—the modern 'library' of Babel, rich with diverse voices and perspectives.

In light of these developments, what role can books, libraries, and librarians play today? Is there a distinct place for them in the global digital sphere? And if so, how can they adapt and contribute to the promotion and preservation of reading in this rapidly changing social and technological environment?

Final Remarks

The answers are not easy, and the challenge they pose is no less: the entire publishing chain - from the first 'producer' of content, the author, to the elements of more widespread diffusion that libraries and their professionals are - is working hard to find spaces for integration and cooperation between paper and digital. The material support of the book and its medium of diffusion, on the other hand, cannot and must not alter the function and use of the contents.

¹⁹⁰ See Section 'Chi siamo' ('About us'), all'URL <https://quattrocentoquattro.wordpress.com/chi-siamo/>; i.e., We are students, but also temporary workers, activists, freelancers. We are a fifth state piece that tries to recognize itself starting from the spaces in which it lives, from the knowledge it produces, and from the desires it passes through. We compare daily, online and live, with the institutions, associations and communities that participate in the Italian cultural debate. (Translated by L.M.)

If it is true, as the research of careful neuroscientists shows (and among all it would be enough to mention those of Maryanne Wolf¹⁹¹), that the ‘fast’ reading that is carried out in a digital environment even modifies the neuronal map responsible for cognition, reducing its extension and functions compared to ‘profound’ reading that is carried out on traditional supports, the ‘replacement’ of the physical environment by the digital one (even if progressive) is not to be carefully pursued, but their integration and their contiguity and continuity. And in this process of integration and continuity - between physical and digital environments -, a fundamental role still belongs to the library and librarians: inside and outside the school walls, inside and outside the Net, to stem, manage and make usable the infinite library that is on the web.

Within the framework of the innovations provided, moreover, by Law 15/2020, school libraries and the regional ‘hub schools’ cannot fail to see in the Center for books and reading (‘Cepell’, www.cepell.it) a valid support and a supportive ‘companion’ of adventure in building a more widespread, free and open access to books and reading for children.

¹⁹¹ See, for example, *Proust and the Squid: The Story and Science of the Reading Brain*. Cambridge: Icon Books (2012), and *Reader Come Home: The Reading Brain in a Digital World*. HarperCollins (2018), both published in Italy by Vita e Pensiero.

The Law for the Promotion and Support of Reading: Focus on School Libraries¹⁹², by Maurizio Caminito¹⁹³

Abstract

Some reflections are presented concerning the possible role of school libraries in promoting reading, in the light of Law 13 February 2000, No. 15, containing the ‘Provisions for the promotion and support of reading’, approved by unanimous vote of the Parliament and after a long process that has seen various proposals follow one another and confront each other for at least a decade.

The result of this long joint work, inside and outside the Italian Parliament, despite some limitations, marks a very important point of reference for the diffusion of reading in Italy and recognizes the role that school libraries can play in this area.

Keywords: advocacy; school library; Forum del Libro; Law 13 February 2000, No. 15 - Provisions for the promotion and support of reading; promotion of reading; Reading Act.

¹⁹² Translation by Luisa Marquardt.

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Provisions for the promotion and support of reading: the role of school libraries

In the field of promoting reading in Italy, the most significant event is certainly represented by the recent approval of Law No. 15 'Provisions for the promotion and support of reading'.¹⁹⁴

The approval of this law, it is important to emphasize, took place with a unanimous vote of the Parliament and comes after a long process that has seen several proposals follow one another and confront each other for at least a decade.

The 'Forum del Libro' (i.e., Book Forum), like many other associative and professional entities, tried to contribute ideas and proposals, which would define as complete a framework as possible of the interventions to be programmed.

Now we must be aware that the result of this long joint work, inside and outside the Italian Parliament, despite some limitations to which we will return, marks a very important point of reference for the dissemination of reading in Italy.

In fact, from the first article of the new law a fundamental principle is affirmed:

'La Repubblica, in attuazione degli articoli 2, 3 e 9 della Costituzione, favorisce e sostiene la lettura quale mezzo per lo sviluppo della conoscenza, la diffusione della cultura, la promozione del progresso civile, sociale ed economico della Nazione, la formazione e il benessere dei cittadini. La Repubblica promuove interventi volti a sostenere e a incentivare la produzione, la conservazione, la circolazione e la fruizione dei libri come strumenti preferenziali per l'accesso ai contenuti e per la loro diffusione, nonché per il miglioramento degli indicatori del benessere equo e sostenibile (BES).'

The law defines several actions, including:

- the need to adopt a National Action Plan for the promotion of reading, every three years, which identifies and defines aims, priorities and general goals;
- the adoption of the 'Patto della lettura' (i.e., the 'Reading Pact') as the main tool for involving libraries and other public entities, especially

¹⁹⁴ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2020/03/10/20G00023/sg>

schools, as well as private entities operating in the area interested in promoting reading;

- the annual bestowal of the ‘Capitale Italiana del Libro’ (‘Italian Book Capital’) Award to a city that shows a particularly effective project for the promotion of reading in its territory;
- the establishment of a ‘Culture Charter’ as a measure to fight educational and cultural poverty;
- the attribution of the ‘Quality Bookshop’ title and the granting of tax incentives for bookstores;
- the amendment of the legislation on discounts on the selling price of books (media attention was mainly focused on this topic, in the presence, however, of a profound division within the book supply chain).

But the aspect on which we focus here is the set of initiatives planned for the ‘Promotion of reading at school’.

As it is well known, in the Italian system there is neither the school library nor, much less, the school librarian job position. From this point of view, the new law only partially resolves this age-old question, even if it marks, however, a point in the desired direction.

The formula that has been adopted provides for the identification of a series of schools that operate as a ‘hub responsible for the school library service of all levels’ and that those schools can ‘organize training for the networked schools’ staff, involved in the management of school libraries’.

There is therefore no obligation to establish school libraries, nor the school librarian job position is formally defined, but the new law opens up to an organization of the library service in the school environment (moreover, by explicitly providing for a collaboration between the networked schools and those of the territory, with particular reference to public libraries) and a path of training and professionalization of the staff, who takes care of and will manage the school libraries, is launched.

As you can well understand, faced with such a solution, the professional community is divided between those who emphasize the limits of what is stated by the new law and those who accept the glimmers contained therein.

Final remarks

In support of the incurable optimists' position (including myself), it should be emphasized that the law intervenes in a situation where, after years of inactivity, in Italy the school library is at the center of a very relevant series of institutional and otherwise initiatives.

I mention two ones. The first concerns an institutional intervention and is the National Plan for Digital School ('Piano nazionale scuola digitale' - PNSD), very well structured, launched by the Ministry of Education in 2016, which explicitly provides for an action in favor of 'School Libraries as literacy environments for use of digital information resources' and to which hundreds of Italian schools could access and use the assigned funds to set up or upgrade their school libraries.

The second, which we could define as a bottom-up action, is the recent birth of a coordination of existing school library networks,¹⁹⁵ established by the 'First national conference of school library networks: network strategies for a sustainable school library', held in Rome, at LUMSA, on 30 November 2019.¹⁹⁶

All this shows that attention to the school libraries situation in Italy is evolving positively, also and above all thanks to the tireless work of numerous colleagues who have never stopped dedicating their passion and intelligence to them.

¹⁹⁵ The 'CRBS - Coordinamento delle Reti di Biblioteche Scolastiche', i.e., the National Coordination of School Library Networks was then formally established in 2020; the school in charge of the national coordination is the Liceo Classico (Grammar School) 'Massimo D'Azeglio', Turin. The CRBS website URL is: <http://www.bibliotechescolastiche.com>. (TN)

¹⁹⁶ <https://www.aib.it/attivita/2019/77590-prim-convegno-nazionale-delle-reti-di-biblioteche-scolastiche-strategie-di-rete-per-una-biblioteca-scolastica-sostenibile/>

Promoting and Supporting Reading Through the School Library,¹⁹⁷ by Rosa Maiello¹⁹⁸

Abstract

The Italian Law 13 February 2020, No. 15 *Provisions for the promotion and support of reading* affirms the constitutional value of reading from early childhood and throughout life in the context of public policies for knowledge and provides the reference regulatory framework within which public and private entities can contribute to the implementation of a national reading plan. In this context, the central role of public libraries and school libraries is recognized.

This contribution focuses in particular on the role assigned to school libraries by law, pointing out how this legislation incorporates some recommendations made by the AIB, in order to aim at effective and sustainable organizational models that leverage, on the one hand, on the professionalism of school librarians and, on the other hand, on cooperation between public libraries and school libraries and on a multilevel coordination of library services within the school system.

Keywords: public library; school library; school librarian; cooperation; Law 13 February 2020, No. 15.

¹⁹⁷ Translation by Luisa Marquardt.

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In 2017, AREAPROGETTI won the Torino fa scuola competition, promoted by the 'Compagnia di San Paolo' and the Agnelli Foundation, for the restructuring of the 'Giovanni Pascoli' Middle School, a national pilot project that combines architectural principles with innovative teaching concepts: the building was opened in September 2019. In 2018 the AP Studio won the design competition for the 'Enrico Panzacchi' Secondary School in Ozzano dell'Emilia, under construction. Currently the AP Studio is active in the planning of innovative school building interventions, in collaboration with the Reggio Children Foundation, the ENEL Cuore Onlus Foundation and the Turin Polytechnic.

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